

SMARTTEES: Deliverable 4.2 (Report)

Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions in SMARTTEES case studies

April 2021

Project Full Title		Social innovation Modelling Approaches to Realizing Transition to Energy Efficiency and Sustainability
Project Acronym	SMARTEES	
Grant Agreement No.	763912	
Coordinator	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)	
Project duration	May 2018 – October 2021 (42 months)	
Project website	www.local-social-innovation.eu	
Work Package		
Work Package	WP4 Choice behaviour and energy usage: knowledge co-production	
Deliverable	D4.2 Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions in SMARTEES case studies	
Delivery Date	30.04.2021 (month 36)	
Author(s)	Ruth Wilson; Kathryn Colley; Phoebe Somervail; Gary Polhill; Tony Craig; Doug Salt (JHI)	
Contributor(s)	Andrea Scalco (JHI) Laurentiu-Gabriel Tiru; Patricia Albuлесcu; Irina Macinga (UVT) Giuseppe Pellegrini-Masini; Erica Löfström (NTNU) Wander Jager; Patrycja Antosz; Loes Bouman (RUG) Adina Dumitru, Isabel Lema Blanco, Alejandro Rodríguez Árias (UDC)	
Reviewer(s) (if applicable)	Christian A. Klöckner (NTNU) Gabriele Quinti (K&I)	
Level	Public (PU)	X
	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	

Keywords

Social innovation; energy transitions; choice behaviour; data analysis; agent-based models

This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project SMARTEES – Social Innovation Modelling Approaches to Realizing Transition to Energy Efficiency and Sustainability. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 763912.

The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the INEA nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Contents

Contents.....	3
Executive summary	4
Part One: Integrated overview of choice behaviour.....	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Data analysis protocol.....	7
3. Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions.....	10
4. Discussion.....	16
Part Two: Cluster-level analyses	18
5. First cluster: Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning (Zürich and Groningen)	19
6. Second cluster: Island renaissance based on renewable energy production (Samsø and El Hierro).....	40
7. Third cluster: Energy efficiency in district regeneration (Malmö and Stockholm)	54
8. Fourth cluster: Urban mobility with superblocks (Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona)	59
9. Fifth cluster: Co-ordinated, tailored, and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty (Aberdeen and Timișoara)	72
Appendices.....	84
Appendix 6: Additional Tables for El Hierro.....	85
Appendix 8: Additional Tables for Barcelona and Vitoria-Gasteiz.....	87
Appendix 9: Additional Tables for Aberdeen and Timișoara	102

Executive summary

This report presents an overview of the factors affecting choice behaviour in the ten SMARTEES social innovation (SI) cases and considers them collectively across the five SMARTEES clusters.¹

The report comprises two parts. **Part One** begins by introducing the purpose of the deliverable and describing our project-wide approach to data collection, curation, preparation and analysis, which was developed during a series of data analysis workshops held online during the spring and summer of 2020. In the workshops, partners discussed issues relating to data harmonisation, data cleaning, and missing data and imputation. Finally, the partners presented initial findings from their own cases. The approach was therefore participatory and designed to be flexible enough to respond to the analysis requirements of individual cases. A set of core principles underpinning the cases' data analysis emerged from the workshops and comprised: preservation of raw data, backing up and version control, keeping track of steps, sharing plans and analyses with other partners, and regular communication between modellers and social scientists. These principles were applied in each of the SMARTEES cases to a diverse collection of datasets, which we outline briefly in this deliverable.

We then present an integrated overview of choice behaviour in energy transitions, based on this analysis. Drawing together findings from across the cases, we find that the factors affecting choice behaviour fall into seven broad categories:

- Socio-demographic variables
- The influence of social networks
- Day-to-day behaviour patterns
- General attitudes towards the environment and society
- Experience or knowledge relating to the SI
- Place-related variables
- Financial considerations

We show which variables are relevant in which cases, outline the similarities and differences between the cases and discuss the meaning of the findings for our understanding of choice behaviour relating to energy transitions, emphasising the importance of considering the needs of different places, the requirements of different groups of people, and the influence of people's social networks in instilling and spreading trust.

Part Two of the report presents detailed analyses for each cluster, which form the basis of the integrated overview presented in Part One and include more depth on each case and comparisons of findings at the cluster level.

¹ First cluster: Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning (Zürich and Groningen); second cluster: Island renaissance based on renewable energy production (Samsø and El Hierro); third cluster: Energy efficiency in district regeneration (Malmö and Stockholm); fourth cluster: Urban mobility with superblocks (Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona); fifth cluster: Co-ordinated, tailored, and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty (Aberdeen and Timișoara).

Part One:

Integrated overview of choice behaviour

1. Introduction

This report synthesises the findings of the primary and secondary data analyses undertaken in the ten SMARTEES case studies, across the five case clusters:

- First cluster: Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning. A defining feature of this social innovation is the participatory development and adoption of a holistic and persistent mobility plan, in which all city development and planning follows a coordinated approach focussed on making the city mobility efficient and sustainable. Reference cases analysed within the scope of SMARTEES: Zürich (Switzerland) and Groningen (the Netherlands).
- Second cluster: Island renaissance based on renewable energy production. This social innovation centres around the mobilization of island residents and public and private stakeholders to achieve energy independence through renewable energy production and energy efficiency measures, thus becoming a means to revive island communities. Reference cases analysed within the scope of SMARTEES: Samsø (Denmark) and El Hierro (Spain).
- Third cluster: Energy efficiency in district regeneration. This social innovation triggers district regeneration through hard and soft measures, such as local energy production and energy efficiency measures, urban green spaces, transport system transition measures and citizen participation. Reference cases analysed within the scope of SMARTEES: Malmö and Stockholm (Sweden).
- Fourth cluster: Urban mobility with superblocks. Superblocks are an urban innovation that introduces low-carbon mobility practices through the reorganization of urban space, which minimizes the use of motorized modes of transportation. Superblocks help to reorganise urban space into car-free areas aimed to maximize public space and foster social and economic interactions at the street level while keeping private cars and public transport outside of the neighbourhoods. Reference cases analysed within the scope of SMARTEES: Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona (Spain).
- Fifth cluster: Co-ordinated, tailored, and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty (Aberdeen and Timișoara). This social innovation is characterized by public authorities working in coordination with supply companies and civil society organisation in order to implement energy efficiency measures for houses and buildings with the aim of fighting fuel poverty with a tailored and inclusive approach. Reference cases analysed within the scope of SMARTEES: Aberdeen (Scotland) and Timișoara (Romania).

In synthesising the WP4 findings we adopted a two-step process. In the first step, cases within a cluster reported their key findings, drawing comparisons at the case cluster level. The contributions from each of the case clusters were then brought together and the conclusions on the factors affecting choice behaviour in the cases summarised at the project-level by the James Hutton Institute. The implications of the analyses for representing choice behaviour in the agent-based models have been drawn out, both at the cluster- and at the project-level, with the input of the modellers.

The report is divided into two parts. Part One, after this introduction (Section 1), describes the WP4 data analysis workshops and data analysis protocol developed through the workshops, as well as a summary of the data sources utilised and key variables of interest in each case (Section 2). Section 3 goes on to present the integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions at the project-level, structured by categories of factors found to affect behavioural choices in the cases. Section 4 discusses these findings and what they mean for our understanding of choice behaviour.

Part Two presents the summaries and integration of findings within each of the case clusters and provides the detailed analyses on which Part One is based.

2. Data analysis protocol

This integrated overview of choice behaviour in energy transitions represents the culmination of an extensive process of data collection, curation, preparation and analysis in each of the SMARTEES cases. The process has been framed by a set of common principles and procedures that were discussed and agreed among the SMARTEES partners during a series of data analysis workshops. This section describes the nature of these workshops and summarises the protocol that emerged from them.

2.1 Data analysis workshops

The purpose of the data analysis workshops (Task 4.8) was to bring partners together to discuss all of the primary and secondary data they hold, ensuring proper interoperability for use in the agent-based models. Specifically, they aimed to:

- Prepare data for input to, and calibration and validation of the models
- Harmonize approaches to analysing data among modellers and social scientists

The task lead partner was JHI; other partners involved were NTNU, K&I, UDC, UOT and UG. Initially, a two-day workshop was planned for 30 and 31 March 2020, hosted by JHI in Aberdeen, which both modellers and social scientists from partner institutions would attend. However, restrictions on travel in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, announced across Europe in early March, made it clear that a face-to-face workshop would no longer be tenable, and it was agreed at the WP Leaders Meeting on 11 March 2020 that we would plan an alternative approach.

Thereafter, a series of discussions at JHI considered how the main activities planned for the workshop could be conducted without face-to-face contact between partners and allowing for flexibility in partners' timelines as they adjusted plans according to the changing Covid-19 restrictions in their countries. The result was an extended schedule of online workshops that shifted focus according to the requirements of partners who were furthest ahead with data collection and preparation, and a set of protocols, agreed during the workshops, that all partners could draw on at the appropriate time for them. The workshops took place as follows, with a broad focus on the topics listed and some overlap between the sessions:

- 30 March 2020 – Workshop 1 – Data Harmonisation
- 20 April 2020 – Workshop 2 – Data Cleaning
- 7 May 2020 – Workshop 3 – Missing Data and Imputation
- 29 September 2020 – Workshop 4 – Presentation of Initial Findings

Between the workshops, work continued offline and in online cluster meetings to progress data preparation tasks. By distributing activities over a period of time, the intention was to allow for participation within and between teams and to ensure the development of a robust but flexible approach to data harmonisation and analysis that would provide a solid grounding for the models. This was also an important opportunity for modelling teams and non-modelling teams to elaborate their expectations, ensuring a common understanding with respect to data requirements.

2.2 Data analysis protocol

The data preparation principles agreed during the workshops included:

1. Preserving raw data – partners agreed that the raw data from surveys and other methods would be preserved as collected, with data transformations made to copies of the original file(s). This minimises the possibility of the original dataset becoming corrupted or overwritten

- and means that all steps in data preparation and analysis can be replicated from the original data, assuming steps are adequately documented (point 3).
2. Backing up and version control – partners agreed to put in place secure back-up measures as they worked with their data in case of loss or corruption. JHI recommended using some form of version control and itself used Github to keep track of changes to data, documents and code automatically, but suggested that this could be done using other methods depending on the requirements of each case.
 3. Keeping track of steps – during the workshops we discussed the importance of recording every step taken in preparing and analysing data, so that the project has a clear history of decisions and changes made, for example in cleaning and merging datasets, and the steps can be replicated if needed. Perl and R scripts as well as SPSS syntax were variously employed by cases to this end.
 4. Sharing – more generally, three Google Docs were shared with colleagues responsible for data analysis in which they were encouraged to describe their a) Data Cleaning Plans, b) Data Imputation Plans, and c) Social Network Initialization Plans. This laid the foundation for sharing more detailed aspects of the analyses than could be communicated during the workshops and meant that cases could learn from one another, since, as a consequence of Covid-19, they were at different stages of collection and analysis at different times. Cases were also encouraged to share methods and approaches within their clusters to provide peer support between the workshops, and project-wide support was ongoing after the final workshop for those cases that were lagging in data collection, to help them to catch up.
 5. Finally, partners agreed that data preparation and analysis tasks should be carried out in regular communication between modellers and social scientists, so that all parties understood the transformations undergone by the data, were involved in the process and had opportunities to consider and address any issues specific to the models or the broader analysis.

These core principles were designed to establish a common culture of good practice across the SMARTEES partners that was founded on transparency, collaboration and replicability. Given the different circumstances of each case, they were intended to allow partners to comply according to their own requirements and capabilities and were not prescriptive about the methods or software used in doing so.

2.3 Case and cluster-wide approaches to data analysis

The data analysis protocol underpinned a diverse set of approaches to data collection and analysis in the different SMARTEES cases. As noted elsewhere in the project, this diversity emerged partly in response to the different data requirements for responding to each case's research questions, partly due to the availability of good sources of secondary data in some cases and not others, and partly because of changes of data collection plans made in response to the Covid-19 restrictions in different countries. Table 2.1 provides a snapshot of the different data used to determine choice behaviour in the different cases. The data analysis protocol ensured some degree of project-level consistency in order to produce comparable results while allowing sufficient flexibility to account for the different kinds of data approaches according to analysis.

Table 2.1 Approaches to data collection in the SMARTEES cases

Cluster	Case	Focus	Secondary Data	Primary Data Collection	Dependent Variable/Key Behaviour
1 - Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning	Zürich	Mobility planning	Masters thesis, statistical yearbooks, neighbourhood statistics, population survey	Interviews with stakeholders; online survey	Voting to keep Limmatquai closed to traffic
	Groningen	Mobility planning	Referendum report, statistical yearbooks, websites	Interviews with stakeholders; online survey	Voting to keep Noorderplantsoen closed to traffic
2 - Island renaissance based on renewable energy production	Samsø	Island intervention	Secondary data analysis reported in deliverables: D6.1, D3.1, and D3.4	Semi-structured interviews	Diffusion of heat network
	El Hierro	Renewable energy (technological) innovations	Island reports and statistics, press releases, websites, local news/media, social media	Semi-structured interviews; field data; multi-stakeholder policy workshops; face-to-face survey	Acceptance and adoption of renewable energies
3 - Energy efficiency in district regeneration	Malmö	Local eco-neighbourhood	Secondary data analysis reported in deliverables: D6.1, D3.1, and D3.4	Interviews; joint workshop with city managers, researchers and consultants	Acceptance of social innovations for district regeneration
	Stockholm	Retrofitting energy efficiency measures	Secondary data analysis reported in deliverables: D6.1, D3.1, and D3.4	Interviews; joint workshop with city managers, researchers and consultants	Willingness to retrofit energy efficiency measures
4 - Urban mobility with superblocks	Barcelona	Social acceptability of superblocks	Neighbourhood statistics, press releases, websites, local news and media, social media	Semi-structured interviews with policy makers/ supporters/ stakeholders/ beneficiaries; face-to-face survey	Individual and social endorsement of superblocks
	Vitoria-Gasteiz	Social acceptability of superblocks	Neighbourhood statistics, CIVITAS survey, press releases, websites, local news and media, social media	Semi-structured interviews with policy makers/ supporters/ stakeholders/ beneficiaries; face-to-face and telephone survey	Individual and social endorsement of superblocks
5 - Co-ordinated, tailored and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty	Aberdeen	District heating network	Stakeholder interviews, Census data, Scottish Household Survey, planning documents, neighbourhood statistics	Online and postal survey	Likelihood of joining a district heating network
	Timișoara	Energy efficiency and heat network retrofit	Previous deliverables, websites, local news, spatial data (local statistics)	Online survey	Uptake of a district heating network ²

² Since data were not collected directly regarding heat network uptake in Timișoara, three variables derived from survey data (environmentally responsible behavior, responsible energy behavior, and environmental concern) are proposed as indicators of choice behaviour and heat network uptake will be tested for sensitivity to these variables.

3. Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions

3.1 Introduction

This section takes a holistic look at the factors affecting choice behaviour across the SMARTTEES cases. It draws on Part Two, in which individual clusters present their approaches to discovering variables of relevance to their SIs through analysing their respective sources of data. Here, we highlight the similarities and differences between the cases and consider the broader implications for our understanding of choice behaviour in energy-related social innovations.

Seven broad categories of factors affecting choice behaviour were applied across the ten SMARTTEES cases:

- Socio-demographic variables
- The influence of social networks
- General attitudes towards the environment and society
- Day-to-day behaviour patterns
- Experience or knowledge relating to the SI
- Place-related variables
- Financial considerations

These categories are outlined in Table 3.1, alongside the particular factors considered and their salience in each case. The table indicates that there is a broad spread of influencing factors, reflecting the diversity of the social innovations that comprise the SMARTTEES cases. It is worth noting that these factors also influence each other. In particular, socio-demographic factors such as age and gender can influence the amount of trust people place in their social networks as well as their attitudes towards the environment, which in turn influences their engagement with the SIs. Factors and how they affect energy choices are considered in turn below.

Table 3.1 Factors affecting choice behaviour in the SMARTEES cases

Category	Factor	Cluster 1 Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning		Cluster 2 Island renaissance based on renewable energy production		Cluster 3 Energy efficiency in district regeneration		Cluster 4 Urban mobility with superblocks		Cluster 5 Co-ordinated, tailored and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty	
		Zürich	Groningen	Samsø	El Hierro	Malmö	Stockholm	Barcelona	Vitoria-Gasteiz	Aberdeen	Timișoara
Socio-demographic	Age	X								X	X
	Gender		X							X	X
	Education	X	X								
	Status			X	X						
	Life stage		X								
Networks	Household		X								
	Family		X								
	Organisations						X				
	Information									X	X
	Media			X							
	Project leaders				X						
Attitudes	Environment	X		X		X	X	X			X
	Society			X		X	X	X			
Behaviour	Cycling	X	X								
	Walking	X									
	Public transport	X									
Experience	Knowledge					X	X				
	Adversity					X			X	X	
	Awareness							X	X		
	Engagement							X	X		
Place	Attachment	X					X			X	X
	Identity				X				X		
	Image					X	X		X		
	Pride in place							X			
	Aesthetics							X			
Finance	Benefits			X	X	X					
	Support			X			X				
	Economy			X	X			X	X		

3.2 Socio-demographic factors

The influence of socio-demographic factors on people's choice behaviour was considered in each of the SMARTEES social innovations and found to be of particular relevance in Clusters 1 (Zürich and Groningen), 2 (Samsø and El Hierro) and 5 (Aberdeen and Timișoara).

Gender had an effect on behaviour in the Groningen, Aberdeen and Timișoara surveys. In Groningen, women were slightly more likely to vote for the closure of the park than men. In Timișoara, women demonstrated more responsible energy behaviour and environmental concern. These findings

support previous studies that showed women have stronger pro-environmental beliefs, values and attitudes than men (Dietz et al, 2002; McCright, 2010). Furthermore, in both Timișoara and Aberdeen, women tended to place greater trust and importance in some information sources than men. This suggests that, in addition to having a direct effect on levels of environmental concern in some cases, gender may also influence how people respond to sources of information about energy-related social innovations, indirectly influencing the decisions they make.

Age played a role in the Aberdeen, Timișoara and Zürich cases, albeit with different implications. In the Aberdeen survey, older people (65 to 74-year-olds) were more likely than people of younger working age (35 to 44-year-olds) to be in favour of the SI, and older respondents (aged over 35) to the Timișoara survey were more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviour. In the Zürich survey, however, older people were less likely to be in favour of the SI than people of working age. These contrasting findings are due to the different nature of the SIs and how they are experienced by different age groups at different stages of life. In Zürich, the lower level of support for the road closure among older people is hypothesized to be due to them remembering a time when the road was less congested. In Aberdeen, older people's greater propensity to join a heat network is likely to be due to them being at a more settled stage of life in which they are spending more time at home and feel they are unlikely to move and will therefore experience the longer-term cost and efficiency savings of investing in their heating system. In the case of Timișoara, place attachment may be an intervening variable, with older people also expressing greater attachment to the city than younger people. This finding is consistent with the literature, in which feelings of connection to place have been found to increase with age (Hey, 1998) and are also associated with pro-environmental behaviour. An age-related effect was also observed in Groningen, where survey respondents with young children (under the age of 13) were more likely to vote in favour of the SI since the lack of cars made the park a quieter and safer place to play, again underlining the importance of thinking about life stage, as well as age, when considering the impact of energy transitions, albeit the impact on different life stages can be very specific to the particular SI.

Level of education was found to be a relevant factor in Zürich and Groningen. In Zürich, the survey found that, the higher the level of education, the more likely people were to vote in favour of the social innovation (closure of the road), supporting previous research which has shown that education improves people's environmental awareness. In Groningen, men with a higher level of education were more likely to vote for the park's closure than men who were educated to a moderate level.

In Samsø, social status was found to play a role. Farmers held high status in the community because of their affluence and social connections, which was an enabling factor in their participation in the social innovation. Conversely, some residents' lower social status acted as a barrier to participation.

3.3 Networks, influence and trust

Networks, influence, and trust were found to affect respondents' choice behaviours throughout several of the SMARTEES clusters. Differences of gender, age, and barriers resulting from a lack of trust were reported.

In Aberdeen, Timișoara, and Groningen, the various actors within respondents' networks of information sources differed in level of importance and therefore influence. In all three cases, household and extended family were reported to be the two most important sources of information when making energy efficiency and voting decisions. In Aberdeen and Timișoara, this was also found to be the case when examining the levels of trust in respondents' network of information sources. In the Aberdeen sample, age was significantly negatively associated with the levels of trust and importance across several of the potential information sources. In both cases, there were significant

differences according to gender across a number of the sources. For these information sources, women tended to give higher trust/importance scores than men.

In El Hierro, a lack of trust in project leaders following multiple misunderstandings within the population was reported. The distrust in project leaders resulted in a difficult and persisting barrier to SI adoption that promoters had to cope with. Similarly, in Stockholm a barrier to residents' engagement in the intervention was a lack of trust in the organisations associated with running the project (the municipality's housing company (Svenska Bostäder) and the union of tenants).

3.4 Behaviour

Patterns of behaviour among residents were found to be a predictor of energy transition choices in Zürich and Groningen, closely linked to the nature of the social innovation. In Zürich, survey respondents who moved around the city by walking, cycling and using public transport – pro-environmental mobility behaviours – were mostly in favour of the road closure, while more than half of those who used cars and motorbikes were not. In the Groningen survey, the ability to cycle safely through the park was mentioned as an important factor in people's decision to close the park to traffic.

Behavioural patterns were also examined in Aberdeen and Timișoara but no explicit links were found between pro-environmental behaviour and support for the social innovation. Rather, attitudes towards the environment were a stronger predictor of support for the SI in Timișoara and were also found to be prominent in other cases.

3.5 Attitudes

In the case of Samsø, attitudinal variables appeared to play a role in the decision-making of actors. In particular, pro-environmental attitudes were a moderate to strong variable that motivated local government, farmers, and the energy academy to engage in the SI's initiatives.

In Malmö, a 'general environmentalist predisposition' appeared to be a key factor that acted as a driver for most actors and to various degrees. While a general environmental predisposition was a primary driver for the MKB (Malmö municipality's housing company), it was also a secondary driver for the municipality. Further, it was a strong driver for some of the NGOs involved in the project and for a subgroup of residents involved in a sustainable living project (the Augustenborg Greenhouse residents). However, these pro-environmental views did not extend to the general group of residents of the neighbourhood, resulting in less motivation to engage in the project than the subgroup.

Pro-environmental attitudes played a key role in Stockholm, particularly for the environmental health administration (city department). These attitudes were a weak driver for the urban planning administration and a moderate driver for the politicians involved in the project. Perceived benefits of the social innovation included improving the environmental quality of the neighbourhood and achieving more social inclusion. In Barcelona, an exploratory factorial analysis found environmental quality to be one of five types of needs that were relevant to how interventions were perceived by residents.

In Samsø, Malmö, Stockholm, and Barcelona prosocial attitudes were considered a factor with the potential to influence actors' choice behaviour. Social inclusion was a driver for the Energy Academy in Samsø; the SI was perceived as being a suitable method of delivery to encourage the increase of inclusion. In Stockholm, social inclusion was a major driver for the organisations involved and for the design and implementation of the SI itself. Through a lack of neighbourhood consultation by the city council in Barcelona, social contestation arose in various sectors of the population living and/or working in the area. The lack of citizen engagement resulted in a negative perception of the SI developing in both the local neighbourhood and the wider city, and the lack inclusion of stakeholders

and civil organisations contributed to the “social polarization” that followed. However, the city council learnt from this and adopted a policy of actively engaging citizens in discussions about and implementations of new superblocs, eventually leading to wider acceptance of the model.

3.6 Experience

In several of the cases, residents' previous experience or knowledge of the social innovation – or of similar innovations – was found to influence their likelihood of supporting it. This was especially evident in Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona, where residents who were aware of good examples of the social innovation (in both cases, an exemplary pilot superbloc) had a more positive perception of the SI and were more inclined to favour its replication because they could see its benefits with their own eyes. Public engagement about the SI was also found to be important in Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona, as residents' involvement in the design process meant that models of innovation could respond to local needs and foster a sense of ownership, albeit this could mean slowing down the planning and design process to enable residents to become involved in tangible ways. In both cases, this principle extended to ensuring that information about the SI was communicated accurately and proactively throughout relevant parts of the cities to counter “fake news” and encourage positive discourse.

The importance of knowledge relating to the SI was also highlighted in the Malmö and Stockholm cases. In Malmö, knowledge and skills enabled people to see the opportunity and for project leaders to move forward with implementing the SI. In Stockholm, lack of knowledge and skills meant that residents mistrusted the organisations coordinating the SI and were initially disengaged.

Finally, adverse experiences relating to the SI can influence people's support. In Malmö, one of the main factors driving support for the SI was its perceived impact on flooding, which had been an issue in the area. In the case of Aberdeen, survey respondents who had experienced heating hardship (indicating that they had found it difficult to heat their home in the past year) were more likely to support the SI by joining a district heating scheme, suggesting that personal experience of heating hardship may motivate people to make a choice in favour of this particular energy transition.

3.7 Place

Throughout the clusters, five factors relating to place were reported to affect choice behaviour: place attachment, place identity, neighbourhood image, pride in neighbourhood, and neighbourhood aesthetics. These factors varied between clusters and were found to be influenced by trust, age, home ownership, heating hardship, and having problems with the current boiler/heating system.

Place attachment was examined due to its association with various pro-environmental behaviours and potential to affect people's sense of care for their local environment as well as their propensity to make a long-term financial investment in their home. Attachment to place positively influenced the choice behaviours of research participants in Zürich, Aberdeen, Timișoara, and Stockholm. A key difference reported in Stockholm was that the initial effect of place attachment resulted in resistance to the implementation of the intervention. It was only in the later stages, when the institutional actors gained the trust of residents, that place attachment worked as a driver instead. Both Aberdeen and Timișoara reported an effect of age on place attachment. Place attachment was a significant factor in Aberdeen's regression model when grouped with age, heating hardship, and problems with current boiler/heating system. Timișoara found significant differences between age groups; in line with the literature, results showed that the older age group reported stronger attachment to the city/surrounding suburbs. Further, Timișoara reported a significant effect of home ownership on place attachment: the average level of place attachment for the group of owners is higher than that of the ‘other’ group.

Most of the respondents (90%) in Zürich rather/completely agreed that they felt attached to Zürich city. Of those who rather/completely agreed with the statement “*I am very attached to Zürich city*”, the majority (92.4%) were in favour of keeping Limmatquai closed. Notably, of those who did not express an opinion on their attachment to Zürich city or disagreed with the statement completely, fewer are in favour of keeping Limmatquai closed (86.5%). Prosocial values were a major driver in Stockholm for the design and implementation of the social innovation. For residents, the key prosocial value was place attachment. Stockholm’s partner city, Malmö, did not report an effect of place attachment.

Neighbourhood image was found to be an important factor in Malmö, Stockholm, and Vitoria-Gasteiz. For the municipality in Malmö, neighbourhood image was a primary driver as it also promoted a better image of the whole city. Further, a secondary driver was the improvement of the political image of the city administration. Stockholm noted that, for the political and institutional actors, tackling the negative image of a ‘troubled’ neighbourhood would result in political gain. Finally, residents of different regions (Sancho el Sabio, Judizmendi) in Vitoria-Gasteiz reported different perceptions of the superblocs – a contributing factor to this was the new image of the city.

Barcelona identified level of pride in the local neighbourhood as a potential factor motivating support or opposition to the superblocs. In El Hierro, islanders reported feeling proud to be part of a pioneer island in renewable energies. The island has gained an international reputation for sustainability and self-sufficiency, and this has become a relevant factor in islanders' endorsement of the project.

Similar to the analysis carried out in Vitoria-Gasteiz, Barcelona analysed types of needs that might motivate support or opposition to superblocs, one of which was identified as the neighbourhood aesthetic (falling under the sub-heading ‘mixed dimension of comfort’).

3.8 Finance

Financial considerations were often mentioned as influencing people's propensity to support the social innovations. The complex nature of financial motivations was clear in the case of El Hierro, where the government implemented a series of pilot initiatives to bring the financial benefits of the SI to the island through grants for businesses to install solar panels, subsidies for residents to buy electric vehicles and the installation of electric charging points across the island, with a view to increasing support for the SI. The emphasis on financial benefits meant that residents developed high expectations and believed that they would have access to free electricity once the energy plant was profitable, which was not the case and ultimately led to a lack of trust in the leaders of the SI. The project did, however, create jobs and contribute to the island's economic development, which has increased support among residents.

In Samsø, too, government grants allowed the SI to be established, and the primary driver was to generate economic benefits for island communities with otherwise uncertain prospects. And in Malmö, the availability of financial support was found to be a driver for residents to accept the SI by providing access to energy efficiency measures that they would otherwise have to pay for.

In Barcelona and Vitoria-Gasteiz, financial concerns related to the impact of the SI on the local economy more broadly. In particular, concerns about the implications for tourism and access to local shops and businesses was a factor in residents' support for the superblocs.

4. Discussion

Many of the findings from the case study analyses confirm what we already know about influences on energy-related choice behaviours, albeit in the context of specific social innovations. It is not unexpected to find that women or people with a higher level of education express stronger pro-environmental attitudes, that the people holding such attitudes are more likely to be motivated to engage with the SI, or that financial and economic benefits and incentives encourage support for an SI. Neither is it surprising that people's attachment to the place where they live influences energy-related decisions in at least one case in every cluster, as previous research has shown that place attachment is positively associated with caring for one's local environment. In this respect, our findings support foregoing research into the factors influencing pro-environmental behaviour.

What is more interesting to consider is the salience of these factors across the range of social innovations that comprise the SMARTEES portfolio of cases. It is notable that no single dominant factor was found to affect choice behaviour in all of the SMARTEES social innovations. Rather, influences vary between cases, with some consistency within clusters, reflecting the fact that clustered cases focus on related social innovations and therefore encounter similar themes and challenges. This can be seen in the example of Cluster 1, in which Zürich and Groningen identified people's behaviour patterns, such as use of pro-environmental forms of transport, as influencing their energy-related decision-making, in this case relating to keeping areas of the city closed to traffic, while behaviour was not relevant in Aberdeen and Timișoara. It is also evident in the importance of people's attitudes towards society and the environment in the cases of Malmö and Stockholm (Cluster 3), which both concern energy efficiency in district regeneration.

Notwithstanding the spread of relevant factors depicted in Table 3.1 (above), certain aspects emerged as essential ingredients for successful innovation across multiple cases. As well as underlining the importance of considering the individual characteristics of different place-based contexts when designing social innovations, several cases reported contrasting findings relating to differences between individuals, particularly age and life stage. For example, older people may have different values and priorities from younger people living in the same area, and households with children may have distinct requirements from adult-only households. Taken together, the importance of place and life stage identified in the analyses speak to a need for approaches to social innovations that are cognisant of the peculiarities of the places in which they are being proposed or implemented, and sensitive to the varied experiences and situations of the affected populations.

Our findings highlighted the benefits for innovation diffusion of residents having first-hand positive experience of pilot schemes or similar innovations elsewhere. This is evident in Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona, where pilot superblocs improved public perceptions of the initiatives. Conversely, negative experiences relating to the innovation can inhibit diffusion. This was evident in the case of El Hierro where a misunderstanding about the financial benefits of the project resulted in a loss of support for the initiative and damaged the relationship between local residents and project leaders.

Perhaps the most illuminating aspect of the enclosed analyses, however, has been in considering the impact of people's social networks on their propensity to support an SI, whereby the impact of individual experiences, whether positive or negative, can ripple throughout communities. People are embedded in families, friendship groups, workplaces and neighbourhoods where they are exposed to information, anecdotes and opinions that shape their expectations and beliefs. Through their networks, people convey their own and learn of others' experiences and knowledge related to the social innovation.

The currency of these social relationships is trust, denoting the confidence with which one regards the information or advice provided by another person, organisation or other entity, and therefore the likely degree of influence they have over one's choices. As such, trust can be a significant driver of social innovation, just as distrust can be a barrier. This can be explicit, such as in the cases of Stockholm and El Hierro, where a lack of trust among local residents in the innovation leaders negatively affected engagement with the respective initiatives. In Stockholm, it was only in the later stages, when the institutional actors gained the confidence of residents, that trust became a driver rather than a barrier. Trust also operates less visibly to moderate the influence of the agents in a person's network. For example, findings from the SMARTEES cases showed that people place particular trust in their household and extended family networks, that these personal networks play an important role in energy-related decisions, and that gender and age act as mediating factors. These relationships may not be visible to the innovators but are nonetheless an important consideration in successfully spreading an innovation.

In summary, this analysis of SMARTEES cases adds detail and nuance to previously known influences on pro-environmental choice behaviour by emphasising the importance of considering the unique situations and personal impacts of each SI, which vary according to place, life stage and previous experience. In particular, it highlights the importance of social networks in spreading acceptance of the SI throughout a community. Engaging with local communities and encouraging residents' participation in the design process can be practical and effective methods of ensuring that trust is diffused on a large scale, securing the success of the SI.

The next steps in this research are to operationalise what we have discovered so that choice behaviour can be represented in the models. Approaches to doing so are outlined in the cluster contributions in Part Two.

Part Two: Cluster-level analyses

5. First cluster: Holistic, shared, and persistent mobility planning (Zürich and Groningen)

Cluster 1, “Holistic, shared and persistent mobility planning”, refers to the case of Zürich and Groningen. Both cases are characterized by a very long life (around 40-45 years until today) and are centred on mobility (based on high quality public transport and propagation of bikes and bike lanes; mainly the first in Zürich, mainly the latter in Groningen) with little interest in the main other sectors of energy consumption (e.g., housing, industry, etc.) or in energy production.

In both cases, the “starting point” is in the ‘70s of the 20th century (mobility strategy to speed up trams and buses in Zürich; design and launch of a new Traffic Circulation Plan/TCP in Groningen aimed at limiting the use of cars). In both cases, the main actor was (and still is) the municipality.

Both approaches were participative. In Zürich, the implementation of the mobility strategy governance is rooted in a very strong system of direct democracy characterized by the celebration of various referenda (promoted either by public local authorities or by citizens) and traditional consultations of citizens at the local level). In general, the city of Zürich and all the other local planning authorities try to engage stakeholders and do engage them in formal and informal fora as much as they can. Before the final decisions are taken, there is normally a formal request for comments where most of the formal actors get a chance to be involved. In Groningen, there was an important evolution of the governance model of mobility. The organisation of city planning has changed completely because of the paradigm shift in the 1970s. Basically, the top-down approach of the technical planning experts has shifted towards a holistic planning process, where plans are being developed including many relevant sustainability dimensions such as well-being and involvement of the citizens, energy use and economic viability. Consequently, citizens and shopkeepers/ entrepreneurs are increasingly being involved in planning processes. In the beginning, they did not have an important influence on decision-making, but later (especially since the 1990s) they could influence decisions thanks to referenda and local, more or less binding consultations. An important tipping point in this evolution process was the referendum held in 1994 on the closure of Noorderplantsoen Park to through-going car traffic.

In both cases (Zürich and Groningen), big changes in citizens’ mobility behaviours towards new, much more pro-environmental behaviours are well documented. The big difference is that: (a) in Zürich the transition has been from cars firstly to public transport and, secondly, to bikes and walking, and (b) in Groningen the transition has been from cars, firstly to bikes and, secondly, to public transport and walking.

This difference between Zürich and Groningen concerns all age groups (e.g., youth in Groningen ride bikes, while in Zürich they prefer public transport, which is considered an effective means of mobility thanks to comfort and to ICT/WiFi availability).

In both cases, change of behaviour in mobility is also beginning to inspire the adoption of more pro-environmental behaviours in other sectors (e.g., rational use of water). However, this is still limited.

5.1 Aims of the analysis

In both cases, the analysis was first global, considering all the actions implemented since the beginning throughout the years (documentary research, interviews with key informants). This large analysis considered both cases as social innovations in energy transition (more specifically, in sustainable mobility), which is a process of change in social relationships, interactions, configurations, and/or the sharing of knowledge leading to, or based on, new environmentally sustainable ways of producing,

managing, and consuming energy that meet social challenges/problems. Therefore, many issues were considered, such as:

- Changes in ways of producing, managing, and consuming energy (towards environmentally sustainable methods)
- Changes in social relationships, interactions, and configurations (of actors, processes, forms of governance, rules, business models, etc.)
- The diffusion of new values
- Strategies for gaining social support
- Critical issues (including resistances and conflicts) and how these have been overcome (paying particular attention to negotiation processes among the involved actors and to strategies for gaining social support)
- Changes in the sharing of knowledge
- Societal/environmental benefits
- Citizens' new behaviours
- Up-scaling/replicability of the experience.

In both cases, thanks to this comprehensive analysis, we have also tried to understand how the change in the sustainability of mobility patterns could be considered as consolidated, or in other words, how much we can consider that a structural change happened (i.e. irreversible; characterized by a comprehensive modification of the local life; and including, in a collective effort, all the relevant players and stakeholders within the involved territory/system, from the leaderships to the citizens).

Later, the analysis was restricted to a specific issue: "restricting movement by use of a certain modality in the city" and was focused, in both cases, on two similar events:

- In Groningen, the closure of Noorderplantsoen park for through-going car traffic; this happened after a popular referendum (the first referendum in Groningen) held on 5th October 1994 (a majority vote of 50.9% decided in favour of a permanent closure)
- In Zürich, the closure of Limmatquai for through-going car traffic; this happened after a popular referendum (one among dozens of referenda celebrated each year) held on 13th June 1999 (a majority vote of 59.5% decided in favour of a permanent closure).

These two referenda represent the "core" issue of two surveys implemented through similar questionnaires in Groningen and in Zürich (see § 5.2), aimed at analysing the diffusion, modalities, and motivations for acceptance of a new organization of traffic in the city: the main artery connecting the east to the west - the Noorderplantsoen park, in the case of Groningen; an important street, in the right-hand (eastern) bank of the Limmat river for about 1 km through the Altstadt, or historical core, of the city, in the case of Zürich. The overall aim is to represent the process of Groningen or Zürich residents deciding whether to have through traffic, respectively, in the Noorderplantsoen park (Groningen) and in the Limmatquai (Zürich).

5.2 Approach

a. Selection of data sources (for secondary data)

Groningen

In Groningen, there was a report available on the referendum that took place. Because the closure of the park was decided using a referendum, the whole population of the municipality of Groningen was entitled to cast their vote on either keeping the park open for cars, or closing it down. The report provided data per voting location (multiple in neighbourhoods), providing votes and turnout per neighbourhood.

Concerning the data on the social, economic and demographic variables of the general population of Groningen in 1994, we used statistical yearbooks produced by the municipality of Groningen. Unfortunately, the statistical yearbook series had been discontinued for a few years, and the year 1994 was lacking. However, we found references in the 1999 yearbook (Stinissen Blanco et al., 1999) to earlier years, and using these we could get close to the social-economic-demographic data of citizens by neighbourhood district.

Hence, the original data used for population recreation was retrieved from the Statistical yearbook 1999 and Gemeente Groningen's report from the referendum. Data were obtained on age, gender, educational level, economic activity, income, family size, and neighbourhood residence.

Qualitative secondary data was found on specific websites. In particular the website of the Noorderplantsoen neighbourhood (<http://www.noorderplantsoen.nl>) contains a very good description of the historic developments that took place in this park. Obviously, the case of closing the park for car traffic and the associated referendum are described here based on further references, e.g. on the ecological values of the park and historic developments.

Sources consulted included:

- Statistical yearbook Groningen 1999: Municipality of Groningen
- Gemeente Groningen's report from the referendum: Uitslag en Achtergrond van het Referendum Noorderplantsoen. October 1994. Available: <https://os-groningen.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/referendum-noorderplantsoen-1994.pdf>

Zürich

In Zürich, specific studies related to the Limmatquai case were not founded, with the exception of a Master's thesis, "Simulating the traffic impacts of the closure of the Limmatquai", which was very helpful for understanding the context of the decisions made through the referendum held in June 1999 (the historical events leading to this decision as well as in the same context the traffic policies of the City and the Canton of Zürich).

Many secondary data were used, taken from the Zürich Statistisches Jahrbuch (2000, 2002 and 2017) related to the distribution of people by sex, class of ages, residence (in each of the 12 districts of the Zürich city), socio-professional categories, according to the highest level of education, and the results, by district of the referendum held on June 13th 1999 on closing Limmatquai. Some other statistical sources related to the municipality of Zürich were exploited. More specifically:

- Zürcher Stadtquartiere – Statistik um 12 (Zürich 12 city districts statistics); 10 November 2020
- Vielfältiges Zürich – Die Menschen und ihre Quartiere - Eidgenössische Volkszählungen (Diverse Zürich - The people and their neighborhoods - Federal censuses), 1970–2000 – (Segregation and removals in the city and agglomeration of Zürich - CARTOGRAPHIC APPENDIX) analysen 9/2004 (Highest degree of training completed by people aged 30 and over by city district 2000; Socio-professional categories for people aged 15 and over by city district, 2000)
- Segregation und Umzüge in der Stadt und Agglomeration Zürich - KARTOGRAPHISCHER ANHANG (Segregation and relocations in the city and agglomeration of Zürich - CARTOGRAPHIC ANNEX) (2001).

Among the further statistical documents consulted, we can also quote:

- Population survey of the Department of City Development in Zürich (in 2015 and in 2019)
- Bevölkerungsbefragung der Stadtentwicklung (Population survey of urban development, 2012).

b. Data collection methods (for primary data)

Groningen

Primary data were collected through interviews and questionnaires. Whereas for getting data on the general population a representative sample using questionnaires is an effective approach, getting data from important stakeholders requires the identification of these persons, and approaching them directly. Because their experiences will be quite rich as they were in some way or another involved in the process of the closure, a semi-structured interview was used to be able to get the highest quality of qualitative data possible.

The interviews were conducted with key stakeholders that were responsible for the implementation of the Traffic Circulation Plan (former mayor and elderman), the former elderman responsible for the referendum, a policy advisor having experience with the case and a representative of the shopkeepers. These interviews lasted about 1.5 hours, and contributed to a deeper understanding of the dynamics in the case, because (1) the referendum on the closure of the park for car traffic was one event in a longer process of transforming the traffic system in the city, and (2) they revealed a bias of the newspapers at that time in favour of the keep-the-park-open position of most shopkeepers (who were advertising in the same newspapers). These interviews were critical in getting an understanding of the forces that were playing a role in the public debate.

Questionnaires were used to get data on the preferences of the citizens relating to opening versus closing the park for cars. It is clear that these data could not directly be used to parameterize a 25-year-old case. While in the referendum just over 50% of the citizens voted for a car-free park, in 2020 an overwhelming majority (close to 95%) reported to be in favor of keeping the park closed to cars.

The questionnaire was online between 18th October 2019 and 4th November 2019 and a total of 2,747 respondents filled in the questions. The questions addressed the key factors described in the HUMAT framework, and included the following elements:

- Social demographic data (age, gender, family composition, education, economic activity, income, neighbourhood)
- Groups who vote in the referendum related to the Noorderplantsoen (Your immediate family members; Your friends; Your co-workers/fellow students; Your local neighbours; Other parents you know; Your local shopkeepers)
- Sources that help you to make the decision about the vote in the Noorderplantsoen referendum (same as above plus local newspapers; free of charge media; social media; representatives of the city of Groningen; political parties; business community “City Club” / other shopkeepers; environmental organisations).
- Aspects of daily life that are positively or negatively impacted by the closure of Noorderplantsoen for private motorised traffic (using my car, safety of children in my neighbourhood, business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Noorderplantsoen, ecological value of the Noorderplantsoen, biking, walk, living quality in Groningen, car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding the Noorderplantsoen, number of service sector jobs in the vicinity of Noorderplantsoen, accessibility of the city)

- How important would be the effects on the following aspects of daily life in making your own decision voting in the referendum on closing Noorderplantsoen for motorised private car traffic? (same as above)
- The voter's intention regarding Noorderplantsoen today
- Actions supporting the voting decision (share your opinion on the matter with people you know; share your opinion on the matter on social media; participate in public consultations organised by the municipality of Groningen; participate in meetings of a relevant organisation/interest group; participate in a demonstration; organise a demonstration; inform a local newspaper)
- Level of agreement or disagreement with the statement: "I am very attached to the city of Groningen"

Zürich

Primary data were collected through qualitative interviews and an online survey held by GFS.BERN on the behalf of the Municipality of Zürich and the SMARTEES project, administered to residents registered in Zürich before 1st July (e.g. born in Zürich or who moved to Zürich before 1st July 2019).

Qualitative interviews were conducted with key stakeholders from the Zürich municipality, the Zürich canton, Zürich transport facilities and people from ETH Zürich and citizens' organisations.

The survey questionnaire was very similar to the one used in the Groningen survey and included 20 questions (19 closed; 1 open) relating to the socio-demographic status of respondents (gender, age, income/living conditions, educational level, employment status, children/family, residence district, migration status, marital status) and to the following issues:

- Groups who vote in the referendum related to Limmatquai (Your immediate family members; Your friends; Your co-workers/fellow students; Your local neighbours; Other parents you know; Your local shopkeepers)
- Sources in helping you to make the decision about the vote in the Limmatquai referendum (same than above + Local newspapers; free of charge media; Social media; Representatives of the city of Zürich; Political parties; Business community "City Vereinigung" / other shopkeepers; Environmental organisations; Pro Velo/Specific citizens' groups, e.g. "street communities"; Car group "Touring club Switzerland"/Automobil-Club; experts from ETH Zürich/UZH)
- Aspects of daily life that were positively or negatively impacted by the closure of Limmatquai for private motorised traffic (using my car, safety of children in my neighbourhood, attractiveness of the area for restaurant owners as well as tourists, business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Limmatquai, ecological image of the city of Zürich, biking, walk (improvement of the pedestrian area), living quality in Zürich, car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Limmatquai, number of service sector jobs in the vicinity of Limmatquai, accessibility of the city)
- How important would be the effects on the following aspects of daily life in making your own decision voting in the referendum on closing Limmatquai for motorised private car traffic? (same than above)
- The voter's intention regarding Limmatquai today (next Sunday/next month)
- Actions to gather support for the voting decision (share your opinion on the matter with people you know; share your opinion on the matter on social media; participate in public consultations organised by the Stadt Zürich; participate in meetings of a relevant organisation/interest group; participate in a demonstration; organise a demonstration; inform a local newspaper)

- Level of agreement or disagreement with the statement: “I am very attached to Zürich city”

The questionnaire was online from 27th January to 9th March 2020.

c. Sample size, composition and response rate (for surveys)

The following table provides an overview of the data collection period, sampling frame, sampling frame size and (effective) sampling size for the Groningen and Zürich cases.

Table 5.1. Data collection in Groningen and Zürich

	Groningen	Zürich
Mode	CAWI	CAWI
Data collection period	18.10.2019 – 4.11.2019	10.2.2020 – 8.3.2020
Sampling frame	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recipients of the Nieuwsbrief gemeente Groningen – weekly newsletter sent by the Groningen municipality. The newsletter contained a short description of the study and the survey link. 2. Recipients of University College Groningen’s (UCG’s) BUZZ newsletter. 3. Subscribers to the Gemeente Groningen Facebook profile. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A random sample of 8,000 addresses of residents aged 18 and above from the municipal citizen register was the basis for this survey. Excluded from the sample were persons who have been residents of Zürich for less than six months. The addresses were provided by the city of Zürich.
Sampling frame size	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nieuwsbrief gemeente Groningen: approx. 15,000 residents of the Groningen municipality . 2. BUZZ newsletter: approx. 300 students and employees of UCG (a faculty of University of Groningen). 3. Gemeente Groningen Facebook: approx. 32,000 Facebook profiles. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All 8,000 persons in the gross sample address-file received an invitation letter by post. The letter contained information on the client, a short project outline and the login information to participate in the online survey. 2. The final data set was validated based on the sociodemographic structure for the resident population of the city of Zürich aged 18 and above. A population weight variable has been created for correct age and gender proportions interlocked with Swiss vs. non-Swiss nationality, measured by voting eligibility.
Sample size ¹	2747	1111
Effective sample size ²	703	1001

¹ Sample size is the total number of collected questionnaire responses. It includes a registry of all instances when the survey link was clicked on regardless of providing any information by the respondent (e.g., situations when the respondent resigned after a reading the privacy statement).

² Effective sample size is the number of fully filled out questionnaires that were obtained after cleaning procedures and missing data imputation. This is the number that serves as a basis for all analyses.

d. Limitations of the approach

The following limitations should be highlighted.

Groningen

1. The closure of the Noorderplantsoen for car traffic was one policy implementation in the broader context of the Traffic Circulation Plan. This plan was launched in 1977, and the referendum on the Noorderplantsoen took place in 1994.
2. The referendum on the Noorderplantsoen was the first advisory referendum that ever took place in the Netherlands. Hence it was also a political experiment, supported strongly by the responsible elderman who was member of a national party favouring democratic renewal.

Zürich

1. The Limmatquai closure is just a specific, albeit important, event in a long history of promoting sustainable mobility in Zürich, starting 45 years ago.
2. Contrary to what happened in Groningen, where the 1994 referendum had a strong relevance and was the subject of several studies (also being the first in Groningen), the one in Zürich was just one of the many referenda held in 1999, and just one among many referenda in the history on mobility/transport issues in Zürich. However, closing Limmatquai is still important for Zürich citizens (but “memory” of the referendum is likely lower than in Groningen).

5.3 Key findings

5.3.1 Groningen

The effective sample for the Groningen survey consisted of 703 citizens. Due to self-selection bias, and possibly a sampling frame bias, there is significant underrepresentation of Groningers with lower levels of education and overrepresentation of young adults.

In 2019, survey respondents have a very strong inclination to opt for closing the Noorderplantsoen park for car traffic. Almost 94% of the respondents prefer the current status quo. This is a significant change compared to the referendum results in 1994, where only 51% voted for the closure of Noorderplantsoen for car traffic. It seems that over the course of 25 years, Groningers have adapted to the Noorderplantsoen being a car-free park and now prefer keep it that way. While we are aware of the bias in the sampling, considering the strong effects we conclude that the evaluation of the closure of the park for cars is much more preferred than in 1994.

In 1994, we observe that people living in neighbourhoods closer to the park had a higher likelihood of voting for the closing of the park to cars (Figure 5.1). In 2019, the turnout and voting decision per neighbourhood relationship is no longer present in the data. The overwhelming majority of respondents across all districts would vote for closure of the park to cars.

Figure 5.1. Voting decision per district in the 1994 referendum.¹

¹ Source: own on the basis of Dienst informatie en administratie Gemeentelijk Informatiecentrum (1994) Uitslag en achtergrond van het referendum Noorderplantsoen.

In green-coloured districts over 50% of voters chose a car-free Noorderplantsoen; in red-coloured districts over 50% of respondents preferred to keep car traffic in the park (marked black on the map). The detailed referendum results are presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. Turnout and % of voters opting for a car-free Noorderplantsoen in the 1994 referendum.¹

District	Turnout	% Car-free votes
Centrum	33	63
Oranjewijk / Schilderswijk	42	61
Oud-Zuid	28	56
Nieuw-Zuid (corporatief)	30	38
Nieuw-Zuid (particulier)	30	40
Oosterpark	24	54
Korreweg / De Hoogte	34	60
Lewenborg	23	45
Beijum	29	61
Nieuw-Oost	31	29
Paddepoel	36	43
Vinkhuizen	25	36
Hoogkerk / De Dorpen	24	25

¹ Source: own on the basis of Dienst informatie en administratie Gemeentelijk Informatiecentrum (1994) Uitslag en achtergrond van het referendum Noorderplantsoen.

In the 2019 survey, having young children (under the age of 13) played an important and unexpected role in the decision on a car-free park (Figure 5.2). Respondents with younger children are slightly less inclined to support a car-free park (87%, compared to 95% of adults without young children). Within Groningers without small children, women especially support a car-free park (98%, compared to 92% support among men). In the group of men without small children, those with higher education are

more likely to support the car-free park. However, it is important to highlight that in each of those nodes an overwhelming majority prefers to keep the park closed to cars. Based on the survey results, a specific socio-demographic segment opposing a car-free park cannot be identified. Table 5.3 presents the relationship between the voting preference and socio-demographic characteristics of the survey respondents. Note that characteristics that did not appear in the decision tree (Figure 5.2) do not influence the decision to vote in a statistically significant manner.

Figure 5.2. Decision tree showing key factors in voting decision

Table 5.3. Descriptive overview of the survey sample

		Imagine that cars are still allowed in the park today, and a vote on the issue takes place next month. How would you vote?			
		I would vote for closing the park for cars	I would vote for keeping the cars allowed in the park	I would not go voting	Total
Overall		93.7%	5.5%	0.7%	100%
Gender	man	91.2%	7.7%	1.0%	100%
	woman	96.8%	2.9%	0.3%	100%
Age group	18-24	98.2%	0.9%	0.9%	100%
	25-64	93.4%	5.9%	0.7%	100%
	65+	91.0%	8.2%	0.7%	100%
Education	lower	-	-	-	-
	middle	91.9%	7.8%	0.3%	100%
	higher	95.5%	3.4%	1.1%	100%
Main economic activity	student	98.2%	0.9%	0.9%	100%
	employed	93.3%	6.2%	0.5%	100%
	inactive	96.1%	3.9%	0.0%	100%
	retired	90.3%	8.1%	1.6%	100%
How do you feel about your household's income nowadays?	living comfortably on present income	94.5%	4.7%	0.8%	100%
	copying on present income	94.7%	4.9%	0.4%	100%
	difficult on present income	89.8%	10.2%	0.0%	100%
	very difficult on present income	75.0%	18.8%	6.3%	100%
What is your marital/partnership status?	single	95.8%	3.8%	0.4%	100%
	married/living together	92.6%	6.9%	0.5%	100%
	divorced	94.7%	0.0%	5.3%	100%
	widowed	85.7%	7.1%	7.1%	100%
Does a person have a small child (<13 y.o.)	no	94.7%	4.5%	0.8%	100%
	yes	86.9%	13.1%	0.0%	100%
District	Centrum + Oranjewijk/Schilderswijk	94.7%	5.3%	0.0%	100%
	rest	93.2%	5.7%	1.1%	100%

In 2019, the majority of respondents reported that closing the park would have a positive effect on the recreational value of the park, biking, the ecological value of the park, the possibility of organizing cultural events in the park (e.g., Noorderzon), the appeal of the city for visitors and safety of children in my neighbourhood (Table 5.4). The most recognized negative effect of a car-free park is the increase

in traffic in neighbourhoods surrounding the park. According to the analyses from 1994, this issue was also a major concern when the referendum took place. Same aspects that witness positive consequences of closing the park for car traffic were considered most important for respondents' voting decisions (Table 5.5).

Table 5.4. From your perspective, would closing of the park for car traffic have positive or negative effects on the following aspects of daily life?

	Positive	Neutral or no impact	Negative	I don't know
Recreational value of the park	89.60%	4.30%	5.90%	0.10%
Biking	86.50%	8.70%	4.40%	0.40%
Ecological value of the park (e.g., plants, bats)	87.70%	5.90%	5.50%	1.00%
Possibility of organizing cultural events in the park (e.g., Noorderzon)	82.90%	7.90%	8.20%	1.00%
Appeal of Groningen for visitors	80.40%	11.40%	6.30%	2.00%
Safety of children in my neighbourhood	60.40%	32.10%	3.30%	4.20%
Number of service sector jobs in the vicinity of Noorderplantsoen	42.00%	41.80%	7.60%	8.60%
Accessibility of the city	32.30%	47.90%	15.90%	3.90%
Business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Noorderplantsoen	22.70%	46.80%	20.00%	10.60%
Car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Noorderplantsoen	18.90%	30.70%	41.80%	8.60%
Using my car	10.40%	63.10%	14.70%	11.80%

Table 5.5. How important would be the effect of the following aspects of daily life, in making your own decision voting in the referendum on closing the park for car traffic?
(0 – not at all important, 10 – extremely important)

	Mean	Standard deviation
Recreational value of the park	8.35	1.71
Ecological value of the park (e.g., plants, bats)	8.27	2.02
Biking	8.11	1.96
Possibility of organising cultural events in the park	7.15	2.39
Safety of children in my neighbourhood	7.09	2.91
Appeal of Groningen for visitors	6.61	2.56
Accessibility of the city	5.64	2.57
Number of service sector jobs in the vicinity of the park	5.25	2.44
Business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Noorderplantsoen	5.09	2.40
Car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Noorderplantsoen	4.61	2.60
Using my car	3.03	2.92

Respondents' own closest family was marked as having most influence on their voting decision (Table 5.6). Gemeente Groningen (the municipality of Groningen) is marked as second most influential in one's decision for voting. This should be interpreted with caution, as it likely is an artifact of the sampling frame and data collection mode. The survey was mainly distributed via the Gemeente Groningen's Facebook page.

Table 5.6. How important do you think the following sources would be in helping you to make your decision?

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Immediate family (household)	6.54	2.89
Gemeente Groningen	6.20	2.72
Pro-environment organisations	6.13	2.84
Friends	5.95	2.73
Local newspapers	5.68	2.76
Extended family (outside household)	5.17	2.95
Co-workers/fellow students	5.13	2.79
Algemene Nederlandse Gehandicapten Organisatie	5.12	3.07
Echte Nederlandse Fietsersbond	5.10	3.12
Vereniging Reizigers Openbaar Vervoer	4.62	3.10
Local neighbours	4.58	2.92
Local neighbours with small children (up to 12 years old)	4.56	3.02
Social media	4.34	3.02
Local school	4.27	3.08
Local shopkeepers	3.84	2.86
Shopkeeper associations, e.g. Groningen City Club	3.48	2.81

Respondents that seek support for their opinion indicate that they would most prefer to engage in discourse with their own network. More demanding means of evoking support (e.g., organizing demonstrations as suboptimal) are not too popular among Groningers (Table 5.7).

Table 5.7. To gather support for the option you favour, would you... ?

	Yes	No	Don't know
Share your opinion on the matter with people you know	91.6%	5.0%	3.4%
Share your opinion on the matter on social media	37.1%	51.7%	11.2%
Participate in public consultations organised by the city council	30.0%	49.8%	20.1%
Participate in a demonstration	22.4%	59.6%	18.0%
Participate in meetings of a relevant organisation/interest group	20.4%	57.4%	22.2%
Inform a local newspaper	12.7%	73.2%	14.1%

5.3.2 Zürich

As already stated, the SMARTTEES Zürich survey involved 1,001 respondent who filled a questionnaire online.

A. Some basic data

Tables 5.8 to 5.12 below display the distribution of respondents by gender, by class of age, degree of education, employment status, and district of residence (district where the respondents live).

Table 5.8. Gender distribution of interviewees

Gender	%
Male	49.3
Female	48.8
Prefer to self-describe	0.7
Don't know/no answer	1.2

Table 5.9. Respondents by age group

Age group	%
18 - 24 years	4.2
25 - 64 years	76.1
65+ years	16.7
No answer	3.0

Table 5.10. Respondents by educational degree

Last school attended/vocational training	%
none	0.9
primary/secondary school	2.6
apprenticeship – vocational school – KV – trade school	11.4
secondary school for adults, grammar school, teacher training, vocational school-leaving certificate	6.7
specialist or vocational training, school of arts and crafts	8.4
higher technical college such as HTL, HWV	7.1
university of applied sciences (FHS) and teacher training college	12.7
technical college (ETH), university	48.1
Don't know/no answer	2.2

Table 5.11. Respondents by employment status

Employment status	%
Working as an employee	63.0
Self-employed/freelance	7.2
Training/apprenticeship	1.5
Student	6.9
military service / civilian service / civil protection	0.3
Looking after home or family	2.6
Long term sick or disabled	0.4
Unemployed	1.2
Retired	15.0
Other	0.7
don't know/no answer	1.4

Table 5.12. Respondents by district of residence³

District where the respondents live	%
district 1 Old town	1.4
district 2	7.8
district 3 Wiedikon	11.6
district 4 Aussersihl	5.7
district 5 Industriequartier	3.5
district 6	12.2
district 7	10.2
district 8 Riesbach	3.8
district 9	9.2
district 10	14.2
district 11	15.3
district 12 Schwamendingen	4.8
No answer	0.5

B. Closing Limmatquai – Yesterday and today

One of the referenda held on 13th June 1999 concerned the closure of Limmatquai for through car traffic. Limmatquai is located in district 1 (old town) of Zürich. To be precise, the referendum question was “Änderung des kommunalen Verkehrsplans der Stadt Zürich, Aufhebung der Bezeichnung des Limmatquais als 'durchgängige Quartierstrass” (Change in the municipal transport plan of the city of Zürich, the designation of the Limmatquai as a 'continuous district street' is no longer used).

A majority vote of 59.5% decided in favour of a permanent closure. Apparently, today (i.e. in the first quarter of 2020, when this survey was implemented) the respondents are much more in favour, at 84.2%. In the table below, a comparison of the results by the twelve Zürich districts can be found (% of people voting for closing Limmatquai).

Table 5.13. Respondents in favour of Limmatquai closure in 1999 and in 2020 (%)

In favor of closing Limmatquai	1999	2020	difference
district 1 old town	72.5	78.6	+6.1
district 2	56.6	93.1	+36.5
district 3 Wiedikon	64.4	90.7	+26.3
district 4 Aussersihl	68.0	90.0	+22.0
district 5 Industriequartier	75.4	84.4	+9.0
district 6	64.5	94.8	+30.3
district 7	56.6	85.3	+28.7
district 8 Riesbach	64.6	84.8	+20.2
district 9	55.6	86.6	+31.0
district 10	60.1	89.9	+29.8
district 11	54.7	83.7	+29.0
district 12 Schwamendingen	49.4	82.1	+32.7
Whole city of Zürich	59.5	88.3	+28.2

The following observations can be made:

First. The closure of Limmatquai was certainly a successful operation. While at the time of the referendum (1999), albeit with a good majority of in favour, the population of Zürich was almost split in half; in 2020, it is almost a plebiscite of people in favour (8 people out of 9). The closure of Limmatquai was a forward-looking measure that is now appreciated by almost everyone.

³ In the Zürich Statistisches Jahrbuch (2000) for some districts only the number is reported; while for others (often) it is reported both the number and the name. Here we proceeded in a similar way

Second. The difference in the % of those in favour is however minimal in district 1, where Limmatquai is located (+6.1%). It should be remembered, however, that in 1999, district 1 was one of the two where there was the highest % of "yes"; % which remains almost at the same level, so that, in 2020, district 1 is the one where there is, conversely, the lowest % of "yes". Contrary to what has happened in the rest of the city, the opinion of the people of the area concerned does not seem to have changed much. However, it should be remembered that, in district 1, in 2020 as in 1999, few people live (while business and administration are concentrated in this district). The same happened (roughly) in District 5 (+9.0%) that is the "industriequartier", which is also very sparsely populated (and close to Limmatquai). Therefore the most "working" and less "resident" districts are the ones where people in favour of the closure of Limmatquai were the most in 1999, but agreement remains almost the same in 2020.

Third. In all other districts, the % of those in favour increases dramatically (from +20.2% to +36.5%). The lower increase happened in district 4 (Aussersihl) close to Limmatquai. One thus gets the impression that the % of those in favour has increased, above all, in residential districts of Zürich that are not close to Limmatquai. Therefore, while in 1999, those in favour were concentrated above all in the "business" and "next" districts in Limmatquai, in 2020, the favourable opinion spread massively throughout the whole city.

Fourth. The difference in the increases between 1999 and 2020 highlighted in the two previous points could be linked to the fact that, in 1999, the focus was mainly on mobility. Therefore, the most interested (district 1, and, to a lesser extent, the closer districts 4 and 5) were the most favourable. In the following 20 years, ecological awareness has grown which has led to an upward "homogenization" across Zürich of those in favour of closure. Another possible explanation is that people living close to the closed road now have also experienced the downsides, whereas people living further away only experience the "sunny side" of the closure.

C. Closing Limmatquai – behaviors in mobility

We have just seen that in 2020 an overwhelming majority of those who would have voted are in favour of the closure of Limmatquai (8 out of 9 people). The data are roughly similar, considering all those who responded to the survey, including those who would not have gone to vote in a hypothetical referendum at the beginning of 2020 (yes = 84.2%). Is there a relationship between the opinion towards the closure of Limmatquai and the behaviours assumed in mobility? First of all, let us see how those who participated in the survey at the beginning of 2020 "move" in Zürich.

Table 5.14. Respondents by means of transport

When you think about your everyday life, how do you mainly move around in Zürich?	%
car	8.6
motorcycle/ scooter	1.1
public transport like bus, tramway or suburban railway	57.9
bicycle	22.0
E-bike	1.5
on foot	8.5
wheelchair	0
others (e.g. kickboard, skateboard)	0.1
don't know/no answer	0.5

Crossing these data with the opinion on the closing Limmatquai, we can see (Figure 5.3) that:

- Those in favour of closing are, of course, almost all of those who, to move use bicycles, e-bikes, and kickboard/skateboard or moving walk (yes = 92.5%), but also almost all who use mainly the public transports (yes = 86.5%)
- Conversely, among those who use cars or motorcycle/scooter to move those in favour of closing Limmatquai for through-going car traffic are less than 50% (yes = 45.8%).

Figure 5.3. Respondents in favour of closing Limmatquai by transport use

Therefore, the more "ecological" mobility is adopted, the more favoured is the closure of Limmatquai. However, it can also be noted that even among those who use motorized vehicles, 4 out of 9 people are in favour of closing.

D. Attachment to Zürich (and "closing Limmatquai")

Data from the 2020 survey on attachment to Zürich city are reported in figure 5.4 below.

It should be emphasized that practically all interviewees declare themselves attached to Zürich city (90%), while dividing themselves, almost equally, among those who agree completely with the proposed sentence (a kind of "citizen nationalism") and those who have a more aloof attitude. Those who disagree are, however, a completely negligible number, while a small % has no opinion.

It is worth noting that those who agree completely or rather agree with the statement: "I am very attached to Zürich city" are more in favour of closing Limmatquai (yes = 93.4%) with respect to those who do not express an opinion or disagree with the proposed statement. Among these, those in favour of the closure of Limmatquai are always in the majority, but they are fewer (yes = 86.5%).

Figure 5.4. Level of agreement with the statement: "I am very attached to Zürich city"

E. Closing Limmatquai and demographic/sociographic variables

Regarding the will to close Limmatquai, there are no significant differences according to the demographic variables (in the 2020 survey; no data are available related to the 1999 referendum).

- The difference is just 1.8% between the female (85.8%) and the male (84.0%) in favour of the closure of the Limmatquai.
- Looking at the age groups, people in favour are a strong majority in all age classes, with little differences:
 - In the class of age 18-24 years, people in favour are 84.6%
 - In the class of age 25-64 years, people in favour are 91.7%
 - In the class of age 65 years+, people in favour are 80%.
- People of working age are more in favour of closure, while others, especially the elderly (i.e., those who have more "memory" of the time in which Limmatquai circulated freely with motorized vehicles) would seem to be a little less favourable.

Looking at another sociographic variable, "education", differences appear more important. The higher the level of education (see also Figure 5.4), the more people would vote for the closure of Limmatquai:

- Among those with a low level of education (none, primary/secondary school), people in favour are 60%
- Among those with a medium level of education (apprenticeship – vocational school – KV – trade school, secondary school for adults, grammar school, teacher training, vocational school-leaving certificate, specialist or vocational training, school of arts and crafts), people in favour are 77.4%
- Among those with a high level of education (higher technical college, university of applied sciences/FHS and teacher training college, technical college/ETH, university), people in favour are 89.5%.

Figure 5.5. Respondents in favour of closing Limmatquai by level of education

These differences are important, but not surprising. Once again, it is confirmed⁴ that ecological awareness grows with the level of education. Looking also at the employment status, there are a few differences, but less important. Students have the highest proportion of those in favour (88.1%) – in line with what has just been said on education; followed by occupied (86.7%). They are a little less among the inactive people (78%) and retired (75.3%).

F. Impacts of the closing Limmatquai

Two of the core questions in the 2020 survey are Q3 and Q4. Q3 asked, “In your opinion, which aspects of daily life are positively or negatively impacted by the closure of Limmatquai for private motorised traffic?”

Table 5.15. Impact of Limmatquai closure on aspects of daily life

	positive	neutral/no effect	negative	don't know/no answer
using my car	8.3	51.6	17.3	22.7
safety of children in my neighbourhood	55.7	35.2	1.7	7.3
attractiveness of the area for restaurant owners as well as tourists	84.6	9.1	4.4	1.9
business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Limmatquai	50.6	26.2	13.8	9.4
ecological image of the city of Zürich	80.1	15.9	2.5	1.6
biking	85.1	9.5	2.1	3.3
walk (improvement of the pedestrian area)	90.2	7.3	1.7	0.8
living quality in Zürich	85.5	10.2	2.3	2.0
car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Limmatquai	25.0	27.8	33.2	14.0
number of service sector jobs in the vicinity of Limmatquai	35.2	40.7	9.7	14.4
accessibility of the city	45.8	37.1	13.8	3.2
other				

⁴ According to Unesco, education is critical in helping populations understand and address the impacts of climate change, and in encouraging the changes in attitudes and behaviour needed to help them address the causes of climate change, adopt more sustainable lifestyles and develop skills that support different modules of economies, as well as to adapt to the impact of climate change – cfr.

<https://en.unesco.org/themes/addressing-climate-change/climate-change-education-and-awareness>;
https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/how-can-education-contribute-awareness-and-action-climate-change_en

Given that almost all respondents, as we have seen above, have declared themselves to be in favour of the closure of Limmatquai, it is not surprising that, above all, many positive effects are identified by a very high or pretty high percentage of people, such as:

- Walking (improvement of the pedestrian area) (positive effect: 90.2%)
- Living quality in Zürich (positive effect: 85.5%)
- Biking (positive effect: 85.1%)
- Attractiveness of the area for restaurant owners as well as tourists (positive effect: 84.6%)
- Ecological image of the city of Zürich (positive effect: 80.1%)
- Safety of children in my neighbourhood (positive effect: 55.7%).

Obviously, those who highlight these positive effects are, for the most part, people in favour of closure. And given their high number, they are distributed among all socio-demographic categories, according to what has been discussed in point E) above.

However, there are also some negative effects identified by a relevant % of people, albeit being a minority:

- Car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Limmatquai (negative effect: 33.2%)
- Using of car (negative effect: 17.3%)
- Business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Limmatquai (negative effect: 13.8%)
- Accessibility of the city (negative effect: 13.8%).

People who are against of closing identified mostly negative effects:

- "Using my car", 58.1%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 12.6% of those who are in favour
- "Business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Limmatquai", 62.9%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 7.1% of those who are in favour
- "Accessibility of the city", 61.9%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 7.7% of those who are in favour.

From a socio-demographic point of view, there are no important differences by gender. However, there are meaningful differences according to people's education: people with lower educational levels identify to a stronger degree negative effects:

- "Using my car", 31.4%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 19.5% of those with a medium level, and 16.1% of those with a high level
- "Business of shopkeepers in the vicinity of Limmatquai", 29.4%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 19.6% of those with a medium level, and 10.9% of those with an high level
- "Accessibility of the city", 28.6%; conversely, this negative effect is identified only by 16.2% of those with a medium level, and 12.2% of those with a high level.

It is also worth noting that almost all those who "move" using cars or motorcycles / scooters are among those who highlight these negative effects, which are much less reported among those who use public transport and "ecological transport". As an example: negative effects on "using the car" are reported among 48.5% of those moving by cars or motorcycles / scooters; 14.3% among those using public transports; and 13.7% among those using bikes or other ecological carriers.

The difference is, however, a little less distinct for "car traffic in the neighbourhoods surrounding Limmatquai": 52.1% among those moving by cars or motorcycles / scooters; 32.5% among those using public transports; and 29.4% among those using bikes or other ecological carriers.

Q4 asked, "How important would be the effects on the following aspects of daily life in making your own decision voting in the referendum on closing Limmatquai for motorised private car traffic?" The question concerns which effects of closing Limmatquai influence voting intentions in favour or against closure of the road to cars, and to what extent. Results are reported in the Table 5.16 (the aspects considered are the same as in Q3, to be evaluated with a value from 0 (not important at all) to 10 (very important)).

Table 5.16. Effects considered the most important (persons who choose the values 8, 9, 10)

Effects	%
Living quality in Zürich	76.6
Walking (improvement of the pedestrian area)	72.6
Biking	59.6
Ecological image of the city of Zürich	53.8
Safety of children in my neighbourhood	50.8

Comparing the results relating to questions (Q3) and (Q4), it is more than evident that the four effects mentioned in Table 5.16 are important in a positive sense. Given the high number, people who highlight these important positive effects are distributed among all socio-demographic categories, according to what has been discussed in point E) above.

The only effect considered not important at all is "using my car" (persons who choose the values 0, 1, 2 are 62.2%). Of course, those who consider this effect important (8% who choose the values 8, 9, 10) are among people who are against the closing of Limmatquai.

From a socio-demographic point of view, it is mainly among those with a higher level of education that we can find people who choose (answering to Q3) the values 0, 1, 2 (the lower values, e.g. considering this effect not important): 66.6% (conversely, 55.1% among those with a medium level; and 36.1% among those with a lower level). They are also much less concentrated among inactive people 50.9% (conversely, 71.1% among students).

5.3.3 Points of similarity and difference between the two cases

An important similarity in both cases is that we observe increasing acceptance of closing the road and park to cars. In the Groningen case, in the referendum 50.9% voted for a closure, whilst in the 2019 survey 94.5% of respondents reported to be in favour of keeping the park closed for cars. In the Zürich case, we observe a similar adaptation effect, where 59.5% initially voted in favour of a permanent closure, whereas in 2020 84.2% favour a car-free Limmatquai street.

Also, we observe that the closer people live to the Noorderplantsoen or Limmatquai street, the more favourable they are about the closure. This indicates that having more direct negative experiences with car traffic serves as a motivation for closing the street/park for car traffic.

We also observe in both cases that a higher educational level results in a stronger preference for closing the street/park for car traffic.

A difference we noticed was that, whereas in Zürich there was no real effect of gender on the vote, in Groningen women were slightly more in favour of closing the park than men.

Whereas Zürich has an extensive experience with referenda, this was the first ever referendum in Groningen, and the closure of a park could be considered more impactful than the closure of a street. However, both cases seem to be rather similar in terms of the distribution of preferences and the development of the preference for closure over time. The Groningen case could have been very different though as the 50.9% pro closure vote was a very close call.

5.4 Representing choice behaviour in the model

Because we focus on the implementation of the Groningen case in the simulation model, we will describe here briefly how the data have been used to represent behaviour for the Groningen case. This approach serves as an example for future cases to implement choice behaviour in simulation models.

The social demographic data (age, gender, family composition, education, economic activity, income, neighbourhood) were used to allocate the different types of agents over the map of Groningen to create a representative artificial population (scale 1:10).

The social demographic data were also used to construct the networks between agents. Here networks of friends were constructed on the basis of homophily on age and education, co-workers networks on the basis of homophily on education and disposable income, and neighbours networks were based on household location.

The identification of relevant motives, estimation of the importance of motives for various sociodemographic groups and satisfaction of motives by car-free park and by presence of through traffic in the park were estimated on the basis of available secondary materials and information from in-depth interviews conducted with key stakeholders from Groningen. In Deliverable 7.3, an extensive table is presented describing the initialisation of motives of the different agents (Table 1.1, page 15).

The choice behaviour of the agents is a dynamic process following the rules as determined by the HUMAT architecture. Depending on their motives the agents will have a probability to cast their vote, and a tendency to vote in favour or against closing the car for cars. Additionally, depending on the social dilemma they experience they may be motivated to send messages to other agents in their network on their opinions. Agents receiving messages will change their motives if the sender is considered to be reputable. The precise implementation of these decision-making rules can be found in Deliverable 7.3.

6. Second cluster: Island renaissance based on renewable energy production (Samsø and El Hierro)

6.1 Aims of the analysis

The broad aims of the data analysis undertaken in the Samsø and El Hierro cases were:

- To identify key variables from the interviews and workshops and the survey carried out in El Hierro for analysing behavioural choices around island interventions
- To investigate the effects of sociodemographic, socio-economic and other factors on these behavioural choices
- To explore how other people in an individual's social network, institutions and information sources might influence energy-related behavioural choices, comparing both Samsø and El Hierro contexts
- To stimulate discussions with the agent-based modellers about how the empirical findings can inform the models.

Further, regarding the case of El Hierro, we have analysed the factors that influence individual and social endorsement of the model, and the factors that influence the dynamics of public opinion formation, to reach either positive or negative tipping points. Our main questions are about the critical points in the development of a project with a directed government strategy that was initially not very responsive to particular citizen concerns, the dynamics of reputation as a driver of acceptability, and the tactics and strategies used by the promoters to engage citizens and enhance acceptability of the project, to be able to reach the ambitious transformative objective.

6.2 Approach

6.2.1. Semi-structured interviews

In each case of Samsø and El Hierro, were conducted respectively seven and eight semi-structured interviews with key informants falling in the following categories: 'promoters and pioneers', 'third parties' (a category including the business-private sector, local authority officials, civil society representatives, and other stakeholders), 'key supporters' (stakeholders, social actors and public authorities which developed a significant role at any moment of the process), 'recipients and beneficiaries of the initiative', and finally 'experts in social innovation' (see Table 6.1 below). Interviews focus on key factors influencing social acceptability and social dynamics fostering citizens' acceptability of becoming 100 % renewable energy islands.

Table 6.1. Key informants interviewed per case study and category

Case study	Promoters	Stakeholders	Key supporters	Beneficiaries/ recipients	Experts	Total of participants
El Hierro	4	2	-	2	-	8
Samsø	4	3	-	-	-	7

In the case of El Hierro, primary data was also completed with information gathered by the researchers during field visits to El Hierro (2018) and during a multi-stakeholder policy scenario workshop conducted in El Hierro (October 2020).

The key findings of Samsø are drawn mainly from the analysis of the interviews conducted in D6.1 and from the research previously conducted on secondary data and reported in deliverables D3.1 and D3.4. The most relevant variables for the case of Samsø are grouped into the categories 'attitudinal factors', 'costs and benefits', 'capabilities and resources' and 'contextual variables'. Further, a policy

Deliverable 4.2

Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions in SMARTEES case studies

scenario workshop was conducted with social innovation promoters, stakeholders and experts in Samsø in November 2020.

6.2.2 El Hierro survey

In El Hierro, a representative survey was carried out on the island. A sample size of 369 respondents was used (total population: 9,267), at a confidence level of 95% (5% margin of error), stratified by age and gender. Four age groups were used for stratification (18 to 35; 36 to 50; 51 to 65; 66+). The survey was carried out in the month of June 2020, using face-to-face questionnaire administration. Section 6.4.1, below, describes how data from the survey was employed in the agent-based model.

6.2.3 Secondary data sources

Secondary data has been used in El Hierro to define the profile of agents in the model, their social network, as well as the interactions among the critical nodes and humans. Further, secondary data was used also for the analysis of the impact of the different communicative strategies and actions for gaining social acceptability towards the SI. A number of secondary data sources were specifically selected for the analyses relevant for the implementation of choice behaviour in the ABM:

Table 6.2. Secondary data sources used

Case study: El Hierro
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Socio-demographic data of island population (source: Canary Island Statistics Office) ▪ Results of elections 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 in El Hierro (Source: Spanish <i>Statistical Office</i>) ▪ Reports about the public subsidies conceded in 2018 and 2019 by the island council for renewable energies installations and electric car purchasing ▪ Press releases and information published by the critical nodes in Websites and social media: Ossinissa (ecologist NGO) Podemos (political party). ▪ News coverage in local digital media: Diario Elhierro.es and Gaceta del Meridinao (systematic search in both websites with the terms “Hierro 100% renovables”, “Gorona del Viento”). ▪ Critical Nodes Social media impact: number of followers in social networks (Facebook and Twitter) ▪ Mass media audience: number of followers in Twitter and Facebook.
Case study: Samsø
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Socio-demographic data of the island population (source: Danmarks Statistik) ▪ Minutes from the meetings held in the village of Onsbjerg ▪ Reports on the Samsø Renewable Energy Island project by the Energy Academy ▪ Local news coverage for the Onsbjerg district heating case ▪ Academic articles covering the case of Samsø ▪ Website of the Energy Academy (energiakademiet.dk)

6.3 Key findings

6.3.1 El Hierro

Survey results reveal that, in general, the opinion regarding the benefits brought by the 100% renewables project is positive (response scale from 0 = totally disagree; to 6 = totally agree), especially in terms of the reputational gains for the island, such as having contributed to the image of the island as innovative (mean = 5.25 and sustainable = 5.01) (See Table 6.3). Environmental benefits of the project for the island are also perceived by residents. At the other end of the spectrum, there is a lesser degree of agreement regarding the project contribution to the islanders’ identity (mean =2.86).

Table 6.3. Perceived benefits of the “100% renewable energy project” in El Hierro

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
The Project has contributed to the “El Hierro” brand	373	0	6	4.38	1,389
It is positive for the environment	373	0	6	4.68	1,306
Will make the island energetically self-sufficient	373	0	6	4.27	1,403
Will reduce the price of energy in the future	373	0	99	3.71	7,225
Has contributed to the image of the island as sustainable	373	0	99	5.01	7,047
There is more tourism on the island	373	0	99	4.39	11,194
Has contributed to the image of the island as innovative	373	0	99	5.23	8,568
Will help reduce energy bills	373	0	99	3.66	10,124
Is part of our islander identity	373	0	6	2.86	2,043
Will bring economic benefit	373	0	99	4.28	5,132
Valid N (listwise)	373				

When evaluating the general opinion of residents of the Project, we see that almost 70% of the sampled population has a positive opinion, although a significant 29% states their opinion is neither positive nor negative. It is unclear at this point what are the dimensions that might account for this latter result. Interview data suggests that some of the residents perceive the project as not having contributed to personal benefits such as reducing their energy bill, which might be a partial explanation for this result (Table 6.4).

Table 6.4. General evaluation of the “100% renewable energy project” in el Hierro

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very negative	4	1.1	1.1	1.1
	Negative	1	.3	.3	1.3
	Slightly negative	4	1.1	1.1	2.4
	Neither negative nor positive	108	29.0	29.0	31.4
	Slightly positive	121	32.4	32.4	63.8
	Positive	61	16.4	16.4	80.2
	Very positive	74	19.8	19.8	100.0
	Total	373	100.0	100.0	

Regarding voting intentions (Table 6.5), 41.3% of the sampled population are in favor of extending the project, while a significant 50.1% is not sure what their vote would be. A partial explanation can be found in the fact that initial communications on the project did not address some of the expectations and concerns regarding benefits that the islanders would draw from the project. A misconception was that the project would reduce the price of energy in households, which was not possible due to energy market regulations in Spain. Recently, better communication campaigns have emphasized the increased revenue for the island, which will be used in projects that will foster local development and quality of life, and reputational benefits have also decreased opposition to the project. It is likely that, if policy on the island follows the direction it has taken in the last few years, opinion will become more favorable for the mentioned 50% of the population.

Table 6.5. Voting intentions in El Hierro

Answer options	Frequency	Percent
Yes, definitely extend the project towards 100% production and consumption of renewable energy on the island	154	41.3
No, do not extend the project, stay with the production of thermo-electrical energy we have now	18	4.8
Go back to the previous model of using non-renewable sources for energy needs (oil, gas etc)	3	0.8
Other	6	1.6
Not sure what my vote would be	187	50.1
Prefer not to answer	5	1.3

We explored which of the evaluated aspects might be predictors of the overall positive or negative opinion of citizens of the island. We performed a hierarchical multiple regression analysis to assess the ability of perceived benefits of the project to predict the overall attitude of residents towards the “100% renewable energy” project. In the final model, perceived benefits such as the project being positive for the environment, having become part of the islanders’ identity, and having contributed to “El Hierro” branding” were statistically significant, with the score of “The project is positive for the environment recording the highest beta value (beta = .479, p = .000), followed by “it has become part of the islanders’ identity” (beta = .286; p = .000); and “it has contributed to el Hierro brand” (beta = .150 p = .015); explaining 47% of the variance in opinion (See Tables 6.1a, 6.2a, and 6.3a in the Appendix for the relevant statistical information).

Interview data sheds further light on factors that influence the social acceptability of the project “El Hierro 100% Renewable Energy”. Three factors negatively affected acceptability: the lack of confidence in the effectiveness of the social innovation, the lack of trust in the local authorities as well as the lack of information about the scope of the project and the functioning of the Spanish energy market.

- **(Lack of) confidence in the effectiveness of the social innovation.** The promoters of El Hierro had to deal with the lack of confidence of the citizens regarding the effectiveness of the energy projects. According to several interviewees, at the beginning, most of the people did not believe in the project, and they thought it had no benefits for the island. There is still a fraction of the population in El Hierro who think that this project is not relevant and “a lot of money has been wasted for practically achieving nothing” as one interviewee reported. The lack of confidence in the project is due to several factors. On the one hand, the project was mostly a “top-down” political decision in which the islanders were not actively involved, which meant they observed the project from a distance and waited to see the return of investment for the island. Due to the initial slow start of the project, scepticism about its success increased among the population. However, as one interviewee points, not all the citizenship is critical or against the project and many people are confident that Gorona del Viento has become an asset to the island: *“Not all the people on the island are negative. No, there are quite a few people who agree and believe that this project is positive for the island, for sure” (Hierro_05).*
- **Trust in the leaders of the project.** The promoters had to cope with a problem of misinformation and high expectations created among the population. Residents expected that once the energy plant became profitable, the islanders will obtain electricity for free. As they did not perceive the benefits of the investment in terms of reduction of the energy bill or any form of financial compensation from the energy plant, the islanders felt that institutions had “lied” to them, generating feelings of anger and distrust in the project, because “People

believed that 100% renewable energy would mean free electricity bills, so there is a lot of anger about that". According to other interviewees, this situation was caused by a "bad information strategy" that focused more on economic benefits than on environmental goals of the project: "it is not because of the money, it is about the air, it is because of having a clean island, it's because you can bring high-quality tourists because they are looking for precisely that sustainability. I think that part did fail, I believe that the communication partly failed, that everyone was awaiting energy for free, without any cost".

- **Lack of knowledge about the scope of the project and the functioning of the energy system.** Related to the previous point, the energy market in Spain is centralized, and energy prices are set at a central level, an aspect that was not properly included in the promoters' communication strategy and is still a misunderstanding for some of the citizens today.

The social acceptability of the project increased over time, as a result of the positive impact of the project on the local economy, the international reputation gained by Gorona del Viento as well as the strengthening of local identity as a sustainable, self-sufficient island.

- **Positive impact on local economy.** In El Hierro, the project had a positive impact on the island's economy, which enhanced citizens' support. According to one of the promoters, citizens know very well that the plant has become a key element in job creation and economic development, and some students on the island have been employed by the Gorona plant. Also, Gorona del Viento receives students and researchers from all over the world and a kind of "scientific tourism" brings visitors to the island that has been positive for the local economy.
- **Reputation as a frontrunner island in renewable energies.** The international reputation generated by its investment in renewable energy has become a relevant factor for people endorsing the project. Several key informants affirm that the islanders feel proud of being a pioneer island in renewable energies: "at the moment I believe that people already accept it very well, and with great pleasure and let's say, pride to have this infrastructure and the benefits it is giving and the repercussion it is having worldwide". The fact that the renewable energy plant of Gorona del Viento has gained national and international acknowledgement increases the confidence of residents "in their own capacity to become energy self-sufficient and make a difference, becoming an international reference for other isolated territories in the world that can learn from El Hierro experience", as one of the promoters ensures.
- **Strengthening the identity of the island as a sustainable place.** Due to the historical isolation and lack of resources in El Hierro "sustainability and self-sufficiency belongs to the El Hierro DNA and constitutes parts of the islanders' lifestyle". Thus, according to several key informants, the project has strengthened the local identity of El Hierro as a sustainable place for living and visiting, which also reinforces the feeling that their economic development should ground on sustainable projects that protect the island's natural resources.

Qualitative interviewees also explored the factors influencing the adoption of renewable energies in households and businesses. Several interviewees mention that the next step in "El Hierro 100% Renewable Energy" project is to encourage residents to install rooftop solar panels for personal consumption facilities in households and local businesses and promoters report an increasing interest in renewable self-consumption alternatives. To favour the adoption of renewable energies, engage the population and decrease the electricity consumption on the island, the government of El Hierro implemented a series of **pilot financial incentives** in the last two years. The benefits of the plant also provide the island government with funds destined to provide grants to farmers, hotels, and other business sectors to install solar panels. They have also developed sustainable mobility programs, with

the installation of electricity charging points across the island, giving subsidies to residents for purchasing e-cars and e-bikes. However, some respondents argue that subsidies might be a positive measure but insufficient.

Finally, for people to invest in renewable energies (e.g., photovoltaic technology), regulatory changes are needed. Interviewees in El Hierro regret the lack of regulations in Spain that stimulate citizen's involvement in small-scale renewable energy production. For instance, respondents refer to the so-called 'sun tax' approved in 2012 that charged Spanish households fitted with solar panels with an additional tax to remain connected to the grid. This tax has been suspended but, until the moment, citizens are reluctant to become 'prosumers' and install solar panels in their homes.

6.3.2 Samsø

In the case of Samsø, *attitudinal variables* appeared to play a role in the decision-making of actors. In particular, proenvironmental attitudes were a moderate to strong factor that led local government, farmers and the energy academy to engage in the SI's initiatives.

Further, a number of specific perceived costs and benefits regarding aspects of the SI were found. The local government was prompted to act by a sense of responsibility regarding the future of Samsø's declining economy and society. Farmers, instead, were held back by their reluctance to accept the co-operative model of ownership for wind turbines while being driven by the perceived benefits of lucrative business opportunities. Local trade actors were similarly motivated by their perception of business opportunities. For the Energy academy, a further driver was related to prosocial attitudes, i.e. the perception of the SI being suitable to deliver an increased social inclusion.

In terms of *capabilities and resources*, social status appeared to be a driver for farmers; they are relatively affluent, well connected and with a relatively high status in the community. This position allowed them to invest and negotiate the conditions of their participation in the projects.

Financial resources were acting as a driver enabling the SI to take off. The municipality and the energy academy relied on government grants which Samsø was capable of winning in a national competition. This made it possible to overcome a lack of financial resources, which otherwise would have been a decisive barrier. The farmers were the only actor that had resources to invest or use as collateral for bank loans.

Knowledge and skills were a barrier for the municipality, which initially lacked skilled staff for handling e.g. the applications for wind turbines. For the energy academy, however, it was a strong driver, which contributed to the process of launching the SI. For the other subjects, knowledge and skills enabled them to see a business opportunity, even though they lacked specific knowledge about renewable energy.

Availability of human resources acted as a barrier for the energy academy because the individuals involved were limited in relation to the work that was carried out. For the other actors, it worked mostly as a driver because they had underemployed staff looking for further projects and opportunities.

In terms of *contextual factors*, laws and regulations, along with supportive policies, were a strong driver, without which the SI would not have taken off. Particularly national government's grants and feed-in tariffs made the difference.

Media reports played mainly a positive role in helping to get the community together behind the SI' actions. Further, they criticised the initial stance of farmers pushing for private ownership of wind turbines, thereby facilitating community ownership schemes.

Habits and routine did not play a major role, but they were a barrier for actors like the municipality and the farmers who needed to come to terms with an innovative project. In the case of the municipality, this meant facing new tasks, while for the farmers, it meant adapting to new business models.

6.3.3 Points of similarity and difference between the two cases in the cluster

The cases of El Hierro and Samsø present some similarities and differences. The main similarity was that in both projects, substantial grants and favourable policies allowed the SIs to take off. Secondly, in both cases, the primary driver was to generate economic benefits for rural communities with otherwise uncertain prospects.

The main difference between the two cases regards how they developed: in the case of Samsø, there was a large participatory process that attempted to include as many economic subjects and residents as possible, while in the case of El Hierro, a top-down approach was used, arguably to make the process more efficient. In both cases, the opposition was limited and did not affect the development of the projects.

6.4 Representing choice behaviour in the model

6.4.1 El Hierro

Primary and secondary data was analysed and integrated in the agent-based model according to the following strategy:

- **Qualitative data gathered from interviews and field visits provided information that served to:**
 - 1) the identification of critical nodes in the model. A **critical node is the actor** in charge of the act of communication. In the model, four types of critical nodes are distinguished: (i) promoters, (ii) supporters, (iii) opponents and (iv) media.
 - 2) the identification of the phases, milestones and triggers. Triggers are formulated or expressed in the model in temporal terms. Specifically, the moment at which the act of communication occurred.
 - 3) the identification of the main strategies and tactics adopted by the promoters and supporters to gain social acceptability or reduce social contestation during the implementation of the social innovation.
 - 4) the analysis of the discourse of each critical node in terms of the relevant dimensions and social and experiential needs addressed through each act of communication
 - 5) the scope: the percentage of the population that has been exposed, or that has received, the act of communication.
- **Secondary data** concerning the results of local elections, social media impact of critical nodes and media audience served for building the profiles of the critical nodes and estimate their capacity of influence on citizenship. Data gathered from the analysis of the official websites and social networks of the promoters and the different stakeholders (promoters, supporters and opponents) completed the information above on the tactics adopted for gaining social support or to reject the implementation of the SI (see table 6.1, above). A number of tactics from different critical nodes were considered for each trigger.
- The **analysis of the media coverage** served as a basis for measuring the impact of each communication act delivered by each critical node. The analysis specifies whether the act of communication has been covered by the local media and, if so, to what extent or with what impact, by establishing the following categories: (i) low (a single occasional appearance), (ii) medium (at least two news items) and (iii) high (more than two news items and/or appearance

in different local media). Furthermore, the most relevant media in the island have been included as critical nodes, especially when the press intentionally tried to influence the general opinion on Gorona del Viento, supporting or criticizing it.

A table was prepared per each case with the result of the analysis of the information available about the communication actions of the critical nodes and their estimated impact, as well as the type of opinion (positive or negative) about the main milestones or triggers during the implementation process. Within each of these milestones, the communication acts (tactics) are organized chronologically to trace the sequence and highlight the oppositional or supportive reactions of the critical nodes to the promoters' communication acts. An example of how information was translated into the model is provided in the table 6.6, below. Each communication event has been listed with these characteristics:

Table 6.6. Example of a communication action, its duration, frequency, orientation and impact

Trigger	MILESTONE (specific event or period with significance for the SI development)							Opinion
	Critical node	Tactic	Duration	Frequency	Relevant dimensions addressed	Audience reached	Media coverage	
1/10/2013	Ossinissa (NGO)	Ossinissa' critics Cabildo The lack of information and transparency concerning the works in Gorona del Viento	1 day	1 day	Participation	Medium	Published in "Diario de El Hierro"	Against

Example of communicative act or tactic deployed by a critical node during the implementation of Gorona del Viento energy plant in El Hierro.

- Data from the survey was employed in the models for two purposes:

a) To fill in the characteristics of the agents and their social networks; b) To generate the population of agents so that it is compatible with the sociodemographic characteristics of the surveys as well as those of the real population of the island.

- Data for agents and social networks

The main entity of the model is the citizens that are characterized following the HUMAT model (see Del. 7.2, and 7.3). For the El Hierro model, after analysing the survey data it was determined that each citizen will have six categories of needs (dimensions), instead of the original three of the HUMAT model: (1) economic sustainability (2) environmental quality needs, referring to air pollution, (3), energy independence which refer to energy production and security of supply, (4) island prestige, (5) participation needs, referring to possibility to participate in the island decisions and (6) social needs, referring to belongingness, relatedness, social safety, social status, etc. Each of these needs is conditioned by the importance that each citizen gives to it. How much a citizen accepts or rejects the social innovation is calculated by an additive function that takes 1) how much each alternative satisfies them in each group of needs and 2) the importance that the agent gives to each of these groups. After initializing the satisfaction and importance of these needs using this survey and following the HUMAT model, the citizen agents form an initial opinion about the SI that will evolve over time due to the modification of their needs and the influence of their social networks. Questions on the importance of needs and their satisfaction from the survey will be used to build the profile of each agent (table 6.8, below).

Table 6.7. Survey data integrated in the agent-based model

Dimension		Survey question code
Energy Independence	Importance	P13_E, P14_B, P15_C, P15_E
	Satisfaction	P18_C
Environmental Quality	Importance	P14_C, P14_J, P15_B
	Satisfaction	P17_A, P17_B, P17_C, P17_D, P18_B
Economic Sustainability	Importance	P13_C, P15_A, P15_D
	Satisfaction	P18_D, P18_F, P18_H, P18_J
Prestige	Importance	P14_D, P14_E
	Satisfaction	P18_A, P18_E, P19_G, P18_I, P19_C
Participation	Importance	P14_F, P14_G, P14_H, P14_I
	Satisfaction	P20, P21

In addition to citizens, the model incorporates critical nodes, i.e., relevant actors such as the Island Council, Gorona del Viento, environmental associations, political parties and local media.

There are different social networks (friends, neighbours, etc) that connect citizens. Each pair of citizens in the same network are connected through a pair of weighted links, the weight representing the trust one agent has on the other (notice that trust does not have to be reciprocal). Similarly, critical nodes are connected to citizens through weighted unidirectional links coming from the critical node, where the weight represents the trust that the citizen has in the critical node. In this case, the number of links to generate was determined using secondary data sources (for example, Twitter followers). All trust parameters were taken from the survey.

- Generating the population

Each agent is represented by sociodemographic variables and is located in a specific place on El Hierro's map. The following state variables are used to represent a citizen:

Table 6.8. Agents' socio-demographic profiles

Variables	States (if applicable)
Age (years)	integer in [18-100]
Gender	male/female
Educational level	primary/ secondary/ tertiary
Economic activity	employed/ unemployed/ inactive/ student
Business owner	yes/no
Location	municipality section code
Homeowner	yes/no

The initial population is created from the profiles of the citizens that completed the survey. This would allow creating a population of 373 agents. In order to expand the population, we replicated these agents. However, they have to be replicated according to the real sociodemographic characteristics of the population of El Hierro, through the census data for the year 2019). As counting for every

possible combination of the 7 variables is not feasible, we have trained a decision tree using the voting intention of the agent about the expansion of Renewable El Hierro project (also available from the survey) as the variable to predict. The objective was to group the different profiles of the survey based on these characteristics, so each leaf node represents a different profile. After that, for every “empty” citizen agent one profile from the surveys is transferred, randomly chosen among those that meet the criteria for the same group.

6.4.1 Samsø

It was decided to focus on the diffusion of a heat network on Samsø as a case to model. The decision for this is based on the fact that the storyline of the development of heat networks on Samsø is a very interesting case from a social innovative perspective because of the role of norms and reputation. Additionally, it can make use of the Aberdeen model that also addresses the distribution of heat networks and where trust also plays an important role. Hence for a comparative case the heat network distribution of Samsø is interesting.

Because the first interviews mainly addressed the start of the energy transition on Samsø, most attention was spent on discussing the placement of wind turbines on the Island.

From later interviews we however derived a narrative describing the implementation of heat networks on the island.

On Samsø, the main heating technology was based on individual household oil burners, which were serviced by a local mechanic.

At an early stage, a commercial company tried to make a business case out of a heat network in one of the communities on Samsø. They concluded that it was economically not a viable business, and retracted, informing the local community by mail that a heat network was not a realistic option. This basically formed a negative attitude towards heat networks.

Additionally, the population on Samsø is rather old, and especially the elder people often indicated not to be interested in making an investment in their house.

At a later stage, a project was started at the mainland of Denmark to promote heat networks. An engineer from the mainland visited Samsø, and encountered this negative attitude towards the new heat network plan. Additionally, the more trusted heating expert on the island was the local mechanic, who also had a strong negative attitude towards the heat network as it would put him out of business.

Also the local priest was opposed to the project, fearing that the fuel-plant would deteriorate the view.

When the mainland project managers included the local mechanic in the project, offering him new business by becoming responsible for the straw-fueled plant that would generate the heat, the opinion of the local mechanic changed. Having now a reputable local person advocating the heat network project made many people reconsider their opinion, and ultimately a critical mass of people joined the project, serving as a tipping point to also include people that were initially not interested in joining.

When the first heat network was running satisfactory, two other communities could tap into the positive experiences of the first project, and the heat network projects in these two following projects demonstrated a more smooth adoption process.

Currently, three straw-fuelled plants are producing district heating, and 70% of the energy needed for heating homes originates from locally grown biofuel.

The choice of modelling the heating network development is also exemplary of some of the findings highlighted in section 6.3.2. The actors involved in the specific case of heating networks are (as further detailed in the next section): residents, divided into promoters and uptakers, the energy academy and the plumbers. In this case, like for other types of projects developed on the island, ‘attitudinal variables’ played a role, although they were not equally relevant for all the actors involved. Pro-environmental attitudes undoubtedly acted as a driver for the energy academy and to an extent for the promoters, while this driver was much weaker (or irrelevant) for the uptakers and the plumbers. Prosocial attitudes were a significant driver for the promoters and the energy academy, who were concerned with making the heating supply financially more sustainable for everyone on the island. Finally, with regards to attitudes, it appears from reading the minutes of the promoters’ meetings that the plumbers and the uptakers were motivated strongly by a gain orientation. In the first case, the plumbers who, initially, resisted fearing to lose the business of maintenance and repairs of oil-fired stoves, later supported the project when they were involved as contractors; while the uptakers, some of whom were sceptical, particularly the elderly, were granted very low fees and grants to join the scheme at low or no cost. ‘Capabilities and resources’ played a role in various ways. Skilled individuals in the energy academy could support the process and offer guidance, further, local companies, which in some cases accepted to own and operate the facilities, had the competence to engage in the project. Financial resources were again an important driver: while usually district heating projects on the main-land often required from households hefty investments to join the network, in these projects, the fees were very low thanks to government grants, and further grants were available for those households intending to convert from electricity to district heating⁵. ‘Contextual factors’ like laws and regulations played a positive general role shared with other interventions in the island that benefited from government grants. Finally, as a contextual factor, can be mentioned the role of local media that amplified the themes of the debate surrounding the plants: initially, concerns regarding air quality were voiced, while later the coverage was positive.

Modelling the diffusion of heat networks on Samsø

The agent-based model focuses on mobilizing residents of the Samsø town of Onsbjerg to participate in a district heating network project implemented in their neighbourhood. This was one example of district heating implemented on the island, along the Nordby-Maarup and Ballen-Brundby cases. The main elements of characteristics of the heat network project, also characteristic for the entire social innovation, and reflected in the agent-based model include:

- A bottom-up approach, driven by a small number of active members of the local community building an alliance with expert organization of Samsø Energy Academy (Energiakademiet),
- Progressive character of the consensus building through negotiation and dialogue to overcome conflicts and resistance,
- Credible and transparent communication (e.g., open minutes from the meetings and open budget documents),
- Resident co-ownership of the district heating infrastructure and the related economic gains,
- Energy Academy's capitalization on the experience (and lessons learned) through the set-up of three district heating networks in different parts of the Island.

The model will be evaluated positively if it is able to correctly reproduce the pattern of households willing to join the district heating network under a scenario representing the history of the case.

⁵ PlanEnergi (2007) *Samsø – a Renewable Energy Island 10 years of Development and Evaluation*. Available at: <https://energiakademiet.dk/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/samsø-renewable-energy-island.pdf>

Available historical data show the following dynamic of the district heating's popularity among Onsbjerg household residents (Table 6.9)⁶.

Table 6.9. Dynamics of popularity of the district heating network among Onsbjerg residents

Date	Joining	Not joining	Unknown decision
20.02.2001 ⁷ (initial interest)	31	10	NA
15.03.2001 ⁸ (initial interest)	59	44	20
15.05.2002 ⁹ (pre-construction)	63	NA	NA
11.2002 ¹⁰ (ongoing-construction)	69	NA	NA

Entities, state variables, and scales

Typical nodes/agents present in the model are residents of the Samsø island, divided into two groups. Residents of the Onsbjerg district where the heat network is installed, and residents of other districts. Individual residents have a set of *needs* that includes the motives of:

- Affordability (experiential need),
- High air quality (experiential need),
- Safety (experiential need),
- Renovation inconvenience (experiential need),
- Social need,
- Ecological values,
- Islander identity (value),
- Aesthetics (value).

Moreover, Islanders have a set of beliefs (cognitions) about how their current heating system and the new district heating satisfies those needs. For example, a resident might believe that the new district heating will be more affordable than the old system (+1 value of *satisfaction from social innovation* and -1 value of *satisfaction from old system of the affordability need*), and that it will be less polluting for the air (+1 value of *satisfaction from social innovation* and -1 value of *satisfaction from old system of the high air quality need*). Agents residing on the virtual version of the Samsø island differ with respect to the degree to which these needs are important to them, and with respect to beliefs about how satisfying it is to continue to use the default heating mode and how satisfying it will be to switch to the district heating network. Residents also have their individual *cognitive dissonance tolerance threshold*, which if exceeded by the preferred alternative, requires them to take action to reduce it. Moreover, residents are characterised by gender, age group, education and income levels. Individual residents form households. All resident agents living in their houses are placed in the NetLogo world fitted to the map of Samsø island. Onsbjerg residents live in their houses located in the Onsbjerg district.

Critical nodes/agents include:

- **Promoters** of the social innovation:
 - a small group of active community members (e.g., Onsbjerg district heating working group)

⁶ The numbers do not include 8 commercial businesses.

⁷ Source: Minutes from the 11th meeting of the working group; 140952 scanned document.

⁸ Source: 140952 scanned document.

⁹ Source: Samsø weekend newspaper from 15.05.2002.

¹⁰ Source: 2002 Onsbjerg district heating factsheet

- **Supporters** of the social innovation:
 - Samsø Energy Academy
 - Expert working with the Energy Academy
- **Opponents** of the social innovation; depending on the heat network implementation, those were:
 - A local plumber (Nordby-Maarup case),
 - A local priest (Onsbjerg case)
 - NRGi energy company (Ballen-Brundby case)
- **Media.**

In modelling this triple case of heat network adoption we plan to use the following model set-up for the decision making of individual agents.

First, we have 3 successive cases of a heat network implementation on different parts of the island: Case A as the first project, Case B as the second project, and Case C as the final third project.

Each project is composed of 3 stages: Stage 0 – before the heat network, Stage 1 – the discussion on the heat network, and Stage 2 – the projects is implemented

The agents are in the initial situation “I”, which is the old individual fuel system, which is expensive (experiential need). Financial costs are the main issue, but environmental concerns and independence from the main-land are values that can play a role in the perception as well (value needs).

The heat network plan is situation “H”, which may result in 2 outcomes: H’ - The plan will be implemented or H” – The plan will not be implemented

The agents have a probability “P” indicating their expectation that H’ will happen. P can be a personal setting (optimism - pessimism), but P is also dynamical. When a project reaches stage 2, agents P is set at 1.

The value of P depends on:

- If earlier projects were successful (applies not to the initial case A, more to the second Case B and most to the last case C)
- The P of alters being communicated with (opinion dynamics)

The (expected) need satisfaction of agents and hence preference for H’ or H” depends on the three needs:

- **Experiential:** relates to the financial costs (return on investment -roi) and time invested. Financial costs are weighted heavily.
- **Social:** depending on how many alters advocate H’ versus H”
- **Values:** ecological, esthetics (priest)

For I this is a single weighted calculation of E + S + V

For H this is $P * H'(E + S + V) + (1-P) * H''(E + S + V)$

Agent attributes:

- A higher income may result in a lower importance of the costs – experiential need
- A higher age may result in a higher importance of costs – roi is low

Communication by hubs (Energy academy, the local mechanic, the priest) has an impact on the values of the E, S and V for I and H’.

Deliverable 4.2

Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions in SMARTEES case studies

The Samsø model will be capable of demonstrating the resistance and acceptance of the heat network as a function of its properties (mainly financial) and the social support for joining this project. We expect that the model will be capable of identifying tipping points in the acceptance of such a project. The occurrence of these tipping points can be related to the success (or failure) of earlier projects, information supply by e.g., the Energy academy, and of the impact of trustworthy influencers such as the local mechanic and the priest.

For more information on modelling the the Samsø case we refer to Deliverable D7.3.

7. Third cluster: Energy efficiency in district regeneration (Malmö and Stockholm)

7.1 Aims of the analysis

The broad aims of the data analysis undertaken in the Malmö and Stockholm cases were:

- To identify key variables from the interviews and workshops for analysing behavioural choices around district regeneration interventions
- To investigate the effects of sociodemographic, socio-economic and other factors on these behavioural choices
- To explore how other people in an individual's social network, institutions and information sources might influence energy-related behavioural choices, comparing the Malmö and Stockholm contexts
- To stimulate discussions with the agent-based modellers about how the empirical findings can inform the models

7.2 Approach

In both Stockholm and Malmö, seven interviews were conducted with respondents in the following categories: 'promoters and pioneers', 'third parties' (a category including business-private sector, local authority officials, civil society representatives, and other stakeholders), 'key supporters' (stakeholders, social actors and public authorities that developed a significant role at some point during the process), 'recipient and beneficiaries of the initiative', and finally 'experts in social innovation'.

Further, a joint workshop was conducted with city managers, researchers and consultants of both Malmö and Stockholm.

The key findings of Malmö and Stockholm are drawn mainly from the analysis of interviews conducted in D6.1 and from previous research on secondary data, e.g. documentary sources, and reported in deliverables D3.1, D3.4 and D7.3.

The most relevant findings for both cases are grouped into categories named: 'attitudinal factors', 'costs and benefits', 'capabilities and resources' and 'contextual variables'.

7.3 Key findings

Malmö

Within the category of *attitudinal factors*, general environmentalist predisposition was regarded to be a variable acting as a driver for most actors to various degrees. In particular, it was a secondary yet relevant driver for the municipality, while it was a primary driver for the MKB (Malmö Kommunala Bostadsbolag Fastighets AB, Malmö municipality's housing company) concerned with flooding and energy efficiency of the buildings. Further, it was a strong driver for some of the NGOs involved in the project and for the Augustenborg Greenhouse residents, a subgroup of residents involved in a specific sustainable living project, while it did not play a significant role for the general group of residents of the neighbourhood.

Another attitudinal driver that appeared to be significant for MKB was prosocial values, i.e. the wish to create a more socially inclusive living environment in the neighbourhood. This also acted as a driver for the residents of the neighbourhood. Similarly, these attitudes influenced NGOs, which were concerned with improving community cohesion.

A number of perceived *costs and benefits* played a role in influencing the choices of the actors to start or engage with the SI. They appeared to be diverse and related to the nature and objectives of the actors. For the municipality, a primary driver was the foreseeable benefit of improving the image of the neighbourhood and thereby of the city itself. Further perceived benefits, acting as drivers, were solving the flooding problem in the neighbourhood and increasing its safety and social inclusion. Finally, a secondary perceived benefit driving the municipality was that of improving the political image of the city administration.

For MKB, the benefit of solving the drainage issues and reducing the problem of flooding was also a driver, as it was improving the general quality of the housing units. At the same time, the cost of interventions and the risk of having to improve the rental rates was acting as a barrier for the housing association.

For the involved NGOs, a number of drivers were identified that aligned with prosocial attitudes, for example, increasing participation and creating and strengthening networks within the neighbourhood and with other community organisations and the institutional subjects.

Regarding residents, the main drivers influencing the choice to engage in the SI related to the expected benefit of seeing the flooding problems solved; further, expectations of general improvements in the buildings and in the area acted as drivers. There were expectations of improving the negative image of the neighbourhood too, which strengthened the wish to participate.

Finally, the specific subgroup of residents engaged in the Greenhouse Augustenborg residential project (cf. D3.1) were mostly driven by proenvironmental attitudes; nevertheless, a secondary driver was their expectations to reduce energy bills.

In terms of *capabilities and resources* that influenced the actors, availability of financial resources were regarded as a major driver towards implementing the SI's activities for both the municipality and MKB; this was also a driver for residents who otherwise would have needed to contribute financially, through increased rents, which did not happen. For the NGOs, it acted as a potential barrier; however, the municipality worked towards their inclusion, providing seed funding.

The lower social status of some residents appeared to be a barrier and greater efforts were required to include these residents in participatory activities.

Finally, knowledge and skills were considered primary drivers, influencing the ability of all the organisations involved to design, implement or engage suitably with the SI.

Contextual variables also played a role in this SI case. It is worth mentioning that laws and regulations created a positive institutional framework that influenced both the municipality and the MBK, in terms of national policies encouraging actions by the municipality to regenerate neighbourhoods, with programs and grants and regulations prescribing building standards that MBK needed to uphold.

This group of variables includes media reports, which, in the form of negative coverage, appeared to reinforce the initial intention to act by the municipality, MBK and NGOs. At a later stage, when positive reports appeared about the SI, they possibly reinforced the participation of residents.

Stockholm

In Stockholm, *attitudinal variables* played a role, particularly proenvironmental attitudes. This was true particularly for one of the city departments involved in the SI (the environmental health administration), but such attitudes were a weak driver for the urban planning administration and a moderate driver for the politicians.

Within attitudinal variables, lack of trust played a major role at first as a barrier for residents' engagement. Residents initially did not trust either the actions of Svenska Bostäder (SB), the housing company owned by the municipality, or those of the union of tenants.

Prosocial values, e.g. social inclusion, were a major driver for the design and implementation of the SI for all the organisations involved. In the case of residents, place attachment played a role, initially fuelling resistance to interventions that were seen as threatening and, at a later stage, working as a driver when residents' trust was gained by the institutional actors.

Perceived costs and benefits related to the SI varied by actor. In some cases, these related to the attitudinal variables just mentioned, e.g. improving the environmental quality of the neighbourhood or achieving more social inclusion. For politicians and institutional actors, there was the perception of a political gain from tackling some of the issues of a troubled neighbourhood. Besides the environmental gains and the social inclusiveness improvements, safety of the neighbourhood and an improved reputation were regarded by politicians and SB as benefits stemming from the SI's implementation. Safety was also a concern for residents who, after the initial period of trust, perceived improved safety to be a benefit of the SI.

Initial resistance by the union of tenants and the residents themselves was based on the perception of a number of costs, including concerns about an increase in rents and having to relocate outside of the community during the period of refurbishment of the buildings. These concerns were overcome in the initial phase when a process of dialogue with the residents was established.

In terms of *capabilities and resources*, the presence of a large community of immigrants in the neighbourhood meant that many had limited Swedish language skills, which made the participation process more challenging. Further, within the same groups, it was harder to involve women in participatory activities because of their more traditional role and status within the immigrant cultures.

Financial resources were necessary to support the SI's initiatives; therefore, they were a primary driver for the institutional actors and for SB. Some funding was recruited through national schemes for urban regeneration, which underlines the importance of supportive policies (one of the contextual factors that was found to be most relevant).

Other capabilities and resources found to be significant were knowledge and skills, particularly among residents, whose lack of understanding of how local institutions worked contributed to the initial lack of trust. At the same time, institutional actors' lack of awareness of how the neighbourhood community would perceive the planned initiatives meant that the initial approach was too prescriptive and perceived as threatening. Human resources appeared to be a significant driver to start, lead and facilitate the SI. In SB, the initial absence of a skilled facilitator was a hindrance that was later overcome.

The most significant *contextual factors* were laws and regulations, which limited the scope of the SI and forced the renouncement of a wind energy feature that was initially considered. Also, supportive policies held an important role, driving the actions of institutional actors and favouring residents' engagement. Finally, media reports played a role, because their negative coverage of the neighbourhood's problems prompted politicians and institutional actors to tackle them at first, then, during the implementation of the SI, positive media coverage strengthened residents' participation and heightened the commitment of actors.

Points of similarity and difference between the two cases in the cluster

The SIs carried out in Malmö Augustenborg and Stockholm Järva cases present significant similarities. In both cases, low-income troubled neighbourhoods hosting large communities of immigrants were targeted. In both cases, Swedish national policies and grants provided a supportive institutional context which was fundamental in starting and successfully implementing the SI. In Järva, the process of participation was initially deficient, and this prompted a strong adverse reaction by residents who felt threatened by initiatives that they considered to be impositions on their community. The problem was successfully dealt with by the institutional actors and the housing association, which reacted by building an extensive participatory process.

7.4 Representing choice behaviour in the model

Since the Malmö and Stockholm cases share many similarities, the Stockholm model is going to be used for the Malmö case by adapting the relative data sources.

The networks produced and reported in D6.1 (Pellegrini-Masini et al., 2019) were used to determine the key actors of the model and their connections. After several iterations, the conceptual model represented in Figure 7.1 was drawn and used to drive the development of the agent-based model.

The population census was used to determine the percentage of foreign-born residents. The model reads the data and determines the number of foreign-born residents for each city district. The collection of reports produced by the city council was used to determine the different characteristics of the apartments owned by the social housing company.

Secondary data are going to be used to determine agents' socio-demographic attributes, including: income level, age, class, and culture (a binary variable that indicates whether someone was born in the country or foreign-born).

Some of the central concepts of the HUMAT framework (Antosz et al. 2020), were used to inform the representation of citizens in the agent-based model. In particular, each citizen will have a set of different needs. Basic needs are the most important factors for living, such as the ability to pay for the rent and electricity consumption. Social need refers to the sense of belonging to the community and is satisfied by a high rate of social cohesion (at the district level) and the opportunity to enjoy green spaces where people can meet. The final need refers to the satisfaction of pro-environmental values, which is satisfied, again, by the presence of green areas and green mobility.

Figure 7.1. Conceptual model produced from the elaboration of the actors' networks.

Deliverable 4.2

Integrated overview of choice behaviour and energy transitions in SMARTTEES case studies

8. Fourth cluster: Urban mobility with superblocks (Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona)

8.1 Aims of the analysis

Drastic changes generate a variety of reactions, from enthusiastic supporters to vigorous, active opponents. Energy-related social innovations are characterized by such reactions, due to their novel and sometimes quite radical character. Over time, the proportion of people who enthusiastically support social innovations changes, in some cases transforming our expectations and views of what is normal. The dynamics of social transformation, and the social acceptability of innovations, are complex and contingent upon many factors, events and interactions between different elements of the social system. In SMARTEES, we have set out to understand the trajectories of successful cases of social innovations, understood as those that have reached a point where going back to how things were before the social innovation is not possible, i.e. they have altered the system and what we consider normal practice in ways that are irreversible (Avelino et al., 2019). As the social innovations studied in the project have longer or shorter histories, they are at different stages of transformation.

The main objective of the superblock model in the cities of Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona is to drastically alter mobility inside neighbourhoods, in order to reclaim public spaces for other uses, such as recreation and social life. The model simultaneously aims to transform mobility to mitigate climate change, reduce air pollution to increase health and wellbeing, enhance street safety, and create spaces and opportunities for social interaction. Neighbourhoods and cities are to become attractive, clean, safe and friendly places to live.

Although these all seem like worthwhile objectives, disruptions in habitual practices of car-based mobility and alterations in commercial, logistical and transportation systems have generated public debate. The cases of Vitoria and Barcelona illustrate how public opinion has changed over time and has become dominantly favourable, thus making them successful cases of socially innovative interventions and yet in both cases there is still ongoing debate regarding the shape and extension of the model to a city-wide scale.

We are interested in the factors that influence individual and social endorsement of the model, and the factors that influence the dynamics of public opinion formation, to reach either positive or negative tipping points. At the individual level, we are interested in what the level of acceptability is now in the different superblock intervention areas, and how psychological needs and subjective evaluations of superblocks influence overall acceptability of the model. At the social level, we are interested in how social interaction, social networks, as well as policy interventions, interact with individual factors to create social influence dynamics that steer acceptability in one direction or another.

8.2 Approach

To provide answers to these complex questions, we have adopted a mixed-method research design which includes qualitative, quantitative and social simulation methods, and have used both primary and secondary data collection and analysis, as described below.

8.2.1 Semi-structured interviews

A series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with a sample of promoters (policy-makers), supporters, stakeholders and beneficiaries of the SI (see Table 8.1). Out of the 24 interviews carried out in both cities, 20 were conducted in person, three were conducted online, video-camera activated, and one interview was carried out over the phone.

Table 8.1. Key-informants interviewed per case study and category

Case study	Promoters and pioneers	Stakeholders	Key supporters	Beneficiaries	Experts	Total no. of participants
Vitoria-Gasteiz	4	2	2	4	0	12
Barcelona	2	3	3	3	1	12

The objectives of the interviews were to better understand the history and trajectory of the social innovation from its beginnings, and to identify motivations behind it, dynamics of acceptability and resistance, and factors contributing to empowerment and disempowerment and the role they played in patterns of acceptability and resistance. Some of these dimensions have already been presented elsewhere (Del 3.1, Del 3.2, Del 5.1). For the objectives of this report, data were analysed on factors influencing social acceptability for energy innovations: (1) main actors and stages of the social innovation, as well as turning points in public opinion; (2) strategies to achieve support and acceptability; (3) factors affecting acceptability, resistance, contestation and non-involvement.

Interviews were also completed with information gathered by the researchers during field visits to the two cities (2019), as well as from the discussions delivered in the first round of policy scenario deliberative workshops conducted in Barcelona and Vitoria-Gasteiz in October 2020. Following a multi-stakeholder approach, these policy workshops provided rich information about the best strategies for the implementation of superblocks and the definition of policy alternatives to overcome citizen resistance and increase public acceptability and will be fully reported in Del 5.2.

8.2.2 Survey

Surveys were carried out in both the cities of Vitoria and Barcelona. In the case of Vitoria, a sample size of 865 respondents was used, representative of the entire city at a confidence level of 95% (5% margin of error), stratified by age and gender (total city population: 253,765). In this case, our interest was not only to investigate social acceptability dynamics in the superblock implementation areas, but also to understand the extent to which the model has been endorsed at a city-wide scale. In order to gather sufficient data in the two superblock selected neighbourhoods of Sancho el Sabio and Judimendi, we oversampled them, to achieve a sample distribution of 119 respondents from Sancho el Sabio, 120 from Judimendi, and the rest of 626 respondents proportionally represented the other areas in the city. The Sancho el Sabio superblock was the first superblock implemented in the city, and is considered by many the pilot and model intervention. Judimendi represents a newer, still unfinished intervention, illustrating some of the difficulties associated with the model. The survey was carried out in the month of September 2020, using a mix of face-to-face and telephone questionnaire administration, although the majority of questionnaires were applied in face-to-face interviews. The telephone option was offered to respondents who preferred not to have direct contact with the interviewer, because of the pandemic.

In the case of Barcelona, we carried out a survey in two superblock implementation areas, Poblenou and Sant Antoni, chosen due to their very different public participation models and public acceptability dynamics (the former, very polarized in its initial development stages, the latter, less so). With the support of two colleagues from the Planning Department of the City Council, we mapped both the area streets where interventions have been carried out, as well as the surrounding neighbourhood areas that experience both the benefits and some of the potential drawbacks of the model. We used a representative sample of 643 respondents, for the neighbourhoods of Sant Antoni (total population 21.113) and Poblenou (total population: 7.036), divided as: 378 respondents in Sant Antoni, and 265

in Poblenu, also stratified by age and gender. Four age groups were used (18-29; 30-44; 45-59, and 60+). The survey was carried out between the 27th of July and the 6th of August, and the 24th of August and 3rd of September, using face to face interviews.

8.2.3 Selection and analysis of secondary data sources

Secondary data has been used to both frame the findings of the case and fill in some of the gaps in its timeline and trajectory, as well as to define agent profiles and interactions in the social simulation (see section 8.4). Moreover, secondary data was used to identify key communicative actions of main involved actors, following particular triggers, as well as to quantify impact of each of these actions on citizens. The following data sources were analysed:

Table 8.2. Secondary data sources used to identify communicative tactics, their triggers and impact

Case study: Vitoria-Gasteiz	Case study: Poblenu superblock (Barcelona)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Socio-demographic data of city population (source: City Council Statistics Office). ▪ Results of local elections 2007 and 2011 in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Source: Spanish Statistical Office). ▪ Reports about the participatory process and communication campaigns about the Sustainable Mobility Plan. ▪ Survey on mobility behaviour conducted in the CIVITAS Modern project. ▪ Press releases, dissemination brochures and assessment reports published by Vitoria-Gasteiz City Council ▪ Press releases and information published by the critical nodes: <i>Gasteizko Bizkikleteroak</i> and <i>Gasteiz-ON</i>. ▪ Newspaper: EL Correo, Diario de Alava, and other local radio (systematic search in Vitoria-Gasteiz’s press archive with the terms “supermanzana”, “plan de movilidad sostenible” “Sancho el Sabio”). ▪ Social media impact: number of followers in social networks of critical nodes. Social networks consulted: Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. ▪ Media audience: General Media Study (years: 2008, 2009, 2010). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data from the results of local elections 2015 and 2019 in Barcelona (Source: Spanish Statistical Office). ▪ Press releases published in Barcelona city council Website: Barcelona.cat (period 2015-2019). ▪ Reports about the participatory process on City Council superblocks’ website. ▪ Information about the SI published in the websites of critical nodes (e.g., <i>Poblenu residents’ association</i>, <i>Colectivo Superilla Poblenu-CSP9</i>, political parties, <i>Plataforma de Afectados por la superilla de Poblenu</i>). ▪ Media audience: Survey of media consumption habits 2017 in the city of Barcelona. ▪ Analysis of press articles, editorials and opinion pieces in newspapers (La Vanguardia and El Periódico), local TV BTV, and other digital media (a systematic search was done in Google News with the term “supermanzana Poblenu” or “supermanzana Barcelona”). ▪ Social media impact: number of followers in social networks of critical nodes. Social networks consulted: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram.

One of the limitations of the approach is that primary data gathered reflects perceptions and experiences with the superblocks today. The stages and trajectory of the social innovation has been recomposed as closely as possible using the mix of methods described. However, the impact of some of the communicative strategies had to be inferred from the available data and checked with the key informants in the case study to ensure ecological validity.

8.3 Key findings

8.3.1 Vitoria-Gasteiz

In Vitoria, the superblock model has been implemented and communicated as a series of different policies that together form the superblock intervention, and not as a holistic planning policy, as in the case of Barcelona. We have thus investigated the subjective evaluations of these different policies,

which was not the case in Barcelona. Also, we have looked at neighbourhoods where superblocks are at two different stages of development, but also investigated the acceptability of the model at a city-wide scale, unlike Barcelona, where such a city-wide evaluation would have not made sense, given the scale of the city and the fact that only a few neighbourhoods overall have transitioned to this model at the time of this analysis, although more are planned.

Interview data reveals that originally, resistance was mostly due to a fear of losing comfort and seeing business interests affected. Different sectors and profiles of the population protested against the measures adopted: the reorganization of bus lines, the restrictions in on-ground parking and the higher parking fees, as well as the pedestrianization of the city centre (with exceptions) with punitive measures (fines) for offenders. The retail sector was originally belligerent in the face of superblock proposals concerned about the negative impact that parking and mobility restrictions could have on their businesses.

At present, it seems that the level of opposition to superblocks has dropped among the population of Vitoria-Gasteiz. However, there are some voices that do criticize the City Council's claims to expand the superblock model to all the city's neighbourhoods. These voices consider that the model "should not be considered a magic solution that is valid anywhere", or, as a representative of a neighbourhood association of the central superblock explains, the expansion of the model may have negative consequences for the city. Currently, the sustainable mobility plan for Vitoria-Gasteiz is in the process of being reviewed and updated. This has also generated social protest due to new public infrastructures that are to be built such as the extension of the tram to new neighbourhoods of the city.

Public opinion and acceptability of three different elements of the superblock model in Vitoria have been analysed: the changes in public transport organization that the superblock model required (reorganization of bus lines; extensions of the tramways); changes in the use of public spaces (reforms in streets and plazas; pedestrianization of certain streets, traffic limitations in the city centre, and bike use incentivizing); and parking restrictions (changes in parking prices; restricting on-the-ground parking). Although these measures have been implemented in different stages, we checked whether citizens recognize it as part of the same superblock planning policy, by conducting an exploratory factor analysis, using Varimax rotation. All items loaded on the same factor, with a total variance explained of 67%, thus confirming that people perceive these interventions to be part of the same planning strategy. We thus also used a measure of general opinion regarding superblocks (Cronbach's alpha = .77) in our subsequent analyses.

We compared differences in the social acceptability of these different policies between the two superblock areas, as well as between each of them and inhabitants of the rest of Vitoria, by used the T-test for mean differences (see Table 8.1a, 8.2a, and 8.3a in the Appendix). One of our important findings is that the general perception of superblocks is much more positive for residents of the Sancho el Sabio superblock, than for residents of Judimendi (see Table 8.3, below; 0 = very negative; 6 = very positive), who are closer in their average evaluation to perceptions of citizens of the rest of Vitoria-Gasteiz. This demonstrates, in our view, the importance of pilot superblock areas that are exemplary in their design, providing residents with the possibility to fully experience its qualities. In the area of Judimendi, only a few superblock elements have been implemented. Differences between overall evaluations are significant between the two superblock areas specifically for the following interventions: the extension of tram lines, pedestrianization, and public spaces reforms in streets and plazas. Very interestingly, city centre pedestrianization, traffic reduction and tram extension interventions are also seen more positively perceived by inhabitants from other areas of Vitoria than

from those living in Judimendi, again documenting the importance of model superblocks in gaining public acceptability and support for its replication and generalization to other areas of the city.

Table 8.3. Mean comparisons between perceptions of superblock interventions in Sancho el Sabio and Judimendi

	SAMPLE AREA	N	Mean	Standard dev.
P5_1. Reorganization of bus lines	Judimendi	101	3.69	1,412
	Sancho el Sabio	57	3.98	1,685
P5_2. Extension of tram lines	Judimendi	112	3.55	2,013
	Sancho el Sabio	114	4.93	1,480
P5_3. Incentivizing bike use	Judimendi	117	4.49	1,808
	Sancho el Sabio	116	4.78	1,689
P5_4. Changes in parking fees	Judimendi	57	2.84	1,781
	Sancho el Sabio	43	2.19	2,003
P5_5. Reforms in streets and plazas	Judimendi	120	3.90	1,812
	Sancho el Sabio	113	4.35	1,721
P6_1. Pedestrianization of certain neighbourhoods	Judimendi	120	4.28	1,871
	Sancho el Sabio	116	5.01	1,268
P6_2. Traffic calming interventions in the city centre	Judimendi	118	4.12	1,701
	Sancho el Sabio	114	4.53	1,786
P6_3. Above-ground parking restrictions	Judimendi	110	2.20	1,915
	Sancho el Sabio	107	1.86	1,891

A look at the subjective evaluations of different elements and functionalities of the superblocks sheds some light on these differences in opinion between the different regions. Inhabitants of Sancho el Sabio perceive the place as more attractive, safe, providing easy access to local businesses, fostering conviviality and contributing to the image of an innovative city, while in Judimendi problems such as the presence of incivilities, or high pollution are rated higher. The only potentially negative consequence of superblocks rated higher in Sancho el Sabio is the rise in the cost of real estate, a consequence of the area becoming more attractive. Again, the evaluation of Judimendi and the rest of Vitoria is similar (see Tables 8.10a to 8.15a in the Appendix, for the relevant statistics).

We explored which of the evaluated aspects might be predictors of the overall positive or negative opinion of residents of Vitoria. We performed a hierarchical multiple regression analysis to assess the ability of the each of the place attributes to predict the overall attitude of residents towards superblocks. In the final model, characteristics of superblocks as attractive, providing easy access to local shops and businesses, and contributing to the overall image of the city as innovative, as well as the perceived safety of superblocks were statistically significant. The score of “attractive places” recorded the highest beta value (beta = .35, p = .000), followed by the “easy access to local shops” attribute (beta = .241; p = .000); contributions of the superblocks to “the image of the city as innovative” (beta = .168; p = .018); and “safe places” (beta = .166; p = .027), explained 45% of the variance in opinion (See Tables 8.7a, 8.8a, and 8.9a in the Appendix for all the relevant statistical information).

We also measured the social acceptance of the superblock model by asking respondents about their vote in a hypothetical polling on whether to extend the superblock model or not. A significant percentage of Sancho el Sabio residents are in favour of extending the model, with 43.7% answering with a definite yes, another 29.4% supporting it for certain neighbourhoods (the appropriateness of the model for each neighbourhood has been a part of the public discourse in Vitoria-Gasteiz), and 10.8% supporting it with certain feature modifications. Voting intentions are less positive in Judimendi

and the rest of Vitoria, with around 25% in favour of the superblocks, and a significant 35% requiring debate about its appropriateness in particular neighbourhoods. This illustrates the importance of public participation at local levels for each intervention, as well as the relevance of taking particular concerns into account, to achieve consensus regarding design. The absence of such a consensus can lead to replications of the model being rejected, potentially stopping superblock implementation in its tracks. Citizen engagement is a key aspect of a socially innovative process that can foster bottom-up creativity and ownership of the co-design and implementation, as well as a sense of place.

Table 8.4. Voting intentions in the three sampled areas

Answer options	Area	Frequency	Percentage	Total sample percentage
Yes, definitely extend the project with new superblocks	Sancho el Sabio	52	43.7%	235 / 27.2%
	Judimendi	31	25.8%	
	The rest of Vitoria	152	24.3%	
No, do not extend the project	Sancho el Sabio	3	2.5%	94 / 10.9%
	Judimendi	11	9.2%	
	The rest of Vitoria	80	12.8%	
Create more superblocks, but only in some neighbourhoods	Sancho el Sabio	35	29.4%	305 / 35.3%
	Judimendi	40	33.3%	
	The rest of Vitoria	230	36.7%	
Yes, with some caveat (more green space, more parking, more participation, redesigning bike lanes etc)	Sancho el Sabio	13	10.8%	35 / 4%
	Judimendi	6	5%	
	The rest of Vitoria	16	2.7%	
Not sure what my vote would be	Sancho el Sabio	15	12.6%	191 / 22.1%
	Judimendi	32	26.7 %	
	The rest of Vitoria	144	23%	
Prefer not to answer	Sancho el Sabio	1	0.8%	5 / 0.6%
	Judimendi	0	0%	
	The rest of Vitoria	4	0.6%	

The survey also included a question on what respondents remembered their opinion to be at the start of the whole process (see Table 8.5). Very interestingly, initial reported opinion on the matter shows that residents of Judimendi were much more positive of the intervention as compared to how they feel about it now (with 59.1 % stating they were in favour of the intervention), which is in line with perceptions of key informants, who state that the intervention was desired in this neighbourhood, as a result of a prominent car accident involving a minor. Again, this illustrates how the process and the communicative and engagement strategies used, as well as the extent to which they might respond to particular needs and concerns, are essential to gaining support. Caution is needed in interpreting these results, however, as we know perception and the memory of one's position might change as a result of current opinion and experience. Unfortunately, no data is available regarding actual opinion at the start of the superblock design and implementation process.

Table 8.5. Opinion on superblock at the start

Answer option	Sancho el Sabio	Judimendi	The rest of Vitoria-Gasteiz
In favour	56.3 %	59.1 %	40.7 %
Opposed	14.3 %	15 %	9.7 %
Neutral	10.1 %	21.7 %	18.8 %
Does not remember	19.3 %	4.2 %	30.6 %

Key informants interviewed report a series of strategies used to gain social acceptability of the model:

Active community involvement in decision-making. Enabling citizens, society actors and stakeholders to engage in decision-making processes about the sustainable mobility plan has been reported by many interviewees as one of the most effective strategies to gain public acceptance in Vitoria-Gasteiz. The promoters anticipated the resistances of citizens and residents' associations resistance and organized a series of **public meetings in each neighbourhood**. These public meetings aimed to explain the overall objective of the plan as well all engage citizens in the design of the plan asking them to make proposals of changes in those measures, they considered susceptible to be improved. The fact that both the local government representatives (e.g., the city counsellor for mobility), and city technical staff participated in all the meetings and were happy to explain the plan and receive comments and suggestions was a key element for reducing resistance and for people support the plan. Every proposal was studied, its technical viability was analysed and explained, and people felt that they really had the chance to make changes in the plan. The city council working group used all the resources they had available, including GIS data, to demonstrate the potential impact of the plan.

Targeted communication campaigns were designed by using a diversity of media. Among other actions, the city council engaged more than a hundred volunteers that served as “ambassadors” among their fellow citizens, who provided support at street level by informing citizens about the scope, possibilities and operation of the new public transport network. A media campaign was also launched which included advertising in newspapers and radio, Internet, as well as outdoor advertising in bus stops.

Educational strategies. In Vitoria-Gasteiz, the Centre of Environmental Studies together with local cyclists' associations have promoted bicycling courses for students and adult people to increase their competences for safer cycling on streets and interurban roads. Besides, the **School Agenda 21 educational program involved the school community in the city in the new model of sustainable mobility.**

Making change easy. In Vitoria-Gasteiz, the Sustainable Mobility Plan was accompanied by a radical transformation and modernization of the public transport system, including a new electric card that connected all public transport services, as well as the construction of a network of bike lanes that permit people cycling across the city. While the changes implemented facilitate citizens' daily lives, people appear more willing to substitute private car use for more active patterns of mobility or public transport use. Creating a reachable bus infrastructure and investing in cycling lines and other infrastructures were important in making travel easier for people.

Pilot projects. The pilot superblock in Vitoria-Gasteiz allowed the inhabitants to visualize to what extent a superblock increases the neighbourhoods' quality of life and, as a result, they demand similar measures in their streets and neighbourhoods. Interestingly, one of the social actors interviewed said that the first reaction to an urban or model change will always be negative. But that should not be an impediment to moving forward, as one of the interviewees ensures, “what people need is to ‘be forced’ a little, and over time the public will perceive it as positive”.

Finally, we wanted to see whether we can identify particular groups of needs that respondents identified as important, and we conducted an exploratory factorial analysis on the items that referred to the importance of particular lifestyle aspects affected by superblocks. These were initially developed in the survey with the collaboration of key informants. While the same categories of needs as in the case of Barcelona can be identified, the structure is not as clear as in the case of Barcelona,

pointing to a different perception of concerns. For example, health and wellbeing needs include air quality in the case of Vitoria-Gasteiz, while concerns about safety and parking facilities are combined with occasions to communicate with the City Council. Participation needs, such as being involved in decisions about one’s neighbourhood are associated to particular concerns, such as making the neighbourhood attractive (see Table 8.16a, and 8.17a in the Appendix).

8.3.2 Barcelona

Following a similar strategy as in Vitoria-Gasteiz, two different superblocks were analysed in Barcelona: Poblenou and Sant Antoni. They were chosen as very different cases both in terms of the final design, as well as the social dynamics involved, with much more initial polarization of opinion in the case of Poblenou, and a smoother process in Sant Antoni. Interviews have revealed that city council promoters adopted a different strategy in Sant Antoni, taking on a “facilitator” role, allowing sufficient time for addressing concerns and consensus to emerge.

Social contestation arose against a measure that was perceived as a “top-down policy” launched by the city council without the consultation with the neighbourhood. In the superblock of Poblenou, the pilot experience preceded the participatory process and, consequently, huge resistance and social contestation raised from different sectors of population living or working in the area. The lack of consultation with the stakeholders and civil organizations contributed to the “social polarization” of residents supporting or against the measure, which made it more difficult to reach agreements on the interventions on the ground. The negative pilot experience in Poblenou was mentioned as having also a negative impact on other areas of the city. As one of the promoters remembers, “when we went to a new neighbourhood, they told us, ‘we do not want a Poblenou here’”.

One interesting finding has been that the overall opinion regarding superblocks today is much more positive in Sant Antoni, than in Poblenou (T-test mean difference, significant at $p=.01$). However, somewhat paradoxically, evaluations of particular characteristics and dimensions are similarly positive in both cases, and even significantly more positive in Poblenou when it comes to evaluating it as a safe place, where it is easy to walk, and as an attractive area.

Table 8.6. Evaluation of characteristics of the superblock intervention

Group statistics					
	Area	N	Mean	Standard dev.	Standard mean error
P19. IT IS AN ATTRACTIVE PLACE	Sant Antoni	378	4.86	1.264	.065
	Poblenou	265	5.05	1.230	.076
P19. IT IS A SAFE PLACE	Sant Antoni	378	3.31	5.217	.268
	Poblenou	265	4.59	5.960	.366
P19. WALKING IS EASY	Sant Antoni	378	5.03	1.059	.054
	Poblenou	265	5.35	.898	.055

This finding further supports the view that an accommodating participatory process, where debate is encouraged and concerns are addressed, might contribute to a higher level of public endorsement. Moreover, this might be due to social influence, as witnessing a highly polarized process might lead to a more negative opinion, in spite of the experienced benefits. Witnessing the polarized opinion in Poblenou, the City Council adopted a policy of actively engaging with citizens in subsequent superblock implementations, and providing thoughtful responses to each concern, which eventually led to a wider acceptance of the model.

The importance of a true, deliberative process of participation of local communities is visible in the distribution of voting intention for the two superblocks (see Table 8.7). Although the opinion is mostly positive, we can see that it is more so in Sant Antoni than in Poblenou, where around 20% of residents are still against extending the model. An important percentage is also of the view that the superblocks should only be extended to certain neighbourhoods. This demonstrates that certain characteristics may be considered incompatible with the superblock model, and that addressing them one by one is likely to improve acceptability of the model. This seems to be more important than the frequency with which people perform certain activities in the neighbourhood, or the evaluation of particular characteristics of the superblocks, which were not significantly correlated with the overall positive or negative opinion of the superblock. It seems that attending particular concerns and giving voice to them might be a better strategy in ensuring acceptability.

Table 8.7. Voting intentions in the two sampled areas

Answer options	Area	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, definitely extend the project with new superblocks	Poblenou	99	37%
	Sant Antoni	168	44.4%
No, do not extend the project	Poblenou	52	19.6%
	Sant Antoni	49	13%
Create more superblocks, but only in some neighbourhoods	Poblenou	83	31.3%
	Sant Antoni	109	28.6%
Yes, with some change	Poblenou	14	4%
	Sant Antoni	24	4%
Not sure what my vote would be	Poblenou	14	5.3%
	Sant Antoni	24	6.3%
Prefer not to answer	Poblenou	0	0%
	Sant Antoni	2	0.5%

To account for these differences, we also looked into whether particular concerns associated with superblocks were more prominent in one area. We evaluated concerns that are addressed by superblocks (such as traffic-generated noise, air pollution, or climate change) and concerns potentially made worse by superblocks (lack of safety in the area, the rising costs of housing, acts of incivility, the rise in tourism, or the implications for local commerce). The only significant difference we found related to concerns about raising tourism in the area, which was higher in Poblenou than in Sant Antoni.

We also explored which of the evaluated aspects might be predictors of the overall positive or negative opinion of citizens in Barcelona. We performed a hierarchical multiple regression analysis to assess the ability of the each of the perceived place attributes to predict the overall attitude of residents towards superblocks. In the final model, characteristics of superblocks as contributing to the image of the city as innovative, being pleasant places for leisure and conviviality, where walking is easy, where not many acts of incivility are being committed and where it is easy to access local shops were statistically significant, with the score of “superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative” recording the highest beta value (beta = .555, p = .000), followed by “places that are pleasant for leisure and conviviality” (beta = .238; p = .000); “walking is easy” (beta = -.111; p = .000); “there are many incivilities” (beta = -.093; p = .002), and “it is easy to access local shops (beta = .078; p = .01) explaining 51 % of the variance in opinion (See Tables 8.18a, 8.19a, and 8.20a in the Appendix for all the relevant statistical information).

Similar to Vitoria-Gasteiz, we analysed the different types of needs that might motivate support or opposition to superblocks. Through an exploratory factorial analysis, we have identified five types of needs that might be relevant in how interventions are perceived and in the final acceptability of the model: health and wellbeing; environmental quality; prestige (which includes feeling proud of the neighbourhood); participation; and a mixed dimension of comfort, which includes the aesthetic quality of the neighbourhood. A clearer structure emerged in this case (see Table 8.21a, and 8.22a in the Appendix).

Similar strategies to the ones in Vitoria are reported by interviewees, to gain social acceptability of the model:

Citizen engagement. The City Council slowed down and launched negotiations with residents of Poblenu. Such negotiations required the investment of a certain amount of time and the rectification or re-adaptation of several measures adopted to solve the mobility problems in the area. As they explain, most of these participatory co-designing processes currently entail one-and-a-half years negotiating with members of the superblock promoting group and explaining future changes to citizens in several open meetings. Thus, one of the lessons learned by the promoters is that “consensus requires time and despite these processes are slower than expected, going ‘step by step’ serves to deal with contestation and gain social endorsement”. They carried out thematic participatory sessions with the sectors affected by the superblock and other interest groups in the neighbourhood (e.g., public facilities, museums, schools) and the users of such public spaces. These deliberative processes serve for discussing the different existing alternatives and evaluate consequences of the changes in real life. Flexibility to alter the initial project, based on the decisions taken by the promoter group and the contributions received in the different participatory sessions, in which 20-30 neighbours usually participate, is also mentioned as important.

Targeted communication. There are also misunderstandings and disinformation concerning the restrictions caused by the superblock that the promoters and supporters need to deal with. Citizen organizations supporting the innovation developed a communication strategy to dismantle “fake news” concerning the superblock and communicate a positive discourse of the superblocks in social media, press, radio and local television, as well as in their interactions with the district representatives of the political parties. They wanted to show the increasing social support to the superblock and counteract the critical or negative positions on the project. The interviewees highlight the importance of “doing pedagogy” and “make an effort” to explain the complex technical issues implicit in the project. Therefore, the promoters developed a targeted communication strategy by adapting their messages to different audiences focusing on the topics more relevant to each social group (e.g., retail associations, business, schools). Targeted communication also involves presenting “real data” (statistical data) based on research and environmental assessment on level of pollution, rates of accidentally and the effects on health in the area where the new superblock is to be launched.

Pilot superblocks were conceived as demonstrative experiences for people to see the benefits of the superblocks model in specific areas or neighbourhoods in the city. They aimed to create the experience of the superblock as a pleasant, clean, safe, and fun open public place to enjoy. The implementation of the pilot plan was firstly perceived by some residents as an opportunity to turn the “free area” into a place in which to celebrate Christmas and local holidays, or to organise cultural festivals or cinema activities on the street.

8.3.3 Comparing the two cases

As it has hopefully become apparent, both cases illustrate successful instances of socially innovative energy transition policies, with similar pathways and social dynamics involved in achieving social

acceptability. When initial demonstrative projects were proposed, in the case of Sancho el Sabio In Vitoria-Gasteiz, and Poblenou in Barcelona, similar patterns of resistance emerged. Both cases illustrate the importance of citizen engagement and of adopting an attitude of flexibility that allows the model to be tailored to both the physical structure and citizen concerns in each neighbourhood. A public view of a policy as imposed or top-down, or as not responsive to particular concerns, especially in the pilot projects of a social innovation, can generate wide opposition and nip particular ideas in the bud. Importantly, this is the case with each new implementation of superblocks, as illustrated by the case of Judimendi in Vitoria, where social acceptability gained in one neighbourhood, although generating positive expectations, does not automatically carry over, suggesting the importance of local engagement and adaptations. Both cases also show how important pilot cases are, allowing people to experience the new urban space.

There are two main differences between the two cases. One relates to the cities' size. In a medium-sized city such as Vitoria, the public participation process was carried out in a more centralized manner, although here as well local engagement was sought and considered necessary. In a large city such as Barcelona, placed-based engagement is particularly important. Another important difference has to do with how the superblock model was initially presented to the public and implemented. Vitoria-Gasteiz opted for a step-by-step implementation of different policies within the superblock project, as a way to gain acceptability as well as secure funding. Barcelona implemented the model as a whole. Although it is hard to say, given the particular conditions of each city, if one policy is better than the other, it does seem that presenting and implementing the model as a whole has been successful and has potentially led to a faster process of implementation.

8.4 Representing choice behaviour in the model

Primary and secondary data was analysed and integrated in the agent-based model according to the following strategy:

- Qualitative data gathered from interviews and field visits provided information that served to:

- (1) the identification of critical nodes in the model. A critical node is the actor in charge of the act of communication. In the model, four types of critical nodes are distinguished: (i) promoters, (ii) supporters (iii) opponents and (iv) local media.
- (2) the identification of the phases, milestones and triggers. Triggers are formulated or expressed in the model in temporal terms. Specifically, the moment at which the act of communication occurred.
- (3) the identification of the main strategies and tactics adopted by the promoters and supporters to gain social acceptability or reduce social contestation during the implementation of the social innovation
- (4) the analysis of the discourse of each critical node in terms of the relevant dimensions and identification of the social and experiential needs addressed through each act of communication
- (5) the scope: the percentage of the population that has been exposed, or that has received, the act of communication.

- Secondary data concerning the results of local elections, social media impact of critical nodes and media audience served for building the profiles of the key actors (represented as critical nodes in the model) and estimate their capacity of influence on citizens. Data gathered from the analysis of the official websites and social networks of the promoters and the different stakeholders (promoters, supporters and opponents) completed the information above on the tactics adopted for gaining social support or to reject the implementation of the SI (see table 8.2, above). A number of tactics from different critical nodes were considered for each trigger.

- The **analysis of the media coverage** served as a basis for measuring the impact of each communication act delivered by each key actor as well as the focus of the communication in terms of social and experiential needs addressed. The analysis specifies whether the act of communication has been picked up by the local media and, if so, to what extent or with what impact, by establishing the following categories: (i) low (a single occasional appearance), (ii) medium (at least two news items) and (iii) high (more than two news items and/or appearance in different local media). Furthermore, the most relevant media in the city have been included as critical nodes, especially when the press intentionally tried to influence the general opinion on superblocs, supporting or criticizing it. Press articles, headlines, editorials, and opinion pieces in newspapers have been included in the analysis and were considered communication acts from the critical node. In sum, more than 100 news pieces have been analysed in each case study.

A table was prepared per each case with the result of the analysis of the information available about the communication actions of the critical nodes (tactics) and their estimated impact, as well as the type of opinion (positive or negative) about the main milestones or triggers during the implementation process. Within each of these milestones, the communication acts were organized chronologically to trace the sequence and highlight the oppositional or supportive reactions of the critical nodes to the promoters' communication acts. An example of how information was translated into the model is provided in Table 8.9, below. Each communication event has been listed with these characteristics:

Table 8.9. Example of a communication action, its duration, frequency, orientation and impact

Critical node	MILESTONE (specific event or period with significance for the SI development)							
	Trigger	Tactic	Duration	Frequency	Relevant dimensions addressed	Audience reached	Media coverage	Opinion
Residents' association	Sept 2009	Collection of signatures against public transport measures	one month	Single event	Comfort	Low	Low (only 1 newspaper covered this news)	Against

Example of communicative act or tactic deployed by a critical node during the implementation of the sustainable mobility plan in Vitoria-Gasteiz

Data from the survey was employed in the models for two purposes: a) To fill in the characteristics of the agents and their social networks; b) To generate the population of agents so that it is compatible with the sociodemographic characteristics of the surveys as well as those of the real population of the city.

Data for agents and social networks

The main entity of the model is the citizens that are characterized following the HUMAT model (see Del. 7.2, and 7.3). For the superblocs model (both Vitoria-Gasteiz and Barcelona), after analysing the survey data it was determined that each citizen will have six categories of needs (dimensions), instead of the original three of the HUMAT model: (1) wellness needs, which, among others, refer to health and security, (2) environmental quality needs, referring to air and noise pollutions, (3) comfort, which, among others, refer to house price and parking, (4) city prestige, (5) participation needs, referring to possibility to participate in city decisions and (6) social needs, referring to belongingness, relatedness, social safety, social status, etc. Each of these needs is conditioned by the importance that each citizen gives to it. How much a citizen accepts or rejects the social innovation is calculated by an additive

function that takes 1) how much each alternative satisfies them in each group of needs and 2) the importance that the agent gives to each of these groups. After initializing the satisfaction and importance of these needs using this survey and following the HUMAT model, the citizen agents form an initial opinion about the SI that will evolve over time due to the modification of their needs and the influence of their social networks. Questions on the importance of needs and their satisfaction from the survey will be used to build the profile of each agent.

In addition to citizens, the model incorporates critical nodes, i.e., important entities, specifically in Vitoria-Gasteiz the following were included: city council, merchants associations, other associations and local media. In Barcelona, the critical nodes included in the model are: the City Council, Poblenu residents' associations (supporting the SI), political parties, an opponent platform from Poblenu and local media.

There are different social networks (friends, neighbours, etc) that connect citizens. The size of these networks (i.e., the number of links to create) for each citizen was also taken from a question in the survey, asking people to indicate, on average, with how many people they interact over a regular week. Each pair of citizens in the same network are connected through a pair of weighted links, the weight representing the trust one agent has on the other (notice that trust does not have to be reciprocal). Similarly, critical nodes are connected to citizens through weighted unidirectional links coming from the critical node, where the weight represents the trust that the citizen has in the critical node. In this case, the number of links to generate was determined using secondary data sources (for example, Twitter followers). All trust parameters were taken from the survey.

Generating the population

Each agent is represented by sociodemographic variables and is located in a specific place on the city map. The following state variables are used to represent a citizen:

Table 8.10. Agents' socio-demographic profiles

Variables	States (if applicable)
Age (years)	integer in [18-100]
Gender	male/female
Educational level	primary/ secondary/ tertiary
Economic activity	employed/ unemployed/ inactive/ student
Non-independent children	yes/no
Location	neighbourhood section code
Time in the neighbourhood (years)	< 3 / 3-10 / 10-30 / > 30

The initial population is created from the profiles of the citizens that completed the survey. This would allow to create a population of 865 agents. In order to expand the population, we replicated these agents. However, they have to be replicated according to the real sociodemographic characteristics of the population of Vitoria-Gasteiz, which were also available for us through the census data for the year 2016). As counting for every possible combination of the seven variables is not feasible, we have trained a decision tree using the voting intention of the agent about the SI project (also available from the survey) as the variable to predict. The objective was to group the different profiles of the survey based on these characteristics, so each leaf node represents a different profile. After that, for every "empty" citizen agent one profile from the surveys is transferred, randomly chosen among those that meet the criteria for the same group. The model world is comprised of grid cells representing Vitoria-Gasteiz city. The city is drawn through its census sections (taken from government documents), so that each grid cell group represents a section of the city. In the case of Barcelona, the Superblock of Poblenu is being modelled following a similar strategy to the model of Vitoria-Gasteiz.

9. Fifth cluster: Co-ordinated, tailored, and inclusive energy efficiency schemes for fighting fuel poverty (Aberdeen and Timișoara)

9.1 Aims of the analysis

The broad aims of the data analysis undertaken in the Aberdeen and Timișoara cases were:

- To identify key variables from the surveys for analysing behavioural choices around energy efficiency and fuel poverty
- To investigate the effects of socio-demographic, socio-economic and other factors on these behavioural choices
- To explore how other people in an individual's social network, institutions and information sources might influence energy-related behavioural choices, comparing the Aberdeen and Timișoara contexts
- To stimulate discussions with the agent-based modellers about how the empirical findings can inform the models

9.2 Approach

9.2.1 Aberdeen

The Aberdeen survey was designed to understand what influences people's decisions to join a district heating network with a view to informing the development of an agent-based model to explore scenarios for improving district heating adoption in the city. The survey comprised questions about participants' household composition, behaviour, attitudes and how they make decisions about heating their home; it took about 15 minutes to complete. As a financial incentive, participants were offered the chance to enter a prize draw to win a £100 shopping voucher.

Based on previous surveys of a similar scale, we estimated a response rate of 10%. The survey was therefore sent to 10,000 adults (aged 18+) in Aberdeen City local authority with the aim of receiving 1,000 completed surveys. Because fuel poverty is a key theme of this work, questionnaires were divided into five separate samples of 2,000 addresses in each quintile of the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD), as set out in Table 9.1.

Table 9.1. Population of Aberdeen City by Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) quintile

SIMD 2016 Quintile	Total population	2,000 sample as a percentage
1 (most deprived)	18,055	11.08%
2	45,387	4.41%
3	36,337	5.50%
4	38,974	5.13%
5 (least deprived)	90,237	2.22%
Total	228,990	

Within each quintile, and because household decision-making is also a focus of the model, the survey was sent to a representative sample of households, categorized by "Family Lifestage", a demographic segmentation based on the combined stage of life and family status of each household (e.g. young single person, young family with children, mature family with no children). Properties that were already connected to Aberdeen's Heat Network (identified by a list of postcodes obtained from Aberdeen City Council) were excluded from the samples. Samples were provided by Experian.

A paper survey, including a covering letter, privacy notice and consent form, was posted to all addresses in the samples on 16 December 2019, along with a postage paid envelope to return the survey to JHI. Participants were also given the option of completing the survey online, through a version created using Qualtrics software. The survey closed on 31 January 2020. An overall sample size of N=838 was achieved, representing a response rate of 8.4%. The composition of the sample is shown in Appendix 9.1. Despite sending equal numbers of questionnaires to each quintile of the SIMD, fewer responses were received from the most deprived quintiles. If we were to run the survey again, we would address this by boosting the number of questionnaires sent to the most deprived quintiles.

9.2.2 Timișoara

The Timișoara survey was aimed at understanding individual behaviours related to the environment and energy in general, as well as at assessing how people make decisions about energy efficiency measures in particular (i.e., perceptions about existing regional or national programmes aiming to improve the energy efficiency of homes through upgrades to the building fabric with a neighbourhood-scale heat network retrofit). For this purpose, the survey's 23 questions related to demographics (age, gender, relationship status, employment status, education, etc.), living conditions (household composition, income, etc.), place attachment, and the needs, values, behaviours and levels of trust that influence people's decisions. The questionnaire was distributed exclusively online, and it took a maximum of 10 minutes to fill in.

The data were collected using a tool specially developed for this research. The questionnaires were collected online using the QuestionPro platform (www.questionpro.com) between March and August 2020. Second-year students from The West University of Timișoara's Sociology and Human Resources Bachelors programs collected data from the survey sample. The students applied the instruments and obtained data in the Student Practical Activities program in the second semester of the 2019-2020 academic year.

Table 9.2. Demographic characteristics of respondents to the Timișoara survey

Variable	Number	Percentage
Gender		
(1) Male	149	33.9%
(2) Female	239	54.5%
(3) Not mentioned	51	11.6 %
Age group (yr)		
(1) 18-20	82	18.7%
(2) 21-35	237	54.0%
(3) 36-50	75	17.1%
(4) 51-70	29	6.6%
(5) > 70	4	0.9%
(6) Not mentioned	12	2.7%
Marital status		
(1) Married	186	42.4%
(2) Not married	225	51.3%
(3) Other	28	6.4%
Education level		
(1) Medium level (High school)	251	57.2%
(2) Superior level (University)	182	41.5%
(3) Not mentioned	6	1.3%

The survey sample is a convenience sample with a high share of young people (72.7% aged 35 and under), reflecting the fact that respondents were recruited by students. The demographic characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 9.2 (above). 239 (54.5%) respondents were female. Almost half of the respondents (54%) were between 21 and 35 years old. 225 (51.3%) were not married and 251 (57.2%) of the respondents had medium-level education (high school). Although

the sample volume is sufficiently high to ensure a reasonable representativeness of the results (95%), the sample was biased by the data collection procedure (online), since internet access is limited for certain groups of residents, e.g. older people. Another limitation of the research was the fact that we did not measure the heating systems that respondents use. This variable can be important when examining attitudes and behaviors regarding energy consumption.

9.3 Key findings

9.3.1 Understanding behavioural choice in the Aberdeen case

The Aberdeen analysis focused on behavioural choice in relation to residents' likelihood of joining a district heating scheme. Following a description of the Aberdeen Heat Network, respondents were asked: 'How likely are you to join a district heating scheme, if it was available in your area?'. Responses were made on a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from 'highly unlikely' to 'highly likely'. There was evidence of a multimodal distribution of responses (Figure 9.1), with the most common response being 'neutral', perhaps reflecting a lack of prior knowledge of district heating schemes. There were also peaks at the extremes of the scale, indicating that, while the majority of respondents were positive or neutral towards the idea of joining a heat network, a significant minority reported a strongly negative attitude.

Figure 9.1. Likelihood of joining heat network

We investigated the factors associated with these negative attitudes towards heat network uptake using a hierarchical logistic regression model predicting the likelihood of 'highly unlikely'/'unlikely' responses. Independent variables were added in three steps:

Step 1: Individual and household level factors. These included age, gender, education, relationship status, household size, presence of children in the household, dwelling type, tenure, current heating system, income, and area deprivation (SIMD quintile). Distributions of these variables in the sample are shown in Appendix 9.1.

Step 2: Home heating experiences. Respondents' experiences of difficulty keeping their home warm in an affordable way was measured using a 5-item 'heating hardship' scale (see Appendix 9.2). Internal reliability of the scale was deemed acceptable (Cronbach's alpha=0.748). Four further variables were added to represent recent experiences which may influence decisions about heating systems ('I moved house'; 'I replaced my boiler or heating system'; 'I had problems with my boiler or heating system'; 'I experienced a power cut in my home').

Step 3: Place attachment. Place attachment was measured with a single item: 'Please indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with the statement: *I feel very attached to Aberdeen*' (responses on a 7-pt Likert-type scale). The rationale for including place attachment in the model was that it may

affect people's sense of care for their local environment as well as their propensity to make a long-term financial investment in their home.

Table 9.3. Model predicting odds of respondents reporting that they were highly unlikely/unlikely to join district heating scheme

	Step 1: Individual and household factors		Step 2: + Heating experience		Step 3: + place attachment	
	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI
Age 16-24	.517	.095-2.827	.534	.092-3.098	.528	.090-3.115
Age 25-34	.455*	.209-.991	.520	.230-1.178	.487	.210-1.129
Age 35-44	.416*	.192-.900	.481	.212-1.089	.421*	.180-.985
Age 45-54	.614	.289-1.307	.770	.342-1.730	.797	.352-1.803
Age 55-64	.630	.313-1.266	.651	.206-1.387	.592	.271-1.291
Age 65-74 (ref)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age 75+	2.388	.644-8.855	3.535	.859-14.542	3.675	.868-15.565
Female	1.027	.667-1.583	1.044	.660-1.653	.962	.602-1.537
Degree education	1.099	.679-1.778	1.075	.649-1.779	1.103	.655-1.858
Married/in a partnership (ref)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Single	1.060	.544-2.062	1.605	.770-3.344	1.570	.738-3.340
Separated/divorced/widowed	.494	.235-1.038	.635	.285-1.417	.587	.258-1.334
Household size (no. of occupants)	.943	.664-1.340	1.078	.742-1.567	1.062	.726-1.553
Presence of under 16s	1.062	.503-2.243	1.132	.520-2.466	1.289	.577-2.877
Dwelling type – detached	.732	.346-1.551	.781	.351-1.739	.650	.283-1.493
Dwelling type – semi-detached	.917	.507-1.624	1.051	.553-1.996	1.068	.554-2.060
Dwelling type – terraced	.867	.463-1.624	.929	.479-1.800	.922	.468-1.816
Dwelling type – flat (ref)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Homeowner	1.239	.679-2.263	1.061	.549-2.052	1.102	.558-2.060
Gas central heating	1.436	.673-3.063	1.158	.527-2.547	1.094	.494-2.422
Other/no central heating (ref)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Household income	.973	.886-1.069	.946	.857-1.044	.956	.863-1.059
SIMD ^a 1 – most deprived	.924	.432-1.977	1.461	.629-3.392	1.514	.637-3.599
SIMD 2	.720	.338-1.532	.926	.418-2.050	.894	.396-2.015
SIMD 3	.739	.382-1.426	.807	.403-1.616	.779	.383-1.582
SIMD 4	1.207	.677-2.153	1.222	.666-2.243	1.319	.711-2.447
SIMD 5 – least deprived (ref)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Heating hardship	-	-	.593**	.455-.774	.567**	.430-.749
Moved house ^b	-	-	1.006	.344-2.947	1.065	.357-3.180
Replaced boiler/heating system ^b	-	-	.694	.295-1.629	.705	.296-1.680
Had problems with boiler/heating ^b	-	-	.591*	.352-.994	.584*	.343-996
Experienced power cut ^b	-	-	1.079	.605-1.925	1.057	.577-1.938
Place attachment	-	-	-	-	1.026	.884-1.190
N	567		542		524	
R ² (Cox & Snell – Nagelkerke)	.036-.056		.079-.123 (Δ .043-.067)		.088-.138 (Δ .009-.015)	

**p≤0.01 *p≤0.05; Ref = reference category

^a = Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation quintile; ^b = Experienced in the past year.

The hierarchical model found very few factors associated with being highly unlikely/unlikely to join the heat network and predicted only a small proportion of the variance in the dependent variable (Table 9.3). Of the individual and household-level factors entered in step 1, the only statistically significant predictor variables related to age (those aged 25-34 and 35-44 were significantly less likely than 65 to 74-year-olds to report being highly unlikely/unlikely to join). The addition of heating experience improved the model fit, approximately doubling the proportion of variance explained. Those who scored higher on the heating hardship scale (indicating greater difficulty heating their

home affordably) were significantly ($p < 0.01$) less likely to report being highly unlikely/unlikely to join a district heating scheme. This indicates that heat network uptake may be attractive to those experiencing fuel poverty, the key target group of beneficiaries for the Aberdeen Heat Network initiative. It was, however, notable that, whilst individual experiences of difficulty heating the home affordably appear to predict attitude towards heat network uptake, objective socio-economic factors of income and area deprivation do not. In addition, those who reported having problems with their boiler or heating system were also significantly less likely ($p < 0.05$) to be highly unlikely/unlikely to join the heat network. This is consistent with existing evidence that the primary reasons householders report for upgrading their heating system are breakdowns and frequent repairs needed to their existing system (Gilchrist & Craig, 2014). In the third step, after the addition of the place attachment variable, only age (age 35-44 vs. reference category of 65-74s; $p < 0.05$), heating hardship ($p < 0.01$), and having had problems with the boiler/heating system ($p < 0.05$) were associated with the dependent variable.

9.3.2 Understanding behavioural choice in the Timișoara case

In accordance with the objectives of the study, to identify the sociodemographic determinants of attitudes and responsible behaviors in relation to energy and the environment, the analysis starts with the definition of the composite variables. Three variables were differentiated and defined as follows:

- Environmentally responsible behavior (ERB), comprising questions about use of water in the home, shopping habits, waste separation and reuse of old items. To explore the structure of this variable we used the exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure verifies the sampling adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .67$ and Bartlett's test of sphericity chi square (6) = 147.1, $p < .001$, indicating that factor structure is relatively adequate for EFA. The factor that we consider explain 44.1% from the variability of items.
- Responsible energy behavior (REB), comprising questions about energy use at home, including use of heat, light and appliances. We analyzed the factor structure through the EFA and the $KMO = .80$ and Bartlett's test of sphericity chi square (10) = 571.7, $p < .001$, showed that those five items formed a reliable variable for the further analysis. The factor "responsible energy behavior" explain 54.3% from the variability of items.
- Environmental concern (EC), comprising views of climate change generally and perceptions of energy cost, reliability and dependency in Timișoara specifically. This factor is reliable because the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure has a good value ($KMO = .79$) and Bartlett's test of sphericity is below $p = .05$, chi square (6) = 675.6, $p < .001$. Environmental concern as a composite variable explains 67% of the variability of items. Then, we conducted a set of Independent t tests or Mann Whitney U tests to identify the possible significant differences between multiple categories of respondents. Different respondents were compared at the level of education (*high educational level*, university versus *medium educational level*, high school), age (cut-off at 35 years old), gender (*males* versus *females*), occupational status (*employees* versus *students*) and ownership status (*own the house* versus *do not own the house*).

The composition of these variables is described in more detail in Appendix 9.

Place attachment

Place attachment was considered because it is associated with various pro-environmental behaviours, and thus could affect Timișoara residents' decisions to protect the environment in which they live (Scannell & Gifford, 2010; Tonge et al., 2014). First, we tested whether place attachment is perceived differently by different groups of respondents. The results were mixed, and we found significant differences between different ages and between respondents with different ownership statuses.

Table 9.4. Age groups and place attachment

	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Independent t test
I am very attached to the place where I live.	=<35	323	3.58	.917	t(429) =2.941, p=0.003
	>35	108	3.87	.810	

The result is statistically significant, showing stronger place attachment among the older group. This result is consistent with the literature. For instance, developmental theories of attachment to place explain this attachment by the fact that place becomes an anchor for people's identity and shapes their sense of self. Studies investigating place attachment over the human life span found that feelings of connection to place increased as people aged (Hey, 1998).

Table 9.5. Home ownership status and place attachment

	Home ownership status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Independent t test
I am very attached to the place where I live.	Ownership	221	3.80	.899	t(436)=3.301, p=0.001
	No ownership	217	3.52	.877	

As can be seen in Table 9.5, at the level of place attachment, the average for the group of home owners is higher ($m=3.80$) than the average of the other group ($m=3.52$), and the difference is statistically significant. Studies concerned with the relationship between place attachment and home ownership differentiate between owning a property and feeling at home, the latter being an example of place attachment (Windsong, 2009). Home is a particularly significant type of place, and the fact that someone has ownership over it means assuming responsibilities as well as freedoms. Attachment to the home extends attachment to the place, by activating the feeling of rootedness (Easthope, 2004).

ERB, REB and EC

Our data showed a significant difference between the age categories related to environmental behavior. This result is consistent with the literature. In a meta-analysis of studies relating age to environmental behavior covering the years 2000-2010, the authors conclude that the association between age and behavior, attitudes and pro-environmental values is negligibly small but that older people are more likely to engage with nature and to avoid environmental harm (Wiernik, Ones, & Dilchert, 2013). Other studies show that different age groups have different attitudes towards the environment. For example, Iversen and Rundmo (2002) found that people over 60 were less positive about the environment, had more barriers to safety, and rated health and disease prevention values as significantly more important than those under 30 years of age. The younger respondents reported less frequency of positive consumer behavior and positive health behavior compared with age groups.

Table 9.6. Age groups differences related with ERB, REB and EC

	Environment responsible behaviour	Responsible energy behaviour	Environmental concern
Mann-Whitney U	14187,000	16232,000	16908,500
Wilcoxon W	66513,000	68558,000	22794,500
Z	-2,914	-1,083	-,477
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,004	,279	,633
a. Grouping Variable: Age			

Table 9.7. Gender groups differences related with ERB, REB and EC

	Environmentally responsible behavior	Responsible energy behavior	Environmental concern
Mann-Whitney U	17070,000	14943,000	15438,000
Wilcoxon W	28245,000	26118,000	26613,000
Z	-,687	-2,671	-2,209
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,492	,008	,027
a. Grouping Variable: Gender			

Our results showed that women scored higher than men on Responsible Energy Behavior, $U(149, 239)=14943$, $z=-2,671$, $p<.01$. There was also a significant difference in Environmental Concern, $U(149,239)=15438$, $z=-2,209$, $p<.05$. This result is consistent with previous studies showing that women, compared to men, have stronger pro-environmental beliefs, values, and attitudes (Dietz et al, 2002; McCright, 2010) and is explained in terms of the institutional support hypothesis, which combines the perspective of gender socialization and risk analysis theory. Thus, the explanation for this difference comes from the fact that women tend to have less confidence in social institutions because these institutions are dominated by men, and, as a result, their concern for the environment is greater than that of men (Gustafsson & Li, 2000). Another advanced hypothesis is that women are more sensitive than men to health and safety issues and have a greater tendency towards risk aversion (Xiao & McCright, 2015).

9.3.3 Importance of and trust in different information sources – Aberdeen and Timișoara

Previous research has indicated that householder decisions with respect to home energy efficiency may be influenced by a range of different sources, with some potential sources of information trusted more than others (Pyrko & Darby, 2011). With this in mind, the Aberdeen and Timișoara surveys both included a set of questions on the importance of various information sources and trust in each source. In the case of the Aberdeen questionnaire, this question was posed with respect to joining the district heat network. In the Timișoara case, the question focused on the adoption of energy efficiency measures in private buildings being undertaken by the Municipality of Timișoara.

- *How important do you think the following sources would be in helping you to make the decision... ..about joining a district heating scheme? [Aberdeen] / ...to benefit from such energy efficiency measures? [Timișoara].*
- *On average, how much would you say you trust the following sources of advice or information?*

Figures 9.2 and 9.3 show the proportions of the samples in each case study reporting high levels of importance of (Figure 9.2) and trust in (Figure 9.3) different information sources. Differences between Aberdeen and Timisoara were not tested for significance; rather, the data were analysed separately and comparisons drawn visually by looking at Figures 9.2 and 9.3. Within each of the cases, the profile

of responses is broadly similar for both importance and trust scores. For both Aberdeen and Timișoara, other people in the household and the wider family were the groups most likely to receive high trust and importance scores. There were, however, some notable differences between the cases:

- The proportion of respondents placing high importance on family, friends, colleagues/fellow students, and neighbours was higher in Timișoara than in Aberdeen.
- Energy (electricity/gas) suppliers were much more likely to be scored as important/extremely important in influencing decisions in the Timișoara sample compared to in Aberdeen. This is despite similarly low proportions reporting high levels of trust in energy suppliers across the two cases.
- In the Timișoara case, social media was much more likely to be scored high in importance than in the Aberdeen case. Trust in social media was low in both cases.
- In the Aberdeen sample, respondents were much more likely to place a high level of trust in energy advice organisations than in Timișoara. This pattern was mirrored to a lesser degree in relation to the public sector institutions of central and local government.

Figure 9.2. Importance of information sources in Aberdeen and Timișoara samples. N.B: ‘national news’ was included in Aberdeen only; ‘local schools’ and ‘local merchants’ in the Timișoara only.

Figure 9.3. Trust in information sources in Aberdeen and Timișoara samples. N.B: ‘national news’ was included in Aberdeen only; ‘local schools’ and ‘local merchants’ in the Timișoara only.

The data were also analysed using non-parametric tests to examine differences in importance and trust scores according to socio-demographic factors. Mann-Whitney U tests were used to compare scores between binary socio-demographic classifications (gender, education level, age classification), with Spearman’s correlations used to examine associations between importance/trust scores and interval or ordinal level socio-demographic variables (age in years, Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation). The results of these tests are reported in Appendix 9.5 tables A9.5.1 and A9.5.2. Age (comparing under and over 35s) was not strongly related to trust nor importance in the Timișoara case, although local news outlets were scored higher in importance by over 35s. In the Aberdeen case age was significantly (though weakly) negatively associated with trust and importance across a number of the potential information sources. There were significant differences according to gender across several of the potential information sources in both Timișoara and Aberdeen. For all of these information sources women tended to give higher trust/importance scores than men. This suggests that gender may moderate the role of social influence in energy-related decision-making.

9.3.4 Discussion

The observed differences between the cases in the levels of importance and trust attributed to different actors within an individual’s social network, institutions and information sources may be interpreted in relation to: a) differences in the profile of respondents across the two case studies; b) cultural differences between the case study contexts; and c) differences in the decision-making contexts for the behavioural choices of interest in the two cases.

Differences in the sample profiles

The survey work in the Aberdeen and Timișoara case studies followed different sampling strategies, resulting in a divergence in respondent profiles. In the Timișoara case, almost three-quarters of participants were 35 or under. In comparison, less than 20% of the Aberdeen case study was under 35. The large number of younger adults in the Timișoara sample may partly account for the comparatively high levels of importance placed upon family, friends, and colleagues/fellow students.

Younger respondents may rely more on others in their immediate social network due to a lack of personal experience in making decisions about energy efficiency measures or home improvement and maintenance more broadly. The demographic of the case study samples may also help to explain the difference in importance placed on social media in the Aberdeen and Timișoara cases.

Cultural differences between Scotland and Romania

The higher importance placed on actors within an individual's social network may relate to cultural differences in collectivistic vs. individualistic value orientations. Cross-cultural comparisons suggest that whereas the UK is a highly individualist society, Romania is considerably more collectivist (Hofstede et al., 2010). This may partly explain the higher levels of importance respondents in Timișoara placed particularly on the wider family, but also friends, colleagues or fellow students, and neighbours, in making decisions about adopting energy efficiency measures.

Other cultural differences between Scotland and Romania may exist around levels of institutional trust. Respondents to the Aberdeen survey were more likely to place a high level of trust in energy advice organisations, and also in the city council and the national (Scottish) government than in Timișoara. Mishler & Rose (2001) have noted that institutional mistrust is widespread in post-communist Central and Eastern European countries. There is some debate over whether international differences in trust in political institutions, non-governmental organisations is due to underlying exogenous cultural differences (which may extend cultural norms around intrapersonal trust to institutions) or to endogenous processes of trust-building which rely on the satisfactory performance of the institutions in question (Mishler & Rose, 2001).

Differences in decision-making contexts

Some of the differences in importance and trust scores in the two cases may also be attributable to the behavioural choices of interest in the Aberdeen and Timișoara cases. In particular, the importance questions specifically asked respondents about the importance of different sources in making the decision about joining the district heating scheme (Aberdeen) or benefiting from energy efficiency measures offered by the municipality (Timișoara). It is possible that different actors or institutions were seen by respondents to be more salient sources of information depending on the decision they were presented with. For example, the adoption of energy efficiency measures which relate to the building fabric might be thought of as analogous to other home improvements which respondents might consult individuals in their social network on. On the other hand, the adoption of district heating, a technology which many in the UK are unfamiliar with, might be seen as a decision which would be better supported by sources that have a greater understanding of the technical aspects of heat networks.

9.4 Representing choice behaviour in the model

There are various ways in which the findings above can be used to influence decision-making and other dynamics in the models of Aberdeen and Timișoara (named 'ACHSIUM' and 'HOTNESS' respectively). With respect to decision-making specifically, one of the most important findings has been in relation to the gender effect on the importance of and trust placed in various sources of information when making decisions about heating the home. Although agent-based modelling has the capability to represent individuals' heterogeneity, the use of ABMs to explore gendered issues in empirical contexts is relatively rare. In both ACHSIUM and HOTNESS, we will be able to use agents' assigned gender attribute to differentially affect the way in which they use their social networks to facilitate decision-making.

The trust model in ACHSIUM and HOTNESS is based on an endorsements mechanism (Moss 1998; Alam et al. 2010), described briefly in Deliverable 7.3 (Antosz et al. 2020). Endorsements rank different sources of information, and use an exponential weighting heuristic to determine the number of people with a lower endorsement rank needed to over-rule the advice of one person with a higher endorsement rank (assuming those with a lower endorsement all advise the opposite of the advice given by the one with the higher endorsement). The main difference between ACHSIUM and HOTNESS is that the latter implements rules allowing rankings to change based on experience of the agent in the model, while in the former, agents retain the ranking they were initialized with (based on data in the questionnaire). The findings from the surveys suggest that the gender of the agent should be a determining factor in whether social networks are consulted.

The decision-making mechanism in ACHSIUM and HOTNESS is based on case-based reasoning, in which agents store experiences with heating systems that are evaluated when considering a change. Obviously, the introduction of new heating systems means that people have little experience of them, and this allows us to simulate the value of impartial organizations offering heat advice, such as SCARF in Aberdeen. The planned approach was to have a SCARF agent provide experiences to the agents so that they could evaluate more options than they would otherwise. If men do not make (so much) use of such organizations, or do not trust them as much, decision-making will need to include parameters that provide for an individual propensity to experiment with new heating systems.

Turning to the dynamics simulated in the model, it is evident from the questionnaire survey that some of the triggers for agents to change their heating system that were allowed for during the design of ACHSIUM and HOTNESS (e.g. experience of power outages) do not act as such. Hence, this functionality can be switched off in the model, and consequently simplify its dynamics.

The questionnaire survey data itself can also be used to populate the model with agents that have an empirical basis beyond population-level data, and hence more accurately reflect intersectionality.

References

- Alam, S. J., Geller, A., Meyer, R. and Werth, B. (2010) Modelling contextualized reasoning in complex societies with "endorsements". *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* **13** (4), 6. <http://jasss.soc.surrey.ac.uk/13/4/6.html>
- Antosz, P., Jager, W., Polhill, G. Salt, D., Scalco, A., Alonso-Betanzos, A., Sánchez-Marroño, N., Guijarro-Berdiñas, B. and Rodríguez, A. (2020) SMARTEES: Deliverable 7.3 (Report) SMARTEES simulation implementations. December 2020. https://local-social-innovation.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/SMARTEES_D7.3_Simulation_Implementations_R1.pdf
- Dietz, T., Kalof, L., & Stern, P. (2002). Gender, Values, and Environmentalism. *Social Science Quarterly*, 353-364. DOI: [10.1111/1540-6237.00088](https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6237.00088)
- Easthope, H. (2004). A place called home. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 128-138 DOI: 10.1080/14036090410021360
- Gilchrist, K. & Craig, T. (2014) *Home energy efficiency – review of evidence on attitudes and behaviours*. ClimateXChange report for The Scottish Government.
- Gustafsson, B. & Li, S. (2000). Economic transformation and the gender earnings gap in urban China. *Journal of Population Economics*, 305-329. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/20007717
- Hey, E. (1998). The Watercourses Convention: To What Extent does it Provide a Basis for Regulating Uses of International Watercourses? *Review of European, Comparative & International Environmental Law*, 291-300
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (2010) *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*, 3rd Ed. New York; McGraw-Hill.
- Iversen, H.H. & Rundmo, T. (2002). Personality, Risky Driving and Accident Involvement among Norwegian Drivers. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 1251-1263. DOI: [10.1016/S0191-8869\(02\)00010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(02)00010-7)
- McCright, A.M. (2010). The effects of gender on climate change knowledge and concern in the American public. *Population and Environment*, 66-87. DOI: [10.1007/s11111-010-0113-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11111-010-0113-1)
- Mishler, W., & Rose, R. (2001). What are the origins of political trust? Testing institutional and cultural theories in post-communist societies. *Comparative political studies*, 34(1), 30-62.
- Moss, S. (1998) Critical incident management: an empirically derived computational model. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* **1** (4), 1. <http://jasss.soc.surrey.ac.uk/1/4/1.html>
- Pyrko, J. & Darby, S. (2011) Conditions of energy efficient behaviour – a comparative study between Sweden and the UK. *Energy Efficiency* 4, 393-408.
- Scannell, L., & Gifford, R. (2010). The relations between natural and civic place attachment and pro-environmental behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(3), 289–297. doi:10.1016/j.jenvp.2010.01.010
- Stinissen-Blanco A., Snijders, T.H., De Lange, J. (1999). Statistisch Jaarboek gemeente Groningen de staat van Groningen in Grafiek en getal. Municipality of Groningen.
- Tonge, J., Ryan, M. M., Moore, S. A., & Beckley, L. E. (2015). The Effect of Place Attachment on Pro-environment Behavioral Intentions of Visitors to Coastal Natural Area Tourist Destinations. *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(6), 730–743. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287514533010>
- Wiernik, B.M., Ones, D.S., & Dilchert, S. (2013). Age and environmental sustainability: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 826-856. DOI: [10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00194](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00194)
- Windsong, E.A. (2010). There is no place like home: Complexities in exploring home and place attachment. *The Social Science Journal*, 205-214. DOI: [10.1016/j.sosci.2009.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sosci.2009.06.009)
- Xiao, C. & McCright, A.M. (2015). Gender Differences in Environmental Concern: Revisiting the Institutional trust Hypothesis in the USA. *Environment and Behaviour*, 34-65. DOI: [10.1177/0013916513491571](https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916513491571)

Appendices

Appendix 6: Additional Tables for El Hierro

Table 6.1a. Hierarchical regression analysis. Perceived benefits as predictors of the attitude toward the “100 % renewable energy project” in El Hierro. Model summary

Model Summary ^d									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,616 ^a	,379	,378	,950	,379	226,895	1	371	,000
2	,684 ^b	,468	,465	,881	,088	61,389	1	370	,000
3	,690 ^c	,476	,472	,875	,008	5,933	1	369	,015

- a. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment; it is part of our islander identity
 c. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment; it is part of our islander identity; The Project has contributed to the “El Hierro” brand
 d. Dependent Variable: General evaluation of “El Hierro 100% renewable energy” project

Table 6.2a. Hierarchical regression analysis (El Hierro). ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	204,666	1	204,666	226,895	,000 ^b
	Residual	334,653	371	,902		
	Total	539,319	372			
2	Regression	252,289	2	126,144	162,608	,000 ^c
	Residual	287,030	370	,776		
	Total	539,319	372			
3	Regression	256,831	3	85,610	111,829	,000 ^d
	Residual	282,488	369	,766		
	Total	539,319	372			

- a. Dependent Variable: General evaluation of “El Hierro 100% renewable energy” project
 b. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment
 c. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment; it is part of our islander identity
 d. Predictors: (Constant), It is positive for the environment; it is part of our islander identity; The Project has contributed to the “El Hierro” brand

Table 6.3a Hierarchical regression analysis. Regression results (El Hierro)

Model		Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1,539	,183		8,395	,000	1,178	1,899
	It is positive for the environment	,568	,038	,616	15,063	,000	,494	,642
2	(Constant)	1,123	,178		6,306	,000	,773	1,473
	It is positive for the environment	,550	,035	,596	15,687	,000	,481	,619
	it is part of our islander identity	,176	,022	,298	7,835	,000	,131	,220
3	(Constant)	1,080	,178		6,073	,000	,730	1,429
	It is positive for the environment	,442	,056	,479	7,831	,000	,331	,552
	it is part of our islander identity	,168	,022	,286	7,498	,000	,124	,213
	The Project has contributed to the "El Hierro" brand	,130	,053	,150	2,436	,015	,025	,235

a. Dependent Variable: General evaluation of "El Hierro 100% renewable energy" project

Appendix 8: Additional Tables for Barcelona and Vitoria-Gasteiz

Table 8.1a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding evaluations of different superblock policies: Sancho el Sabio, Judimendi

		T-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
P5_2. Opinion about the enlargement of the tramway network	Equal variances assumed	224	,000	-1,376
	Equal variances not assumed	203,751	,000	-1,376
P5_5. Opinion about refurbishment in streets and squares	Equal variances assumed	231	,056	-,445
	Equal variances not assumed	230,984	,056	-,445
P6_1. Opinion about the pedestrianization of some blocks	Equal variances assumed	234	,001	-,725
	Equal variances not assumed	209,966	,001	-,725

Table 8.2a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding evaluations of different superblock policies: Judimendi – the rest of Vitoria

		T-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
P5_2. Opinion about the enlargement of the tramway network	Equal variances assumed	709	,002	-,602
	Equal variances not assumed	148,646	,004	-,602
P6_1. Opinion about the pedestrianization of some blocks	Equal variances assumed	731	,021	-,355
	Equal variances not assumed	148,785	,052	-,355
P6_2. Opinion about traffic calming measures in city centre	Equal variances assumed	731	,001	-,542
	Equal variances not assumed	159,703	,002	-,542

Table 8.3a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding evaluations of different superblock policies: Sancho el Sabio – the rest of Vitoria

		T-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
P5_2. Opinion about the enlargement of the tramway network	Equal variances assumed	711	,000	,775
	Equal variances not assumed	188,106	,000	,775
P5_5. Opinion about refurbishment in streets and squares	Equal variances assumed	710	,010	,470
	Equal variances not assumed	160,649	,009	,470
P6_1. Opinion about the pedestrianization of some blocks	Equal variances assumed	727	,011	,371
	Equal variances not assumed	178,064	,005	,371
P6_3. Opinion about restrictions in on-ground parking within the neighbourhoods	Equal variances assumed	701	,006	-,568
	Equal variances not assumed	150,919	,005	-,568

Table 8.4a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding characteristics of superblocks: Judimendi – Sancho el Sabio

	AREA OF THE SAMPLE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
P20_1. Level of agreement. They are attractive places	Judimendi	119	4,35	1,516
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,07	1,130
P20_2. Level of agreement. They are safe places	Judimendi	117	4,44	1,282
	Sancho el Sabio	118	4,97	1,219
P20_3. Level of agreement. It is easy to access local shops	Judimendi	118	4,40	1,715
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,50	,748
P20_4. Level of agreement. There is low traffic noise	Judimendi	118	4,14	1,709
	Sancho el Sabio	119	4,45	1,522
P20_5. Level of agreement. Walking is easy	Judimendi	119	5,33	1,042
	Sancho el Sabio	119	5,40	1,099
P20_6. Level of agreement. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Judimendi	112	3,89	1,365
	Sancho el Sabio	106	4,62	1,600
P20_7. Level of agreement. The prize of households is too high	Judimendi	98	4,79	1,372
	Sancho el Sabio	87	5,29	1,056
P20_8. Level of agreement. There are many antisocial behaviours in this area	Judimendi	108	2,86	1,585
	Sancho el Sabio	111	1,68	1,329
P20_10. Level of agreement. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Judimendi	119	4,87	1,305
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,30	,899
P20_11. Level of agreement. There is a lot of pollution	Judimendi	115	2,60	1,544
	Sancho el Sabio	109	2,05	1,524

Table 8.5a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding characteristics of superblocs: Sancho el Sabio, Judimendi

		T-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
P20_1. Level of agreement. They are attractive places	Equal variances assumed	235	,000	-,715
	Equal variances not assumed	218,216	,000	-,715
P20_2. Level of agreement. They are safe places	Equal variances assumed	233	,001	-,530
	Equal variances not assumed	232,187	,001	-,530
P20_3. Level of agreement. It is easy to access local shops	Equal variances assumed	234	,000	-1,102
	Equal variances not assumed	159,964	,000	-1,102
P20_7. Level of agreement. The prize of households is too high	Equal variances assumed	183	,006	-,502
	Equal variances not assumed	179,489	,006	-,502
P20_8. Level of agreement. There are many antisocial behaviours in this area	Equal variances assumed	217	,000	1,185
	Equal variances not assumed	208,529	,000	1,185
P20_10. Level of agreement. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Equal variances assumed	235	,004	-,423

Table 8.6a. T-Test mean difference significance regarding characteristics of superblocs: Judimendi – the rest of Vitoria-Gasteiz

	AREA OF THE SAMPLE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
P20_1. Level of agreement. They are attractive places	Judimendi	119	4,35	1,516
	Rest of Vitoria	422	4,49	1,392
P20_2. Level of agreement. They are safe places	Judimendi	117	4,44	1,282
	Rest of Vitoria	399	4,35	1,418
P20_3. Level of agreement. It is easy to access local shops	Judimendi	118	4,40	1,715
	Rest of Vitoria	416	4,67	1,387
P20_4. Level of agreement. There is low traffic noise	Judimendi	118	4,14	1,709
	Rest of Vitoria	402	4,70	1,347
P20_5. Level of agreement. Walking is easy	Judimendi	119	5,33	1,042
	Rest of Vitoria	427	5,37	,919
P20_6. Level of agreement. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Judimendi	112	3,89	1,365
	Rest of Vitoria	384	4,02	1,692
P20_7. Level of agreement. The prize of households is too high	Judimendi	98	4,79	1,372
	Rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.
P20_8. Level of agreement. There are many antisocial behaviours in this area	Judimendi	108	2,86	1,585
	Rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.
P20_10. Level of agreement. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Judimendi	119	4,87	1,305
	Rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.
P20_11. Level of agreement. There is a lot of pollution	Judimendi	115	2,60	1,544
	Rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.

Table 8.7a. Hierarchical regression analysis. Perceived attributes of place as predictors of the attitude towards superblocks. Model summary

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Estimation Error	Change statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	F Change sig.
1	,560 ^a	,314	,309	,99394	,314	67,695	1	148	,000
2	,639 ^b	,408	,400	,92600	,095	23,515	1	147	,000
3	,668 ^c	,446	,434	,89935	,037	9,843	1	146	,002
4	,681 ^d	,464	,450	,88723	,019	5,017	1	145	,027

- a. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Attractive places
- b. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Attractive places, P20_3. Easy to access local shops
- c. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Attractive places, P20_3. Easy to access local shops, P20_6. Image of city as innovative
- d. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Attractive places, P20_3. Easy to access local shops, P20_6. Image of city as innovative, P20_2. Safe

Table 8.8a. Hierarchical regression analysis. ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	66,878	1	66,878	67,695	,000 ^b
	Residual	146,213	148	,988		
	Total	213,090	149			
2	Regression	87,041	2	43,520	50,754	,000 ^c
	Residual	126,049	147	,857		
	Total	213,090	149			
3	Regression	95,002	3	31,667	39,152	,000 ^d
	Residual	118,088	146	,809		
	Total	213,090	149			
4	Regression	98,951	4	24,738	31,426	,000 ^e
	Residual	114,139	145	,787		
	Total	213,090	149			

- a. Dependent variable: General evaluation
- b. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Perceived attractiveness
- c. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Perceived attractiveness, P20_3. Easy to access local shops
- d. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Perceived attractiveness, P20_3. Easy to access local shops, P20_6. Contributed to the image of the city as innovative
- e. Predictor variables: (Constant), P20_1. Perceived attractiveness, P20_3. Easy to access local shops, P20_6. Contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P20_2. Safe places

Table 8.9a. Hierarchical regression analysis. Regression results

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,619	,283		5,715	,000
	P20_1. Perceived attractiveness	,481	,059	,560	8,228	,000
2	(Constant)	,757	,318		2,378	,019
	P20_1. Perceived attractiveness	,408	,057	,475	7,215	,000
	P20_3. Easy to access local shops	,249	,051	,319	4,849	,000
3	(Constant)	,538	,317		1,697	,092
	P20_1. Perceived attractiveness	,343	,059	,399	5,847	,000
	P20_3. Easy to access local shops	,220	,051	,282	4,335	,000
	P20_6. Contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,161	,051	,214	3,137	,002
4	(Constant)	,293	,331		,884	,378
	P20_1. Perceived attractiveness	,308	,060	,359	5,141	,000
	P20_3. Easy to access local shops	,188	,052	,241	3,607	,000
	P20_6. Contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,126	,053	,168	2,389	,018
	P20_2. Safe places	,152	,068	,166	2,240	,027

a. Dependent variable: General opinion

Table 8.10a. Mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Judimendi and Sancho el Sabio

Group statistics					
	AREA	N	Mean	Standard Dev.	Standard Mean Error
P20_1. They are attractive places	Judimendi	119	4,35	1,516	,139
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,07	1,130	,104
P20_2. They are safe places	Judimendi	117	4,44	1,282	,119
	Sancho el Sabio	118	4,97	1,219	,112
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Judimendi	118	4,40	1,715	,158
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,50	,748	,069
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Judimendi	118	4,14	1,709	,157
	Sancho el Sabio	119	4,45	1,522	,140
P20_5. Walking is easy	Judimendi	119	5,33	1,042	,096
	Sancho el Sabio	119	5,40	1,099	,101
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Judimendi	112	3,89	1,365	,129
	Sancho el Sabio	106	4,62	1,600	,155
P20_7. Housing prices are too high	Judimendi	98	4,79	1,372	,139
	Sancho el Sabio	87	5,29	1,056	,113
P20_8. There are many incivilities	Judimendi	108	2,86	1,585	,153
	Sancho el Sabio	111	1,68	1,329	,126
P20_10. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Judimendi	119	4,87	1,305	,120
	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,30	,899	,083
P20_11. There is a lot of air pollution	Judimendi	115	2,60	1,544	,144
	Sancho el Sabio	109	2,05	1,524	,146

Table 8.11a. T-test results for mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Judimendi and Sancho el Sabio

T Test for independent samples

		Levene Test for equal variances		T-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (bilateral)	Mean Difference	Mean diff. error	95% confidence interval	
									Inferior	Superior
P20_1. They are attractive places	Equal variances assumed	11,333	,001	-4,113	235	,000	-,715	,174	-1,057	-,372
	Equal variances not assumed			-4,118	218,216	,000	-,715	,174	-1,057	-,373
P20_2. They are safe places	Equal variances assumed	3,872	,050	-3,249	233	,001	-,530	,163	-,852	-,209
	Equal variances not assumed			-3,248	232,187	,001	-,530	,163	-,852	-,209
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Equal variances assumed	57,357	,000	-6,395	234	,000	-1,102	,172	-1,441	-,762
	Equal variances not assumed			-6,395	159,964	,000	-1,102	,172	-1,442	-,761
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Equal variances assumed	1,868	,173	-1,474	235	,142	-,310	,210	-,724	,104
	Equal variances not assumed			-1,473	231,450	,142	-,310	,210	-,724	,105
P20_5. Walking is easy	Equal variances assumed	,081	,776	-,545	236	,587	-,076	,139	-,349	,198
	Equal variances not assumed			-,545	235,333	,587	-,076	,139	-,349	,198
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Equal variances assumed	3,046	,082	-3,629	216	,000	-,730	,201	-1,126	-,333
	Equal variances not assumed			-3,614	206,664	,000	-,730	,202	-1,128	-,332
P20_7. Housing prices are too high	Equal variances assumed	7,636	,006	-2,761	183	,006	-,502	,182	-,860	-,143
	Equal variances not assumed			-2,804	179,489	,006	-,502	,179	-,855	-,149
P20_8. There are many incivilities	Equal variances assumed	7,762	,006	6,003	217	,000	1,185	,197	,796	1,575
	Equal variances not assumed			5,988	208,529	,000	1,185	,198	,795	1,576
P20_10. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Equal variances assumed	8,482	,004	-2,900	235	,004	-,423	,146	-,710	-,136
	Equal variances not assumed			-2,905	209,557	,004	-,423	,146	-,710	-,136
P20_11. There is a lot of air pollution	Equal variances assumed	1,689	,195	2,702	222	,007	,554	,205	,150	,958
	Equal variances not assumed			2,703	221,628	,007	,554	,205	,150	,958

Table 8.12a. Mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Judimendi and the rest of Vitoria

Group statistics					
	AREA	N	Mean	Standard Dev.	Standard Mean Error
P20_1. They are attractive places	Judimendi	119	4,35	1,516	,139
	The rest of Vitoria	422	4,49	1,392	,068
P20_2. They are safe places	Judimendi	117	4,44	1,282	,119
	The rest of Vitoria	399	4,35	1,418	,071
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Judimendi	118	4,40	1,715	,158
	The rest of Vitoria	416	4,67	1,387	,068
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Judimendi	118	4,14	1,709	,157
	The rest of Vitoria	402	4,70	1,347	,067
P20_5. Walking is easy	Judimendi	119	5,33	1,042	,096
	The rest of Vitoria	427	5,37	,919	,044
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Judimendi	112	3,89	1,365	,129
	The rest of Vitoria	384	4,02	1,692	,086
P20_7. Housing prices are too high	Judimendi	98	4,79	1,372	,139
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_8. There are many incivilities	Judimendi	108	2,86	1,585	,153
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_10. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Judimendi	119	4,87	1,305	,120
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_11. There is a lot of air pollution	Judimendi	115	2,60	1,544	,144
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.

a. T cannot be calculated as at least one group is empty

Table 8.13a. T-test results for mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Judimendi and the rest of Vitoria

T-test for independent samples

		Levene Test for equal variances		T-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (bilateral)	Mean Difference	Mean diff. error	95% confidence interval	
									Inferior	Superior
P20_1. They are attractive places	Equal variances assumed	1,033	,310	-,917	539	,359	-,135	,147	-,425	,154
	Equal variances not assumed			-,875	177,938	,383	-,135	,155	-,440	,170
P20_2. They are safe places	Equal variances assumed	1,284	,258	,599	514	,549	,088	,146	-,199	,374
	Equal variances not assumed			,633	206,393	,527	,088	,138	-,185	,360
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Equal variances assumed	10,953	,001	-1,766	532	,078	-,270	,153	-,570	,030
	Equal variances not assumed			-1,570	162,830	,118	-,270	,172	-,609	,070
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Equal variances assumed	15,255	,000	-3,778	518	,000	-,568	,150	-,864	-,273
	Equal variances not assumed			-3,322	161,986	,001	-,568	,171	-,906	-,231
P20_5. Walking is easy	Equal variances assumed	1,775	,183	-,455	544	,650	-,045	,098	-,237	,148
	Equal variances not assumed			-,423	172,418	,672	-,045	,105	-,253	,163
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Equal variances assumed	6,515	,011	-,734	494	,463	-,128	,174	-,471	,215
	Equal variances not assumed			-,825	219,968	,410	-,128	,155	-,434	,178

a. T cannot be calculated as at least one group is empty

Table 8.14a. Mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Sancho el Sabio and the rest of Vitoria

Group statistics					
	AREA	N	Mean	Standard Dev.	Standard Mean Error
P20_1. They are attractive places	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,07	1,130	,104
	The rest of Vitoria	422	4,49	1,392	,068
P20_2. They are safe places	Sancho el Sabio	118	4,97	1,219	,112
	The rest of Vitoria	399	4,35	1,418	,071
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,50	,748	,069
	The rest of Vitoria	416	4,67	1,387	,068
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Sancho el Sabio	119	4,45	1,522	,140
	The rest of Vitoria	402	4,70	1,347	,067
P20_5. Walking is easy	Sancho el Sabio	119	5,40	1,099	,101
	The rest of Vitoria	427	5,37	,919	,044
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Sancho el Sabio	106	4,62	1,600	,155
	The rest of Vitoria	384	4,02	1,692	,086
P20_7. Housing prices are too high	Sancho el Sabio	87	5,29	1,056	,113
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_8. There are many incivilities	Sancho el Sabio	111	1,68	1,329	,126
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_10. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	Sancho el Sabio	118	5,30	,899	,083
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.
P20_11. There is a lot of air pollution	Sancho el Sabio	109	2,05	1,524	,146
	The rest of Vitoria	0 ^a	.	.	.

a. T cannot be calculated as at least one group is empty

Table 8.15a. T-test results for mean differences between perceived place characteristics in Sancho el Sabioa and the rest of Vitoria

T-test for independent samples

		Levene Test for equal variances		T-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (bilateral)	Mean Difference	Mean diff. error	95% confidence interval	
									Inferior	Superior
P20_1. They are attractive places	Equal variances assumed	10,591	,001	4,156	538	,000	,580	,139	,306	,854
	Equal variances not assumed			4,669	225,956	,000	,580	,124	,335	,824
P20_2. They are safe places	Equal variances assumed	11,959	,001	4,286	515	,000	,618	,144	,335	,901
	Equal variances not assumed			4,652	219,102	,000	,618	,133	,356	,879
P20_3. It is easy to access local shops	Equal variances assumed	28,163	,000	6,258	532	,000	,832	,133	,571	1,093
	Equal variances not assumed			8,593	359,822	,000	,832	,097	,641	1,022
P20_4. There is low traffic noise	Equal variances assumed	4,777	,029	-1,784	519	,075	-,259	,145	-,543	,026
	Equal variances not assumed			-1,670	176,279	,097	-,259	,155	-,564	,047
P20_5. Walking is easy	Equal variances assumed	,749	,387	,311	544	,756	,031	,100	-,165	,227
	Equal variances not assumed			,281	166,677	,779	,031	,110	-,186	,248
P20_6. Superblocks have contributed to the image of city as innovative	Equal variances assumed	,285	,594	3,280	488	,001	,602	,183	,241	,962
	Equal variances not assumed			3,385	175,182	,001	,602	,178	,251	,953

Table 8.16a. Exploratory factor analysis for different needs in relation to superblocs In Vitoria-Gasteiz

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Factor			
	Health and wellbeing	Safety and comfort	Attractiveness	Reputation
P16_1. Level of importance. His/her health	,875			
P16_6. Level of importance. His/her quality of life	,806			
P16_2. Level of importance. Air quality in Vitoria-Gasteiz	,678			
P18_7. Level of importance. To have opportunities to communicate with the city council		,703		
P16_3. Level of importance. Road safety		,652		
P16_5. Level of importance. Easy parking		,622		
P18_5. Level of importance. Being involved in decisions that affect the city			,803	
P16_4. Level of importance. Living in an attractive neighbourhood			,743	
P18_3. Level of importance. Vitoria-Gasteiz being recognised as innovative				,825
P18_6. Level of importance. Availability of transparent information from the city council				,631

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations

Table 8.17a. Exploratory factor analysis for different needs in relation to superblocs In Vitoria. Principal Component Analysis

Total Variance Explained

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	% Cumulative
1	25,659	2,254	22,540	22,540
2	40,025	1,541	15,406	37,946
3	51,078	1,249	12,492	50,438
4	61,364	1,093	10,925	61,364
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				

Table 8.18a. Hierarchical regression analysis. Perceived attributes of place as predictors of the attitude towards superblocs in Barcelona. Model summary

Model Summary^f

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,675 ^a	,456	,455	1,480	,456	489,364	1	584	,000
2	,706 ^b	,498	,496	1,423	,042	48,846	1	583	,000
3	,710 ^c	,504	,502	1,415	,006	7,457	1	582	,007
4	,716 ^d	,512	,509	1,405	,008	9,125	1	581	,003
5	,719 ^e	,518	,513	1,398	,006	6,739	1	580	,010

- a. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative
 b. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality
 c. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy
 d. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy, P19. There are many incivilities
 e. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy, P19. There are many incivilities, P19. Easy access to local shops

Table 8.19a. Hierarchical regression analysis, Barcelona. ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1071,410	1	1071,410	489,364	,000 ^b
	Residual	1278,605	584	2,189		
	Total	2350,015	585			
2	Regression	1170,256	2	585,128	289,152	,000 ^c
	Residual	1179,760	583	2,024		
	Total	2350,015	585			
3	Regression	1185,180	3	395,060	197,388	,000 ^d
	Residual	1164,835	582	2,001		
	Total	2350,015	585			
4	Regression	1203,192	4	300,798	152,389	,000 ^e
	Residual	1146,823	581	1,974		
	Total	2350,015	585			
5	Regression	1216,364	5	243,273	124,464	,000 ^f
	Residual	1133,651	580	1,955		
	Total	2350,015	585			

- a. Dependent Variable: P12.1. General evaluation of the Sant Antoni/Poblenou interventions
 b. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative
 c. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality
 d. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy
 e. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy, P19. There are many incivilities
 f. Predictors: (Constant), P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative, P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality, P19. Walking is easy, P19. There are many incivilities, P19. Easy access to local shops

Table 8.20a. Hierarchical regression analysis, Barcelona. Regression coefficients

Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2,102	,153		13,732	,000	1,801	2,403		
	P19. Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,758	,034	,675	22,122	,000	,691	,825	1,000	1,000
2	(Constant)	,980	,218		4,501	,000	,552	1,408		
	Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,613	,039	,546	15,749	,000	,537	,690	,716	1,396
	P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	,361	,052	,242	6,989	,000	,259	,462	,716	1,396
3	(Constant)	1,642	,325		5,051	,000	1,004	2,281		
	Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,623	,039	,555	16,017	,000	,546	,699	,710	1,408
	P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	,393	,053	,264	7,461	,000	,289	,496	,680	1,470
	P19. Walking is easy	-,166	,061	-,084	-2,731	,007	-,285	-,047	,896	1,116
4	(Constant)	2,362	,401		5,886	,000	1,574	3,150		
	Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,623	,039	,555	16,141	,000	,547	,699	,710	1,408
	P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	,374	,053	,252	7,110	,000	,271	,478	,671	1,491
	P19. Walking is easy	-,194	,061	-,098	-3,172	,002	-,314	-,074	,876	1,142
	P19. There are many incivilities	-,115	,038	-,090	-3,021	,003	-,189	-,040	,944	1,059
5	(Constant)	1,830	,449		4,078	,000	,949	2,712		
	Superblocks have contributed to the image of the city as innovative	,623	,038	,555	16,226	,000	,548	,699	,710	1,408
	P19. There are pleasant spaces for leisure and conviviality	,354	,053	,238	6,686	,000	,250	,458	,656	1,523
	P19. Walking is easy	-,218	,061	-,111	-3,548	,000	-,339	-,097	,855	1,169
	P19. There are many incivilities	-,119	,038	-,093	-3,137	,002	-,193	-,044	,943	1,061
	P19. Easy access to local shops	,147	,057	,078	2,596	,010	,036	,259	,931	1,075

a. Dependent Variable: P12.1. General evaluation of the Sant Antoni/Poblenou interventions

Table 8.21a. Exploratory factor analysis for different needs in relation to superblocks in Barcelona

	Rotated Component Matrix ^a			
	Component			
	Environmental Quality	Participation	Health and wellbeing	Reputation
P17. Reduce environmental pollution	,821			
P17. Fighting climate change	,774			
P17. Living in a society where all have the same opportunities to access high-quality public spaces	,723			
P15. Air quality in Barcelona	,659			
P17. Transparent information from the city council		,910		
P17. To have opportunities to communicate with the city council		,662		
P17. Being involved in decisions that affect the city		,661		
P15. His/her quality of life			,855	
P15. His/her health			,808	
P17. Barcelona being recognised as innovative				,794

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations

Table 8.22a. Exploratory factor analysis for different needs in relation to superblocks In Barcelona. Principal Component Analysis

Component	Total Variance Explained			
	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	% Cumulative
1	20,348	2,415	17,252	17,252
2	32,590	1,735	12,393	29,645
3	42,103	1,643	11,737	41,381
4	50,668	1,292	9,229	50,610
5	58,223	1,066	7,613	58,223
6				

Appendix 9: Additional Tables for Aberdeen and Timișoara

Table 9.1a. Aberdeen survey sample profile

Variable	Valid N	Categories	% sample	Average
Age (years)	811			Mean= 51.1 (SD 15.8)
Age (bands)	811	16-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65-74 75+	2.0 17.5 21.2 14.5 14.8 27.7 2.2	
Gender	780	Male Female Prefer to self-describe	41.3 58.7 0	
Education	738	Degree level Lower	38.1 61.9	
Relationship status	818	Single – Married/in a partnership Separated/divorced/widowed	24.8 56.1 19.1	
Household size	822			Mean= 2.15 (SD 1.13)
Children in household	821	Households with children under 16 Households without children under 16	24.2 75.8	
Dwelling type	786	Detached Semi-detached Terraced Flat/maisonette/apartment	14.1 23.7 18.6 43.6	
Tenure	817	Owner occupied (in shared ownership) Social rented Private rented Live rent free	72 22.5 4.5 1	
Central heating type	796	None Gas Electric Oil Solid Other	0.9 89.7 6.5 1.1 0.1 1.6	
Gross household income	755			Median = £27,000 - £32, 999
SIMD quintile	838	SIMD 1 SIMD 2 SIMD 3 SIMD 4 SIMD 5	14.6 15.5 22.0 21.6 26.4	

Heating hardship scale (Aberdeen)

A scale to measure 'heating hardship' was created using responses to the following items. Responses were made on a 7-point Likert-type scale (1=strongly disagree to 7=strongly agree).

1. My heating bills have increased
2. I could afford to keep my home warm*
3. I have had to choose between keeping my home warm and buying food or essential for myself or my family
4. My heating system was able to keep my home warm*
5. My home sometimes felt uncomfortably cold in the winter

* Item coding reversed.

Selection of data sources for secondary data (Timișoara)

We supplemented survey data with relevant data from selected secondary sources to inform our understanding of choice behaviours. This included data already gathered during previous steps in the project and selected/extracted relevant information, such as Actor Description worksheet with the identification of stakeholders and subpopulations, as well as their social networks (Task 6.1). Also, we included six individual in-depth interviews of key-informants from Timișoara (innovation agents, policymakers and stakeholders), aimed at obtaining insights on social dynamics, bright and dark sides of energy transformations at the local sphere (T3.2, T4.4). Both qualitative data sets – systematic interviews and individual in-depth interviews respect the principle of privacy and anonymity. Second, we extracted relevant information for the case from previously created SMARTEES deliverables, such as: 6.1, 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, and 7.1. This information is also qualitative. Third, we searched online for any news articles on energy production or consumption in Timișoara, a process which yielded seven news articles, representing qualitative data to complement the insights on local specificities. Next, we searched other relevant data on web pages of national and local authorities in form of reports related to energy behaviors, which yielded other three qualitative data sources on energy efficiency trends and policies in Romania (Romanian Energy Regulatory Authority), Romania Country Commercial Guide for energy, as well as a report from EUFORIE H2020 project on consumers and energy efficiency. Finally, we identified what information is needed but currently missing, and obtained a list of datasets (i.e., spatial, quantitative) to retrieve from local authorities or partners, such as Spatial data for heat network pipes and residences, Household spatial data, Energy rates and tariffs, Grants and funding data, Fuel debt data, Home Energy Timișoara City Council loan data, District Heating Loan data, Home Energy Efficiency Programmes data, Rent and mortgage data, Repair, upkeep and installation of systems in the heat network, Repair, upkeep and installation of systems not in the heat network, Local air quality, and Daily average humidity and temperature.

Scale items (Timișoara)

Environmentally responsible behavior (ERB) was defined using a set of four items:

- I1. When I brush my teeth, face, or when I shave, I do not let water flow constantly,
- I2. When I do my shopping, I do not buy more than I intended,
- I3. I selectively collect waste
- I4. No throw away old clothes, but I use it for other purposes).

Responsible energy behavior (REB) is a variable defined by five items:

- I1. If I don't really need heat, I turn it off,
- I2. I turn off the appliances when not in use,

- 13. Turn off the light every time I leave the room,
- 14. During the cold season, when I turn on the heat, I remove objects that obstruct the radiators,
- 15. During the cold season, if it is warmer in the house than I would like, I adjust the temperature (instead of opening the window).

Environmental concern (EC) is operationalized by the following items:

- (11. Energy is too expensive for many people in Timișoara,
- 12. Timișoara is too dependent on the use of energy generated by fossil fuels such as oil, gas and coal,
- 13. Climate change,
- 14. Energy disruptions in Timișoara.

Table 9.2a. Importance of different information sources with respect to energy related decisions

Information source	Age ^a		Gender ^b		Education ^c		SIMD ^d
	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen
	Spearman rho	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Spearman's rho
Household	-.213**	n/s	n/s	14182.5** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Neighbours	n/s	n/s	n/s	15399* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Family	-.145**	n/s	57699* (+)	15399.5* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Friends	-.152**	n/s	56161** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Colleagues/fellow students	-.259**	n/s	46772** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Community groups	-.122**	n/s	54055* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Energy supplier	-.074*	n/s	n/s	14793** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
City council/municipality	-.106**	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Energy advice orgs	n/s	n/s	55501** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
National government	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Social media	-.250**	n/s	54024.5* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
Local news	-.081*	14129.5** (+)	52867.5** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
National news	n/s	n/a	52313.5** (+)	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s
Local schools	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a	20019.5* (-)	n/a
Local merchants	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a	20038.5* (-)	n/a

Importance was scored from 1 (=not at all important) to 7 (extremely important)

a = Age operationalised as continuous variable in Aberdeen case, dichotomous (over 35s vs. under 35s) in Timișoara due to differences in sample composition. '(+)' indicates higher scores amongst over 35s in the Timișoara case.

b = Comparison between 0=male and 1=female in both cases. Respondents could also select 'prefer to self-describe', however this was selected by no respondents. '(+)' indicates female scores higher than male.

c = Comparison between degree level vs. other in Aberdeen and high education level (university) vs. medium education level (high school) in Timișoara. '(+)' indicates higher scores in highest educated group.

d = Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation quintile – min 1=most deprived to max 5=least deprived. Relevant for Aberdeen case only.

Table 9.3a. Trust in different information sources with respect to energy related decisions.

Information source (trust scored 1-7)	Age ^a		Gender ^b		Education ^c		SIMD ^d
	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen	Timișoara	Aberdeen
	Spearman rho	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Mann-Whitney U	Spearman's rho
Household	-.106**	n/s	n/s	13584.5** (+)	n/s	n/s	.086*
Neighbours	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s	.124**
Family	n/s	n/s	59024** (+)	14761.5** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Friends	-.121**	n/s	57306** (+)	14491** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Colleagues/fellow students	-.314**	n/s	45764** (+)	n/s	41270** (+)	n/s	.149**
Community groups	-.160**	n/s	50266** (+)	n/s	51573* (+)	n/s	.086*
Energy supplier	n/s	n/s	57248** (+)	15557* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
City council/municipality	-.079*	n/s	55192** (+)	15526* (+)	54861* (+)	n/s	n/s
Energy advice orgs	n/s	n/s	53288.5** (+)	n/s	53498* (+)	n/s	n/s
National government	-.124**	n/s	54048.5** (+)	n/s	52764.5** (+)	n/s	n/s
Social media	-.245**	n/s	51000** (+)	15234.5* (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s
Local news	-.109**	n/s	53477.5** (+)	n/s	n/s	n/s	n/s
National news	-.089*	n/a	52328.5** (+)	n/a	n/s	n/a	.082*
Local schools	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a
Local merchants	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a	n/s	n/a

Trust was scored from 0 (=not at all) to 6 (a great deal)

a = Age operationalised as continuous variable in Aberdeen case, dichotomous (over 35s vs. under 35s) in Timișoara due to differences in sample composition. '(+)' indicates higher scores amongst over 35s in the Timișoara case.

b = Comparison between 0=male and 1=female in both cases. Respondents could also select 'prefer to self-describe', however this was selected by no respondents. '(+)' indicates female scores higher than male.

c = Comparison between degree level vs. other in Aberdeen and high education level (university) vs. medium education level (high school) in Timișoara. '(+)' indicates higher scores in highest educated group.

d = Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation quintile – min 1=most deprived to max 5=least deprived. Relevant for Aberdeen case only.